
SUEWS Documentation

Release v2018c

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1	Introduction	3
2	Parameterisations and sub-models within SUEWS	5
2.1	Net all-wave radiation, Q^*	5
2.2	Anthropogenic heat flux, Q_F	5
2.3	Storage heat flux, ΔQ_S	6
2.4	Turbulent heat fluxes, Q_H and Q_E	6
2.5	Water balance	6
2.6	Snowmelt	7
2.7	Convective boundary layer	7
2.8	Thermal comfort	7
2.9	Surface Diagnostics	7
3	Preparing to run the model	9
3.1	Preparatory reading	9
3.2	Decide what type of model run you are interested in	10
3.3	Download the program and example data files	10
3.4	Run the model for example data	10
3.5	Preparation of data	11
3.6	Run the model for your site	14
3.7	Analyse the output	14
3.8	Summary of files	14
3.9	Get in contact	15
4	Input files	17
4.1	RunControl.nml	17
4.2	SUEWS Site Information	30
4.3	Initial Conditions file	136
4.4	Meteorological Input File	145
4.5	CBL input files	147
4.6	ESTM-related files	150
4.7	SOLWEIG input files	153
4.8	SUEWS input converter	158
5	Output files	165
5.1	Runtime diagnostic information	165
5.2	Model output files	166

6	Troubleshooting	175
6.1	How to report an issue of this manual?	175
6.2	How to join your email-list?	175
6.3	How to create a directory?	175
6.4	How to unzip a file	175
6.5	A text editor	175
6.6	Command prompt	176
6.7	Day of year [DOY]	176
6.8	ESTM output	176
6.9	First things to Check if the program seems to have problems	176
7	Recent publications	179
8	SUEWS-related Software	181
8.1	SuPy	181
8.2	SUEWS and UMEP	181
8.3	Differences between SUEWS, LUMPS and FRAISE	182
8.4	FRAISE Flux Ratio – Active Index Surface Exchange	183
9	Tutorials	185
9.1	Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Introduction	185
9.2	Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Advanced	193
9.3	Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Spatial	202
9.4	Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS and WUDAPT	217
10	Development, Suggestions and Support	225
10.1	Coding Guidelines	225
10.2	Suggestions and Support	227
11	Benchmark Report	229
12	Version History	231
12.1	Version 2018c (released on 21 February 2019)	231
12.2	Version 2018b (released 17 December 2018)	231
12.3	Version 2018a (released 2 August 2018)	232
12.4	Version 2017b (released 2 August 2017)	233
12.5	Version 2017a (Feb 2017)	233
12.6	Version 2016a (released 21 June 2016)	234
12.7	Version 2014b (released 8 October 2014)	234
12.8	Version 2014a.1 (released 26 February 2014)	235
12.9	Version 2014a (released 21 February 2014)	235
12.10	Version 2013a	236
12.11	Version 2012b	236
12.12	Version 2012a	236
12.13	Version 2011b	237
13	Acknowledgements	239
14	Notation	241
	References	245

- **How to get SUEWS?**

- **Latest release:**

- The **latest formal** release of SUEWS is *Version 2018c (released on 21 February 2019)* and can be downloaded via our [Zenodo repository](#) (a sample input dataset is included in the release archive).

- **Previous releases:**

- Previous releases can be downloaded via our [GitHub page](#).

- **How to use SUEWS?**

- **For existing users:**

- Overview of changes in this version, see *Version 2018c (released on 21 February 2019)*. If these changes impact your existing simulations, please see appropriate parts of the manual. It may be necessary to adapt some of your input files for for the current version.

Tip: A helper python script, *SUEWS table converter*, is provided to help facilitate the conversion of input files between different SUEWS versions.

Additionally, the manuals for previous versions can be accessed in respective sections under *Version History*.

- **For new users:**

- Before performing SUEWS simulations, new users should read the overview *Introduction*, then follow the steps in *Preparing to run the model* to prepare *input files* for SUEWS.

- Note there are tutorials learning about running SUEWS available *the tutorial*.

- **How has SUEWS been used?**

- The scientific details and application examples of SUEWS can be found in *Recent publications*.

- **How to cite SUEWS?**

Tip: Visit the repositories below for different citation styles.

- Software:

- Sun Ting, Järvi Leena, Grimmond Sue, Lindberg Fredrik, Li Zhenkun, Tang Yihao, Ward Helen: (2019, February 21). SUEWS: Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (Version 2018c). Zenodo.

- Manual:

- Sun Ting, Järvi Leena, Grimmond Sue, Lindberg Fredrik, Li Zhenkun, Tang Yihao, Ward Helen: (2019, February 21). SUEWS Documentation (Version 2018c). Zenodo.

- **How to support SUEWS?**

1. *Cite SUEWS* appropriately in your work.
2. Contribute to the *development*.
3. Report issues via the [GitHub page](#).
4. Provide *suggestions and feedback*.

Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (**SUEWS**) (Järvi et al. 2011 [J11], Ward et al. 2016 [W16]) is able to simulate the urban radiation, energy and water balances using only commonly measured meteorological variables and information about the surface cover. SUEWS utilizes an evaporation-interception approach (Grimmond et al. 1991 [G91]), similar to that used in forests, to model evaporation from urban surfaces.

Fig. 1.1: Overview of SUEWS

The model uses seven surface types: paved, buildings, evergreen trees/shrubs, deciduous trees/shrubs, grass, bare soil and water. The surface state for each surface type at each time step is calculated from the running water balance of the canopy where the evaporation is calculated from the Penman-Monteith equation. The soil moisture below each surface type (excluding water) is taken into account.

Horizontal movement of water above and below ground level is allowed. The user can specify the model time-step, but 5 min is strongly recommended. The main output file is provided at a resolution of 60 min by default. The model provides the radiation and energy balance components, surface and soil wetness, surface and soil runoff and the drainage for each surface. Timestamps refer to the end of the averaging period.

Model applicability: SUEWS is a neighbourhood-scale or local-scale model.

Fig. 1.2: The seven surface types considered in SUEWS

Parameterisations and sub-models within SUEWS

2.1 Net all-wave radiation, Q^*

There are several options for modelling or using observed radiation components depending on the data available. As a minimum, SUEWS requires incoming shortwave radiation to be provided.

1. Observed net all-wave radiation can be provided as input instead of being calculated by the model.
2. Observed incoming shortwave and incoming longwave components can be provided as input, instead of incoming longwave being calculated by the model.
3. Other data can be provided as input, such as cloud fraction (see options in *RunControl.nml*).
4. **NARP** (Net All-wave Radiation Parameterization, Offerle et al. 2003 [*O2003*], Loridan et al. 2011 [*L2011*]) scheme calculates outgoing shortwave and incoming and outgoing longwave radiation components based on incoming shortwave radiation, temperature, relative humidity and surface characteristics (albedo, emissivity).

2.2 Anthropogenic heat flux, Q_F

1. Two simple anthropogenic heat flux sub-models exist within SUEWS:
 - Järvi et al. (2011) [*J11*] approach, based on heating and cooling degree days and population density (allows distinction between weekdays and weekends).
 - Loridan et al. (2011) [*L2011*] approach, based on a linear piece-wise relation with air temperature.
2. Pre-calculated values can be supplied with the meteorological forcing data, either derived from knowledge of the study site, or obtained from other models, for example:
 - **LUCY** (Allen et al. 2011 [*lucy*], Lindberg et al. 2013 [*lucy2*]). A new version has been now included in UMEP. To distinguish it is referred to as **LQF**
 - **GreaterQF** (Iamarino et al. 2011 [*I11*]). A new version has been now included in UMEP. To distinguish it is referred to as **GQF**

2.3 Storage heat flux, ΔQ_s

1. Three sub-models are available to estimate the storage heat flux:
 - **OHM** (Objective Hysteresis Model, Grimmond et al. 1991 [*G91OHM*], Grimmond & Oke 1999a [*GO99QS*], 2002 [*GO2002*]). Storage heat flux is calculated using empirically-fitted relations with net all-wave radiation and the rate of change in net all-wave radiation.
 - **AnOHM** (Analytical Objective Hysteresis Model, Sun et al. 2017 [*AnOHM17*]). OHM approach using analytically-derived coefficients. **Not recommended in this version.**
 - **ESTM** (Element Surface Temperature Method, Offerle et al. 2005 [*OGF2005*]). Heat transfer through urban facets (roof, wall, road, interior) is calculated from surface temperature measurements and knowledge of material properties. **Not recommended in this version.**
2. Alternatively, ‘observed’ storage heat flux can be supplied with the meteorological forcing data.

2.4 Turbulent heat fluxes, Q_H and Q_E

1. **LUMPS** (Local-scale Urban Meteorological Parameterization Scheme, Grimmond & Oke 2002 [*GO2002*]) provides a simple means of estimating sensible and latent heat fluxes based on the proportion of vegetation in the study area.
2. **SUEWS** adopts a more biophysical approach to calculate the latent heat flux; the sensible heat flux is then calculated as the residual of the energy balance. The initial estimate of stability is based on the LUMPS calculations of sensible and latent heat flux. Future versions will have alternative sensible heat and storage heat flux options.

Sensible and latent heat fluxes from both LUMPS and SUEWS are provided in the *Output files*. Whether the turbulent heat fluxes are calculated using LUMPS or SUEWS can have a major impact on the results. For SUEWS, an appropriate surface conductance parameterisation is also critical [*J11*] [*W16*]. For more details see *Differences between SUEWS, LUMPS and FRAISE*.

2.5 Water balance

The running water balance at each time step is based on the urban water balance model of Grimmond et al. (1986) [*G86*] and urban evaporation-interception scheme of Grimmond and Oke (1991) [*G91*].

- Precipitation is a required variable in the meteorological forcing file.
- Irrigation can be modelled [*J11*] or observed values can be provided if data are available.
- Drainage equations and coefficients to use must be specified in the input files.
- Soil moisture can be calculated by the model.
- Runoff is permitted:
 - between surface types within each model grid
 - between model grids (**Not available in this version.**)
 - to deep soil
 - to pipes.

2.6 Snowmelt

The snowmelt model is described in Järvi et al. (2014) [*Leena2014*]. Changes since v2016a: 1) previously all surface states could freeze in 1-h time step, now the freezing surface state is calculated similarly as melt water and can freeze within the snow pack. 2) Snowmelt-related coefficients have also slightly changed (see *SUEWS_Snow.txt*).

2.7 Convective boundary layer

A convective boundary layer (CBL) slab model (Cleugh and Grimmond 2001 [*CG2001*]) calculates the CBL height, temperature and humidity during daytime (Onomura et al. 2015 [*Shiho2015*]).

2.8 Thermal comfort

SOLWEIG (Solar and longwave environmental irradiance geometry model, Lindberg et al. 2008 [*FL2008*], Lindberg and Grimmond 2011 [*FL2011*]) is a 2D radiation model to estimate mean radiant temperature.

Fig. 2.1: Overview of scales. Source: Onomura et al. (2015) [*Shiho2015*]

2.9 Surface Diagnostics

A MOST-based surface diagnostics module is implemented in 2017b for calculating the surface level diagnostics, including:

- T2: air temperature at 2 m agl

- Q2: air specific humidity at 2 m agl
- U10: wind speed at 10 m agl

The details for formulation of these diagnostics can be found in equations 2.54, 2.55 and 2.56 in Brutsaert (2005) [\[B05\]](#)

Preparing to run the model

The following is to help with the model setup. Note that there are also starting [tutorials](#) for the version of SUEWS in UMEP. The version there is the same (i.e. the executable) as the standalone version so you can swap to that later once you have some familiarity.

3.1 Preparatory reading

Read the manual and relevant papers (and references therein):

- Järvi L, Grimmond CSB & Christen A (2011) The Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS): Evaluation in Los Angeles and Vancouver. *J. Hydrol.* 411, 219-237. doi:[10.1016/j.jhydrol.2011.10.00](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2011.10.00)
- Järvi L, Grimmond CSB, Taka M, Nordbo A, Setälä H & Strachan IB (2014) Development of the Surface Urban Energy and Water balance Scheme (SUEWS) for cold climate cities. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 7, 1691-1711. doi:[10.5194/gmd-7-1691-2014](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-7-1691-2014)
- Ward HC, Kotthaus S, Järvi L and Grimmond CSB (2016) Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS): development and evaluation at two UK sites. *Urban Climate* 18, 1-32. doi:[10.1016/j.uclim.2016.05.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2016.05.001)

See other publications with example applications

3.2 Decide what type of model run you are interested in

	Available in this release
LUMPS	Yes – not standalone
SUEWS at a point or for an individual area	Yes
SUEWS for multiple grids or areas	Yes
SUEWS with Boundary Layer (BL)	No
SUEWS with snow	Yes
SUEWS with SOLWEIG	No
SUEWS with SOLWEIG and BL	No

3.3 Download the program and example data files

Visit the [website](#) to receive a link to download the program and example data files. Select the appropriate compiled version of the model to download. For windows there is an installation version which will put the programs and all the files into the appropriate place. There is also a version linked to QGIS: [UMEP](#).

Note, as the definition of long double precision varies between computers (e.g. Mac vs Windows) slightly different results may occur in the output files.

Test/example files are given for the London KCL site, 2011 data (denoted Kc11)

In the following, *SS* is the site code (e.g. Kc), *ss* the grid ID, *YYYY* the year and *tt* the time interval.

Filename	Description	Input/output
SSss_data.txt	Meteorological input	Input file (60-min)
SSss_YYYY_data_5.txt	Meteorological input	Input file (5-min)
InitialConditionsSSss	Initial conditions	Input - _YYYY.nml(+) file
SUEWS_SiteInfo_SSss.x	Spreadsheet	Input lsm containing all other input information
RunControl.nml	Sets model run	Input (located in options main directory)
SS_Filechoices.txt	Summary of model run	Output options
SSss_YYYY_5.txt	(Optional) 5-min	Output resolution output file
SSss_YYYY_60.txt	60-min resolution	Output output file
SSss_DailyState.txt	Daily state variables	Output (all years in one file)

(+) There is a second file `InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY_EndOfRun.nml` or `InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY+1.nml` in the input directory. At the end of the run, and at the end of each year of the run, these files are written out so that this information could be used to initialize further model runs.

3.4 Run the model for example data

Before running the model with your own data, check that you get the same results as the test run example files provided. Copy the example output files elsewhere so you can compare the results. When you run the program it will write over the supplied files.

To run the model you can use **Command Prompt** (in the directory where the programme is located type the model name) or just double click the executable file.

Please see [Troubleshooting](#) if you have problems running the model.

3.5 Preparation of data

The information required to run SUEWS for your site consists of:

1. Continuous *meteorological forcing data* for the entire period to be modelled without gaps. If you need help preparing the data you can use some of the [UMEP](#) tools.
2. Knowledge of the *surface and soil conditions immediately prior to the first model timestep*. If these initial conditions are unknown, model spinup can help; i.e. run the model and use the output at the end of the run to infer the conditions at the start of the main run).
3. The *location of the site* (latitude, longitude, altitude).
4. Information about the *characteristics of the surface*, including land cover, heights of buildings and trees, radiative characteristics (e.g. albedo, emissivity), drainage characteristics, soil characteristics, snow characteristics, phenological characteristics (e.g. seasonal cycle of LAI).
5. Information about *human behaviour*, including energy use and water use (e.g. for irrigation or street cleaning) and snow clearing (if applicable). The anthropogenic energy use and water use may be provided as a time series in the meteorological forcing file if these data are available or modelled based on parameters provided to the model, including population density, hourly and weekly profiles of energy and water use, information about the proportion of properties using irrigation and the type of irrigation (automatic or manual).

It is particularly important to ensure the following input information is appropriate and representative of the site:

- Fractions of different land cover types and (less so) heights of buildings [[W16](#)]
- Accurate meteorological forcing data, particularly precipitation and incoming shortwave radiation [[Ko17](#)]
- Initial soil moisture conditions [[Best2014](#)]
- Anthropogenic heat flux parameters, particularly if there are considerable energy emissions from transport, buildings, metabolism, etc [[W16](#)]
- External water use (if irrigation or street cleaning occurs)
- Snow clearing (if running the snow option)
- Surface conductance parameterisation [[J11](#)] [[W16](#)]

SUEWS can be run either for an individual area or for multiple areas. There is no requirement for the areas to be of any particular shape but here we refer to them as model ‘grids’.

3.5.1 Preparation of site characteristics and model parameters

The area to be modelled is described by a set of characteristics that are specified in the [SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt](#) file. Each row corresponds to one model grid for one year (i.e. running a single grid over three years would require three rows; running two grids over two years would require four rows). Characteristics are often selected by a code for a particular set of conditions. For example, a specific soil type (links to [SUEWS_Soil.txt](#)) or characteristics of deciduous trees in a particular region (links to [SUEWS_Veg.txt](#)). The intent is to build a library of characteristics for different types of urban areas. The codes are specified by the user, must be integer values and must be unique within the first column of each input file, otherwise the model will return an error. (Note in [SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt](#) the first column is labelled ‘Grid’ and can contain repeat values for different years.) See [Input files](#) for details. Note [UMEP](#) maybe helpful for components of this.

Land cover

For each grid, the land cover must be classified using the following surface types:

Classification	Surface type	File where characteristics are specified
Non-vegetated	Paved surfaces	<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>
	Building	<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>
	Bare soil	<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>
Vegetation	Evergreen trees	<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>
	Deciduous trees	<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>
	Grass	<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>
Water	Water	<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>
Snow	Snow	<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>

The surface cover fractions (i.e. proportion of the grid taken up by each surface) must be specified in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*. The surface cover fractions are **critical**, so make certain that the different surface cover fractions are appropriate for your site.

For some locations, land cover information may be already available (e.g. from various remote sensing resources). If not, websites like Bing Maps and Google Maps allow you to see aerial images of your site and can be used to estimate the relative proportion of each land cover type. If detailed spatial datasets are available, UMEP allows for a direct link to a GIS environment using QGIS.

Anthropogenic heat flux (Q_F)

You can either model Q_F within SUEWS or provide it as an input.

- To model it population density is needed as an input for LUMPS and SUEWS to calculate Q_F .
- If you have no information about the population of the site we recommend that you use the LUCY model [*lucy*] [*lucy2*] to estimate the anthropogenic heat flux which can then be provided as input SUEWS along with the meteorological forcing data.

Alternatively, you can use the updated version of LUCY called LQF, which is included in UMEP.

Other information

The surface cover fractions and population density can have a major impact on the model output. However, it is important to consider the suitability of all parameters for your site. Using inappropriate parameters may result in the model returning an error or, worse, generating output that is simply not representative of your site. Please read the section on *Input files*. Recommended or reasonable ranges of values are suggested for some parameters, along with important considerations for how to select appropriate values for your site.

Data Entry

To create the series of input text files describing the characteristics of your site, there are three options:

1. Data can be entered directly into the input text files. The example (.txt) files provide a template to create your own files which can be edited with *A text editor* directly.
2. Data can be entered into the spreadsheet **SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm** and the input text files generated by running the macro.
3. Use UMEP.

To run the xlsm macro: Enter the data for your site into the xlsm spreadsheet **SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm** and then use the macro to create the text files which will appear the same directory.

If there is a problem

- Make sure none of the text files to be generated are open.
- It is recommended to close the spreadsheet before running the actual model code.

Note that in all txt files:

- The first two rows are headers. The first row is the column number; the second row is the column name.
- The names and order of the columns should not be altered from the templates, as these are checked by the model and errors will be returned if particular columns cannot be found.
- Since v2017a it is no longer necessary for the meteorological forcing data to have two rows with -9 in column 1 as their last two rows.
- “!” indicates a comment, so any text following “!” on the same line will not be read by the model.
- If data are unavailable or not required, enter the value -999 in the correct place in the input file.
- Ensure the units are correct for all input information. See *Input files* for a description of parameters.

In addition to these text files, the following files are also needed to run the model.

3.5.2 Preparation of the RunControl file

In the RunControl.nml file the site name (SS) and directories for the model input and output are given. This means **before running** the model (even the with the example datasets) you must either

1. open the RunControl.nml file and edit the input and output file paths and the site name (with a *A text editor*) so that they are correct for your setup, or
2. create the directories specified in the RunControl.nml file

From the given site identification the model identifies the input files and generates the output files. For example if you specify:

```
FileOutputPath = "C:\FolderName\SUEWSOutput\"
```

and use site code SS the model creates an output file:

```
C:\FolderName\SUEWSOutput\SSss_YYYY_TT.txt
```

Note: remember to add the last backslash in windows and slash in Linux/Mac

If the file paths are not correct the program will return an error when run and write the error to the *Error messages: problems.txt* file.

3.5.3 Preparation of the Meteorological forcing data

The model time-step is specified in *RunControl.nml* (5 min is highly recommended). If meteorological forcing data are not available at this resolution, SUEWS has the option to downscale (e.g. hourly) data to the time-step required. See details about the *SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt* to learn more about choices of data input. Each grid can have its own meteorological forcing file, or a single file can be used for all grids. The forcing data should be representative of the local-scale, i.e. collected (or derived) above the height of the roughness elements (buildings and trees).

3.5.4 Preparation of the InitialConditions file

Information about the surface state and meteorological conditions just before the start of the run are provided in the Initial Conditions file. At the very start of the run, each grid can have its own Initial Conditions file, or a single file can be used for all grids. For details see *Initial Conditions file*.

3.6 Run the model for your site

To run the model you can use **Command Prompt** (in the directory where the programme is located type the model name) or just double click the executable file.

Please see *Troubleshooting* if you have problems running the model.

3.7 Analyse the output

It is a good idea to perform initial checks that the model output looks reasonable.

Characteristic	Things to check
Leaf area index	<p>Does the phenology look appropriate?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • what does the seasonal cycle of leaf area index (LAI) look like? • Are the leaves on the trees at approximately the right time of the year?
Kdown	<p>Is the timing of diurnal cycles correct for the incoming solar radiation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although Kdown is a required input, it is also included in the output file. It is a good idea to check that the timing of Kdown in the output file is appropriate, as problems can indicate errors with the timestamp, incorrect time settings or problems with the disaggregation. In particular, make sure the sign of the longitude is specified correctly in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>. • Checking solar angles (zenith and azimuth) can also be a useful check that the timing is correct.
Albedo	<p>Is the bulk albedo correct?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is critical because a small error has an impact on all the fluxes (energy and hydrology). • If you have measurements of outgoing shortwave radiation compare these with the modelled values. • How do the values compare to literature values for your area?

3.8 Summary of files

The table below lists the files required to run SUEWS and the output files produced. SS is the two-letter code (specified in RunControl) representing the site name, ss is the grid identification (integer values between 0 and 2,147,483,647 (largest 4-byte integer)) and YYYY is the year. TT is the resolution of the input/output file and tt is the model time-step.

The last column indicates whether the files are needed/produced once per run (1/run), or once per day (1/day), for each year (1/year) or for each grid (1/grid):

```
[B] indicates files used with the CBL part of SUEWS (BLUEWS) and therefore are only needed/  
↳produced if this option is selected  
[E] indicates files associated with ESTM storage heat flux models and therefore are only needed/  
↳produced if this option is selected
```

3.9 Get in contact

For issues met in using SUEWS, we recommend the following ways to get in contact with the developers and the SUEWS community:

1. Report issues on [our GitHub page](#).
2. Ask for help by joining [the Email-list for SUEWS](#).

SUEWS allows you to input a large number of parameters to describe the characteristics of your site. You should not assume that the example values provided in files or in the tables below are appropriate. Values marked with 'MD' are examples of recommended values (see the suggested references to help decide how appropriate these are for your site/model domain); values marked with 'MU' need to be set (i.e. changed from the example) for your site/model domain.

4.1 RunControl.nml

The file **RunControl.nml** is a namelist that specifies the options for the model run. It must be located in the same directory as the executable file.

A sample file of **RunControl.nml** looks like

```
&RunControl
CBLUse=0
SnowUse=0
SOLWEIGUse=0
NetRadiationMethod=3
EmissionsMethod=2
StorageHeatMethod=3
OHMIncQF=0
StabilityMethod=2
RoughLenHeatMethod=2
RoughLenMomMethod=2
SMDMethod=0
WaterUseMethod=0
FileCode='Saeve'
FileInputPath='./Input/'
FileOutputPath='./Output/'
MultipleMetFiles=0
MultipleInitFiles=0
MultipleESTMFiles=1
```

(continues on next page)

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```
KeepTstepFilesIn=1
KeepTstepFilesOut=1
WriteOutOption=2
ResolutionFilesOut=3600
Tstep=300
ResolutionFilesIn=3600
ResolutionFilesInESTM=3600
DisaggMethod=1
RainDisaggMethod=100
DisaggMethodESTM=1
SuppressWarnings=1
KdownZen=0
diagnose=0
/
```

Note:

- In *Linux* and *Mac*, please add an empty line after the end slash.
 - The file is not case-sensitive.
 - The parameters and variables can appear in any order.
-

The parameters and their setting instructions are provided through the links below:

- *Scheme options*
 - *CBLuse*
 - *SnowUse*
 - *SOLWEIGUse*
 - *NetRadiationMethod*
 - *EmissionsMethod*
 - *StorageHeatMethod*
 - *OHMIncQF*
 - *StabilityMethod*
 - *RoughLenHeatMethod*
 - *RoughLenMomMethod*
 - *SMDMethod*
 - *WaterUseMethod*
- *File related options*
 - *FileCode*
 - *FileInputPath*
 - *FileOutputPath*
 - *MultipleMetFiles*
 - *MultipleInitFiles*
 - *MultipleESTMFiles*
 - *KeepTstepFilesIn*
 - *KeepTstepFilesOut*
 - *WriteOutOption*
 - *SuppressWarnings*
- *Time related options*
 - *Tstep*
 - *ResolutionFilesIn*

- *ResolutionFilesInESTM*
- *ResolutionFilesOut*
- *Options related to disaggregation of input data*
 - *DisaggMethod*
 - *KdownZen*
 - *RainDisaggMethod*
 - *RainAmongN*
 - *MultRainAmongN*
 - *MultRainAmongNUpperI*
 - *DisaggMethodESTM*
- *netCDF related options (Not available in this version.)*
 - *ncMode*
 - *nRow*
 - *nCol*

4.1.1 Scheme options

CBLuse

Warning: Not available in this version.

Requirement Required

Description Determines whether a CBL slab model is used to calculate temperature and humidity.

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	CBL model not used. SUEWS and LUMPS use temperature and humidity provided in the meteorological forcing file.
1	CBL model is used to calculate temperature and humidity used in SUEWS and LUMPS.

SnowUse

Requirement Required

Description Determines whether the snow part of the model runs.

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	Snow calculations are not performed.
1	Snow calculations are performed.

SOLWEIGUse

Warning:

1. **Not available in this version.**
2. This option will considerably slow down the model since SOLWEIG is a 2D model.

Requirement Required

Description Determines whether a high resolution radiation model to calculate mean radiant temperature should be used (SOLWEIG).

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	SOLWEIG calculations are not performed.
1	SOLWEIG calculations are performed. A grid of mean radiant temperature (Tmrt) is calculated based on high resolution digital surface models.

NetRadiationMethod

Requirement Required

Description Determines method for calculation of radiation fluxes.

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	Uses observed values of Q* supplied in meteorological forcing file.
1	Q* modelled with L↓ observations supplied in meteorological forcing file. Zenith angle not accounted for in albedo calculation.
2	Q* modelled with L↓ modelled using cloud cover fraction supplied in meteorological forcing file (Loridan et al. 2011 [L2011]). Zenith angle not accounted for in albedo calculation.
3	Q* modelled with L↓ modelled using air temperature and relative humidity supplied in meteorological forcing file (Loridan et al. 2011 [L2011]). Zenith angle not accounted for in albedo calculation.
100	Q* modelled with L↓ observations supplied in meteorological forcing file. Zenith angle accounted for in albedo calculation. SSss_YYYY_NARPOut.txt file produced. Not recommended in this version.
200	Q* modelled with L↓ modelled using cloud cover fraction supplied in meteorological forcing file (Loridan et al. 2011 [L2011]). Zenith angle accounted for in albedo calculation. SSss_YYYY_NARPOut.txt file produced. Not recommended in this version.
300	Q* modelled with L↓ modelled using air temperature and relative humidity supplied in meteorological forcing file (Loridan et al. 2011 [L2011]). Zenith angle accounted for in albedo calculation. SSss_YYYY_NARPOut.txt file produced. Not recommended in this version.

EmissionsMethod

Requirement Required

Description Determines method for QF calculation.

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	Uses values provided in the meteorological forcing file (SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt). If you do not want to include QF to the calculation of surface energy balance, you should set values in the meteorological forcing file to zero to prevent calculation of QF. UMEP provides two methods to calculate QF LQF which is simpler GQF which is more complete but requires more data inputs
1	Not recommended in this version. Calculated according to Loridan et al. (2011) [L2011] using coefficients specified in SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt. Modelled values will be used even if QF is provided in the meteorological forcing file.
2	Recommended in this version. Calculated according to Järvi et al. (2011) [J11] using coefficients specified in SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt and diurnal patterns specified in SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Modelled values will be used even if QF is provided in the meteorological forcing file.
3	Updated Loridan et al. (2011) [L2011] method using daily (not instantaneous) air temperature (HDD(id-1,3)) using coefficients specified in SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt. Modelled values will be used even if QF is provided in the meteorological forcing file.

StorageHeatMethod

Requirement Required

Description Determines method for calculating storage heat flux ΔQS .

Configuration

Value	Comments
1	Δ QS modelled using the objective hysteresis model (OHM) [<i>G91OHM</i>] using parameters specified for each surface type.
2	Uses observed values of Δ QS supplied in meteorological forcing file.
3	Δ QS modelled using AnOHM. Not recommended in this version.
4	Δ QS modelled using the Element Surface Temperature Method (ESTM) (Offerle et al. 2005 [<i>OGF2005</i>]). Not recommended in this version.

OHMIncQF**Requirement** Required**Description** Determines whether the storage heat flux calculation uses Q^* or ($Q^* + QF$).**Configuration**

Value	Comments
0	Δ QS modelled Q^* only.
1	Δ QS modelled using $Q^* + QF$.

StabilityMethod**Requirement** Required**Description** Defines which atmospheric stability functions are used.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
0	Not used.
1	Not used.
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Momentum: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – unstable: Dyer (1974) [D74] modified by Högstrom (1988) [H1988] – stable: Van Ulden and Holtslag (1985) [VUH85] • Heat: Dyer (1974) [D74] modified by Högstrom (1988) [H1988] <p>Not recommended in this version.</p>
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Momentum: Campbell and Norman (Eq 7.27, Pg97) [CN1988] • Heat <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – unstable: Campbell and Norman [CN1988] – stable: Campbell and Norman [CN1988] <p>Recommended in this version.</p>
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Momentum: Businger et al. (1971) [B71] modified by Högstrom (1988) [H1988] • Heat: Businger et al. (1971) [B71] modified by Högstrom (1988) [H1988] <p>Not recommended in this version.</p>

RoughLenHeatMethod**Requirement** Required**Description** Determines method for calculating roughness length for heat.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
1	Uses value of 0.1z0m.
2	Calculated according to Kawai et al. (2009) [Ka09]. Recommended in this version.
3	Calculated according to Voogt and Grimmond (2000) [VG00].
4	Calculated according to Kanda et al. (2007) [Ka07].

RoughLenMomMethod**Requirement** Required**Description** Determines how aerodynamic roughness length (z0m) and zero displacement height (zdm) are calculated.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
1	<p>Values specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> are used.</p> <hr/> <p>Tip: Note that UMEP provides tools to calculate these. See Kent et al. (2017a) [<i>Kent2017a</i>] for recommendations on methods. Kent et al. (2017b) [<i>Kent2017b</i>] have developed a method to include vegetation which is also available within UMEP.</p> <hr/>
2	<p>z0m and zd are calculated using ‘rule of thumb’ (Grimmond and Oke 1999 [<i>GO99</i>]) using mean building and tree height specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>. z0m and zd are adjusted with time to account for seasonal variation in porosity of deciduous trees.</p>
3	<p>z0m and zd are calculated based on the MacDonald et al. (1998) [<i>Mc98</i>] method using mean building and tree heights, plan area fraction and frontal areal index specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>. z0m and zd are adjusted with time to account for seasonal variation in porosity of deciduous trees.</p>

SMDMethod

Requirement Required

Description Determines method for calculating soil moisture deficit (SMD).

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	SMD modelled using parameters specified in <i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i> . Recommended in this version.
1	Observed SM provided in the meteorological forcing file is used. Data are provided as volumetric soil moisture content. Metadata must be provided in <i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i> . Not available in this version.
2	Observed SM provided in the meteorological forcing file is used. Data are provided as gravimetric soil moisture content. Metadata must be provided in <i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i> . Not available in this version.

WaterUseMethod

Requirement Required

Description Defines how external water use is calculated.

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	External water use modelled using parameters specified in <i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i> .
1	Observations of external water use provided in the meteorological forcing file are used.

4.1.2 Time related options

Tstep

Requirement Required

Description Specifies the model time step [s].

Configuration A value of 300 s (5 min) is strongly recommended. The time step cannot be less than 1 min or greater than 10 min, and must be a whole number of minutes that divide into an hour (i.e. options are 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10 min or 60, 120, 180, 240, 300, 360, 600 s).

ResolutionFilesIn

Requirement Required

Description Specifies the resolution of the input files [s] which SUEWS will disaggregate to the model time step.

Configuration 1800 s for 30 min or 3600 s for 60 min are recommended.

Note: If *ResolutionFilesIn* is not provided, SUEWS assumes *ResolutionFilesIn* = Tstep.

ResolutionFilesInESTM

Requirement Optional

Description Specifies the resolution of the ESTM input files [s] which SUEWS will disaggregate to the model time step.

Configuration The same as for *ResolutionFilesIn*.

ResolutionFilesOut

Requirement Required

Description Specifies the resolution of the output files [s].

Configuration 1800 s for 30 min or 3600 s for 60 min are recommended.

4.1.3 File related options

FileCode

Requirement Required

Description Alphabetical site identification code (e.g. He, Sc, Kc).

Configuration This must be consistent with names of *meteorological input file* and *initial condition files*

FileInputPath

Requirement Required

Description Input directory.

Configuration This can be set either as an absolute path or a relative path where the program is initiated.

FileOutputPath

Requirement Required

Description Output directory.

Configuration This can be set either as an absolute path or a relative path where the program is initiated.

MultipleMetFiles**Requirement** Required**Description** Specifies whether one single meteorological forcing file is used for all grids or a separate met file is provided for each grid.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
0	Single meteorological forcing file used for all grids. No grid number should appear in the file name.
1	Separate meteorological forcing files used for each grid. The grid number should appear in the file name.

MultipleInitFiles**Requirement** Required**Description** Specifies whether one single initial conditions file is used for all grids at the start of the run or a separate initial conditions file is provided for each grid.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
0	Single initial conditions file used for all grids. No grid number should appear in the file name.
1	Separate initial conditions files used for each grid. The grid number should appear in the file name.

MultipleESTMFiles**Requirement** Optional**Description** Specifies whether one single ESTM forcing file is used for all grids or a separate file is provided for each grid.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
0	Single ESTM forcing file used for all grids. No grid number should appear in the file name.
1	Separate ESTM forcing files used for each grid. The grid number should appear in the file name.

KeepTstepFilesIn**Requirement** Optional**Description** Specifies whether input meteorological forcing files at the resolution of the model time step should be saved.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
0	Meteorological forcing files at model time step are not written out. This is the default option Recommended to reduce processing time and save disk space as (e.g. 5-min) files can be large.
1	Meteorological forcing files at model time step are written out.

KeepTstepFilesOut**Requirement** Optional**Description** Specifies whether output meteorological forcing files at the resolution of the model time step should be saved.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
0	Output files at model time are not saved. This is the default option. Recommended to save disk space as (e.g. 5-min) files can be large.
1	Output files at model time step are written out.

WriteOutOption**Requirement** Optional**Description** Specifies which variables are written in the output files.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
0	All (except snow-related) output variables written. This is the default option.
1	All (including snow-related) output variables written.
2	Writes out a minimal set of output variables (use this to save space or if information about the different surfaces is not required).

SuppressWarnings**Requirement** Optional**Description** Controls whether the warnings.txt file is written or not.**Configuration**

Value	Comments
0	The warnings.txt file is written. This is the default option.
1	No warnings.txt file is written. May be useful for large model runs as this file can grow large.

4.1.4 Options related to disaggregation of input data**DisaggMethod****Requirement** Optional**Description** Specifies how meteorological variables in the input file (except rain and snow) are disaggregated to the model time step. Wind direction is not currently downscaled so non -999 values will cause an error.

Configuration

Value	Comments
1	Linear downscaling of averages for all variables, additional zenith check is used for Kdown. This is the default option.
2	Linear downscaling of instantaneous values for all variables, additional zenith check is used for Kdown.
3	WFDEI setting: average Kdown (with additional zenith check); instantaneous for Tair, RH, pres and U. (N.B. WFDEI actually provides Q not RH)

KdownZen**Requirement** Optional

Description Can be used to switch off zenith checking in Kdown disaggregation. Note that the zenith calculation requires location information obtained from *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*. If a single met file is used for all grids, the zenith is calculated for the first grid and the disaggregated data is then applied for all grids.

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	No zenith angle check is applied.
1	Disaggregated Kdown is set to zero when zenith angle exceeds 90 degrees (i.e. sun below horizon) and redistributed over the day. This is the default option.

RainDisaggMethod**Requirement** Optional

Description Specifies how rain in the meteorological forcing file are disaggregated to the model time step. If present in the original met forcing file, snow is currently disaggregated in the same way as rainfall.

Configuration

Value	Comments
100	Rainfall is evenly distributed among all subintervals in a rainy interval. This is the default option.
101	Rainfall is evenly distributed among among RainAmongN subintervals in a rainy interval – also requires RainAmongN to be set.
102	Rainfall is evenly distributed among among RainAmongN subintervals in a rainy interval for different intensity bins – also requires MultRainAmongN and MultRainAmongNUpperI to be set.

RainAmongN**Requirement** Optional

Description Specifies the number of subintervals (of length tt) over which to distribute rainfall in each interval (of length TT).

Configuration Must be an integer value. Use with RainDisaggMethod = 101.

MultRainAmongN**Requirement** Optional

Description Specifies the number of subintervals (of length tt) over which to distribute rainfall in each interval (of length TT) for up to 5 intensity bins. Must take integer values.

Configuration Use with `RainDisaggMethod = 102`. e.g. `MultRainAmongN(1) = 5`, `MultRainAmongN(2) = 8`, `MultRainAmongN(3) = 12`

MultRainAmongNUpperI

Requirement Optional

Description Specifies upper limit for each intensity bin to apply `MultRainAmongN`.

Configuration Any intensities above the highest specified intensity will use the last `MultRainAmongN` value and write a warning to *Warning messages: warnings.txt*. Use with `RainDisaggMethod = 102`. e.g. `MultRainAmongNUpperI(1) = 0.5`, `MultRainAmongNUpperI(2) = 2.0`, `MultRainAmongNUpperI(3) = 50.0`

DisaggMethodESTM

Requirement Optional

Description Specifies how ESTM-related temperatures in the input file are disaggregated to the model time step.

Configuration

Value	Comments
1	Linear downscaling of averages.
2	Linear downscaling of instantaneous values.

4.1.5 netCDF related options

Warning: Not available in this version.

ncMode

Requirement Optional

Description Determine if the output files should be written in netCDF format.

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	Output files are kept as plain text files (i.e., .txt).
1	Output files will be written in netCDF format (i.e., .nc).

nRow

Requirement Optional

Description Number of rows in the output layout (only applicable when `ncMode=1`).

Configuration An integer (e.g., 36) that satisfies $nRow \times nCol =$ the total number of grids.

nCol

Requirement Optional

Description Number of columns in the output layout (only applicable when `ncMode=1`).

Configuration An integer (e.g., 47.) that satisfies $nRow \times nCol =$ the total number of grids

4.2 SUEWS Site Information

The following text files provide SUEWS with information about the study area.

4.2.1 SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt

SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeatFlux.txt provides the parameters needed to model the anthropogenic heat flux using either the method of Järvi et al. (2011) based on heating and cooling degree days (*EmissionsMethod* = 2 in *RunControl.nml*) or the method of Loricán et al. (2011) based on air temperature (*EmissionsMethod* = 1 in *RunControl.nml*). The sub-daily variation in anthropogenic heat flux is modelled according to the daily cycles specified in SUEWS_Profiles.txt.

Alternatively, if available, the anthropogenic heat flux can be provided in the met forcing file (and set *EmissionsMethod* = 0 in *RunControl.nml*) by filling the *qf* column with valid values.

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>BaseTHDD</i>	<i>MU</i>	Base temperature for heating degree days [°C]
3	<i>QF_A_WD</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Base value for QF on weekdays [$W\ m^{-2}\ (Cap\ ha^{-1})^{-1}$]
4	<i>QF_B_WD</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Parameter related to heating degree days on weekdays [$W\ m^{-2}\ K^{-1}\ (Cap\ ha^{-1})^{-1}$]
5	<i>QF_C_WD</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Parameter related to heating degree days on weekdays [$W\ m^{-2}\ K^{-1}\ (Cap\ ha^{-1})^{-1}$]
6	<i>QF_A_WE</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Base value for QF on weekends [$W\ m^{-2}\ (Cap\ ha^{-1})^{-1}$]
7	<i>QF_B_WE</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Parameter related to cooling degree days on weekends [$W\ m^{-2}\ K^{-1}\ (Cap\ ha^{-1})^{-1}$]
8	<i>QF_C_WE</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Parameter related to heating degree days on weekends [$W\ m^{-2}\ K^{-1}\ (Cap\ ha^{-1})^{-1}$]
9	<i>AHMin_WD</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Minimum QF on weekdays [$W\ m^{-2}$]
10	<i>AHMin_WE</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Minimum QF on weekends [$W\ m^{-2}$]
11	<i>AHSlope_Heating_WD</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Heating slope of QF on weekdays [$W\ m^{-2}\ K^{-1}$]
12	<i>AHSlope_Heating_WE</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Heating slope of QF on weekends [$W\ m^{-2}\ K^{-1}$]
13	<i>AHSlope_Cooling_WD</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Cooling slope of QF on weekdays [$W\ m^{-2}\ K^{-1}$]
14	<i>AHSlope_Cooling_WE</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Cooling slope of QF on weekends [$W\ m^{-2}\ K^{-1}$]
15	<i>TCritic_Heating_WD</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Critical heating temperature on weekdays [°C]
16	<i>TCritic_Heating_WE</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Critical heating temperature on weekends [°C]
17	<i>TCritic_Cooling_WD</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Critical cooling temperature on weekdays [°C]

Continued on next page

Table 4.1 – continued from previous page

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
18	<i>TCritic_Cooling_WE</i>	MU O	Critical cooling temperature on weekends [°C]
19	<i>EnergyUseProfWD</i>	MU O	Code linking to <i>EnergyUseProfWD</i> in <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
20	<i>EnergyUseProfWE</i>	MU O	Code linking to <i>EnergyUseProfWE</i> in <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
21	<i>ActivityProfWD</i>	MU O	Code linking to <i>ActivityProfWD</i> in <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
22	<i>ActivityProfWE</i>	MU O	Code linking to <i>ActivityProfWE</i> in <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
23	<i>TraffProfWD</i>	MU O	Code for traffic activity profile (weekdays) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Not used in v2018a.
24	<i>TraffProfWE</i>	MU O	Code for traffic activity profile (weekends) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Not used in v2018a.
25	<i>PopProfWD</i>	MU O	Code for population density profile (weekdays) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
26	<i>PopProfWE</i>	MU O	Code for population density profile (weekends) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
27	<i>MinQFMetab</i>	MU O	Minimum value for human heat emission. [W m ⁻²]
28	<i>MaxQFMetab</i>	MU O	Maximum value for human heat emission. [W m ⁻²]
29	<i>FrFossilFuel_Heat</i>	MU O	Fraction of fossil fuels used for building heating [-]
30	<i>FrFossilFuel_NonHeat</i>	MU O	Fraction of fossil fuels used for building energy use [-]
31	<i>EF_umolCO2perJ</i>	MU O	Emission factor for fuels used for building heating.
32	<i>EnEF_v_Jkm</i>	MU O	Emission factor for heat [J klm ⁻¹ l].
33	<i>FcEF_v_kgkm</i>	MU O	CO2 emission factor [kg km ⁻¹]
34	<i>TrafficUnits</i>	MU O	Units for the traffic rate for the study area. Not used in v2018a.

An example *SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.2 SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt

Caution: The BiogenCO2 part is under development and not ready for use.

SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt provides the parameters needed to model the Biogenic CO2 characteristics of vegetation surfaces.

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>alpha</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	The mean apparent ecosystem quantum. Represents the initial slope of the light-response curve.
3	<i>beta</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	The light-saturated gross photosynthesis of the canopy. [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$]
4	<i>theta</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	The convexity of the curve at light saturation.
5	<i>alpha_enh</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Part of the <i>alpha</i> coefficient related to the fraction of vegetation.
6	<i>beta_enh</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Part of the <i>beta</i> coefficient related to the fraction of vegetation.
7	<i>resp_a</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Respiration coefficient a.
8	<i>resp_b</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Respiration coefficient b - related to air temperature dependency.
9	<i>min_respi</i>	<i>MU</i> <i>O</i>	Minimum soil respiration rate (for cold-temperature limit) [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$].

An example *SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt* can be found online

4.2.3 SUEWS_Conductance.txt

SUEWS_Conductance.txt contains the parameters needed for the Jarvis (1976) [Ja76] surface conductance model used in the modelling of evaporation in SUEWS. These values should **not** be changed independently of each other. The suggested values below have been derived using datasets for Los Angeles and Vancouver (see Järvi et al. (2011) [J11]) and should be used with *gsModel* = 1. An alternative formulation (*gsModel* =2) uses slightly different functional forms and different coefficients (with different units).

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>G1</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to maximum surface conductance [mm s^{-1}]
3	<i>G2</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to Kdown dependence [W m^{-2}]
4	<i>G3</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to VPD dependence [units depend on <i>gsModel</i>]
5	<i>G4</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to VPD dependence [units depend on <i>gsModel</i>]
6	<i>G5</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to temperature dependence [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
7	<i>G6</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to soil moisture dependence [mm^{-1}]
8	<i>TH</i>	<i>MD</i>	Upper air temperature limit [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
9	<i>TL</i>	<i>MD</i>	Lower air temperature limit [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
10	<i>S1</i>	<i>MD</i>	A parameter related to soil moisture dependence [-]
11	<i>S2</i>	<i>MD</i>	A parameter related to soil moisture dependence [mm]
12	<i>Kmax</i>	<i>MD</i>	Maximum incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]
13	<i>gsModel</i>	<i>MD</i>	Formulation choice for conductance calculation.

An example *SUEWS_Conductance.txt* can be found online

4.2.4 SUEWS_Irrigation.txt

SUEWS includes a simple model for external water use if observed data are not available. The model calculates daily water use from the mean daily air temperature, number of days since rain and fraction of irrigated area using

automatic/manual irrigation. The sub-daily pattern of water use is modelled according to the daily cycles specified in *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Alternatively, if available, the external water use can be provided in the met forcing file (and set *WaterUseMethod* = 1 in *RunControl.nml*) by filling the *Wuh* columns with valid values.

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>Ie_start</i>	<i>MU</i>	Day when irrigation starts [DOY]
3	<i>Ie_end</i>	<i>MU</i>	Day when irrigation ends [DOY]
4	<i>InternalWaterUse</i>	<i>MU</i>	Internal water use [mm h ⁻¹]
5	<i>Faut</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of irrigated area that is irrigated using automated systems
6	<i>Ie_a1</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [mm d ⁻¹]
7	<i>Ie_a2</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [mm d ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
8	<i>Ie_a3</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [mm d ⁻²]
9	<i>Ie_m1</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d ⁻¹]
10	<i>Ie_m2</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
11	<i>Ie_m3</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d ⁻²]
12	<i>DayWat (1)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Sundays [1], if not [0]
13	<i>DayWat (2)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Mondays [1], if not [0]
14	<i>DayWat (3)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Tuesdays [1], if not [0]
15	<i>DayWat (4)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Wednesdays [1], if not [0]
16	<i>DayWat (5)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Thursdays [1], if not [0]
17	<i>DayWat (6)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Fridays [1], if not [0]
18	<i>DayWat (7)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Saturdays [1], if not [0]
19	<i>DayWatPer (1)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Sundays [0-1]
20	<i>DayWatPer (2)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Mondays [0-1]
21	<i>DayWatPer (3)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Tuesdays [0-1]
22	<i>DayWatPer (4)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Wednesdays [0-1]
23	<i>DayWatPer (5)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Thursdays [0-1]
24	<i>DayWatPer (6)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Fridays [0-1]
25	<i>DayWatPer (7)</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Saturdays [0-1]

An example *SUEWS_Irrigation.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.5 SUEWS_NonVeg.txt

SUEWS_NonVeg.txt specifies the characteristics for the non-vegetated surface cover types (Paved, Bldgs, BSoil) by linking codes in column 1 of *SUEWS_NonVeg.txt* to the codes specified in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* (Code_Paved, Code_Bldgs, Code_BSoil). Each row should correspond to a particular surface type. For suggestions on how to complete this table, see: *Typical Values*.

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>AlbedoMin</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow).
3	<i>AlbedoMax</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.
4	<i>Emissivity</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface emissivity.
5	<i>StorageMin</i>	<i>MD</i>	Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy).
6	<i>StorageMax</i>	<i>MD</i>	Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy)

Continued on next page

Table 4.2 – continued from previous page

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
7	<i>WetThreshold</i>	MD	Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface [mm].
8	<i>StateLimit</i>	MD	Upper limit to the surface state. [mm]
9	<i>DrainageEq</i>	MD	Calculation choice for Drainage equation
10	<i>DrainageCoef1</i>	MD	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹] used in <i>DrainageEq</i>
11	<i>DrainageCoef2</i>	MD	Coefficient b [-] used in <i>DrainageEq</i>
12	<i>SoilTypeCode</i>	L	Code for soil characteristics below this surface linking to <i>Code of SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>
13	<i>SnowLimPatch</i>	O	Limit for the snow water equivalent when snow cover starts to be patchy [mm]
14	<i>SnowLimRemove</i>	O	Limit of the snow water equivalent for snow removal from roads and roofs [mm]
15	<i>OHMCode_SummerWet</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
16	<i>OHMCode_SummerDry</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
17	<i>OHMCode_WinterWet</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
18	<i>OHMCode_WinterDry</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
19	<i>OHMThresh_SW</i>	MD	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [°C]
20	<i>OHMThresh_WD</i>	MD	Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-]
21	<i>ESTMCode</i>	L	Code for ESTM coefficients linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>
22	<i>AnOHM_Cp</i>	MU	Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
23	<i>AnOHM_Kk</i>	MU	Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
24	<i>AnOHM_Ch</i>	MU	Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

An example *SUEWS_NonVeg.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.6 SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt

OHM, the Objective Hysteresis Model (Grimmond et al. 1991) [*G91OHM*] calculates the storage heat flux as a function of net all-wave radiation and surface characteristics.

- For each surface, OHM requires three model coefficients (a1, a2, a3). The three should be selected as a set.
- The *SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt* file provides these coefficients for each surface type.
- A variety of values has been derived for different materials and can be found in the literature (see: *Typical Values*).
- **Coefficients can be changed depending on:**
 1. surface wetness state (wet/dry) based on the calculated surface wetness state and soil moisture.
 2. season (summer/winter) based on a 5-day running mean air temperature.
- To use the same coefficients irrespective of wet/dry and summer/winter conditions, use the same code for all four OHM columns (*OHMCode_SummerWet*, *OHMCode_SummerDry*, *OHMCode_WinterWet* and *OHMCode_WinterDry*).

Note: #. AnOHM (set in *RunControl.nml* by *StorageHeatMethod* = 3) does not use the coefficients specified in *SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt* but instead requires three parameters to be specified for each surface type (including snow): heat capacity (*AnOHM_Cp*), thermal conductivity (*AnOHM_Kk*) and bulk transfer coefficient (*AnOHM_Ch*). These are specified in *SUEWS_NonVeg.txt*, *SUEWS_Veg.txt*, *SUEWS_Water.txt* and *SUEWS_Snow.txt*. No additional files are required for AnOHM.

1. AnOHM is under development in v2018b and should NOT be used!

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>a1</i>	<i>MU</i>	Coefficient for Q^* term [-]
3	<i>a2</i>	<i>MU</i>	Coefficient for dQ^*/dt term [h]
4	<i>a3</i>	<i>MU</i>	Constant term [$W\ m^{-2}$]

An example *SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.7 SUEWS_Profiles.txt

SUEWS_Profiles.txt specifies the daily cycle of variables related to human behaviour (energy use, water use and snow clearing). Different profiles can be specified for weekdays and weekends. The profiles are provided at hourly resolution here; the model will then interpolate the hourly energy and water use profiles to the resolution of the model time step and normalize the values provided. Thus it does not matter whether columns 2-25 add up to, say 1, 24, or another number, because the model will handle this. Currently, the snow clearing profiles are not interpolated as these are effectively a switch (0 or 1).

If the anthropogenic heat flux and water use are specified in the met forcing file, the energy and water use profiles are not used.

Profiles are specified for the following

- Anthropogenic heat flux (weekday and weekend)
- Water use (weekday and weekend; manual and automatic irrigation)
- Snow removal (weekday and weekend)
- Human activity (weekday and weekend).

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	2-25	<i>MU</i>	Multiplier for each hour of the day [-] for energy and water use. For SnowClearing, set those hours to 1 when snow removal from paved and roof surface is allowed (0 otherwise) if the snow removal limits set in the <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i> (SnowLimR remove column) are exceeded.

An example *SUEWS_Profiles.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.8 SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt

For each year and each grid, site specific surface cover information and other input parameters are provided to SUEWS by *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*. The model currently requires a new row for each year of the model run. All rows in this file will be read by the model and run.

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Grid</i>	<i>MU</i>	a unique number to represent grid
2	<i>Year</i>	<i>MU</i>	Year [YYYY]
3	<i>StartDLS</i>	<i>MU</i>	Start of the day light savings [DOY]
4	<i>EndDLS</i>	<i>MU</i>	End of the day light savings [DOY]
5	<i>lat</i>	<i>MU</i>	Latitude [deg].
6	<i>lng</i>	<i>MU</i>	longitude [deg]
7	<i>Timezone</i>	<i>MU</i>	Time zone [h] for site relative to UTC (east is positive). This should be set according to the times given in the meteorological forcing file(s).
8	<i>SurfaceArea</i>	<i>MU</i>	Area of the grid [ha].
9	<i>Alt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Used for both the radiation and water flow between grids.
10	<i>z</i>	<i>MU</i>	Measurement height [m].
11	<i>id</i>	<i>MD</i>	Day of year [DOY]
12	<i>ih</i>	<i>MD</i>	Hour [H]
13	<i>imin</i>	<i>MD</i>	Minute [M]
14	<i>Fr_Paved</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of <i>Paved</i> surfaces [-]
15	<i>Fr_Bldgs</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of buildings [-]
16	<i>Fr_EveTr</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of <i>EveTr</i> : evergreen trees and shrubs [-]
17	<i>Fr_DecTr</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of deciduous trees and shrubs [-]
18	<i>Fr_Grass</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of <i>Grass</i> [-]
19	<i>Fr_Bsoil</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of bare soil or unmanaged land [-]
20	<i>Fr_Water</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of open water [-]
21	<i>IrrFr_EveTr</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of evergreen trees that are irrigated [-]
22	<i>IrrFr_DecTr</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of deciduous trees that are irrigated [-]
23	<i>IrrFr_Grass</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of <i>Grass</i> that is irrigated [-]
24	<i>H_Bldgs</i>	<i>MU</i>	Mean building height [m]
25	<i>H_EveTr</i>	<i>MU</i>	Mean height of evergreen trees [m]
26	<i>H_DecTr</i>	<i>MU</i>	Mean height of deciduous trees [m]
27	<i>z0</i>	<i>O</i>	Roughness length for momentum [m]
28	<i>zd</i>	<i>O</i>	Zero-plane displacement [m]
29	<i>FAI_Bldgs</i>	<i>O</i>	Frontal area index for buildings [-]
30	<i>FAI_EveTr</i>	<i>O</i>	Frontal area index for evergreen trees [-]
31	<i>FAI_DecTr</i>	<i>O</i>	Frontal area index for deciduous trees [-]
32	<i>PopDensDay</i>	<i>O</i>	Daytime population density (i.e. workers, tourists) [people ha ⁻¹]
33	<i>PopDensNight</i>	<i>O</i>	Night-time population density (i.e. residents) [people ha ⁻¹]
34	<i>TrafficRate_WD</i>	<i>O</i>	Weekday traffic rate [veh km m ⁻² s ⁻¹] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation - not used in v2018a.
35	<i>TrafficRate_WE</i>	<i>O</i>	Weekend traffic rate [veh km m ⁻² s ⁻¹] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation - not used in v2018a.
36	<i>QF0_BEU_WD</i>	<i>O</i>	Building energy use [W m ⁻²]
37	<i>QF0_BEU_WE</i>	<i>O</i>	Building energy use [W m ⁻²]
38	<i>Code_Paved</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for <i>Paved</i> surface characteristics linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>
39	<i>Code_Bldgs</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for <i>Bldgs</i> surface characteristics linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>
40	<i>Code_EveTr</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for <i>EveTr</i> surface characteristics linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>
41	<i>Code_DecTr</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for <i>DecTr</i> surface characteristics linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>
42	<i>Code_Grass</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for <i>Grass</i> surface characteristics linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>

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Table 4.3 – continued from previous page

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
43	<i>Code_BSoil</i>	L	Code for <i>BSoil</i> surface characteristics linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>
44	<i>Code_Water</i>	L	Code for <i>Water</i> surface characteristics linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>
45	<i>LUMPS_DrRate</i>	MD	Drainage rate of bucket for LUMPS [mm h^{-1}]
46	<i>LUMPS_Cover</i>	MD	Limit when surface totally covered with water for LUMPS [mm]
47	<i>LUMPS_MaxRes</i>	MD	Maximum water bucket reservoir [mm] Used for LUMPS surface wetness control.
48	<i>NARP_Trans</i>	MD	Atmospheric transmissivity for NARP [-]
49	<i>CondCode</i>	L	Code for surface conductance parameters linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>
50	<i>SnowCode</i>	L	Code for snow surface characteristics linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>
51	<i>SnowClearingProfWD</i>	L	Code for snow clearing profile (weekdays) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
52	<i>SnowClearingProfWE</i>	L	Code for snow clearing profile (weekends) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
53	<i>AnthropogenicCode</i>	L	Code for modelling anthropogenic heat flux linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i> , which contains the model coefficients for estimation of the anthropogenic heat flux (used if <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1, 2 in <i>RunControl.nml</i>).
54	<i>IrrigationCode</i>	L	Code for modelling irrigation linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>
55	<i>WaterUseProfManuWD</i>	L	Code for water use profile (manual irrigation, weekdays) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
56	<i>WaterUseProfManuWE</i>	L	Code for water use profile (manual irrigation, weekends) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
57	<i>WaterUseProfAutoWD</i>	L	Code for water use profile (automatic irrigation, weekdays) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
58	<i>WaterUseProfAutoWE</i>	L	Code for water use profile (automatic irrigation, weekends) linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .
59	<i>FlowChange</i>	MD	Difference in input and output flows for water surface [mm h^{-1}]
60	<i>RunoffToWater</i>	MD MU	Fraction of above-ground runoff flowing to water surface during flooding [-]
61	<i>PipeCapacity</i>	MD MU	Storage capacity of pipes [mm]
62	<i>GridConnection1of8</i>	MD MU	Number of the 1st grid where water can flow to
63	<i>Fraction1of8</i>	MD MU	Fraction of water that can flow to <i>GridConnection1of8</i> [-]
64	<i>GridConnection2of8</i>	MD MU	Number of the 2nd grid where water can flow to
65	<i>Fraction2of8</i>	MD MU	Fraction of water that can flow to <i>GridConnection2of8</i> [-]
66	<i>GridConnection3of8</i>	MD MU	Number of the 3rd grid where water can flow to
67	<i>Fraction3of8</i>	MD MU	Fraction of water that can flow to <i>GridConnection3of8</i> [-]

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Table 4.3 – continued from previous page

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
68	<i>GridConnection4of8</i>	MD MU	Number of the 4th grid where water can flow to
69	<i>Fraction4of8</i>	MD MU	Fraction of water that can flow to <i>GridConnection4of8</i> [-]
70	<i>GridConnection5of8</i>	MD MU	Number of the 5th grid where water can flow to
71	<i>Fraction5of8</i>	MD MU	Fraction of water that can flow to <i>GridConnection5of8</i> [-]
72	<i>GridConnection6of8</i>	MD MU	Number of the 6th grid where water can flow to
73	<i>Fraction6of8</i>	MD MU	Fraction of water that can flow to <i>GridConnection6of8</i> [-]
74	<i>GridConnection7of8</i>	MD MU	Number of the 7th grid where water can flow to
75	<i>Fraction7of8</i>	MD MU	Fraction of water that can flow to <i>GridConnection7of8</i> [-]
76	<i>GridConnection8of8</i>	MD MU	Number of the 8th grid where water can flow to
77	<i>Fraction8of8</i>	MD MU	Fraction of water that can flow to <i>GridConnection8of8</i> [-]
78	<i>WithinGridPavedCode</i>	L	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>Paved</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .
79	<i>WithinGridBldgsCode</i>	L	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>Bldgs</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>
80	<i>WithinGridEveTrCode</i>	L	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>EveTr</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .
81	<i>WithinGridDecTrCode</i>	L	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>DecTr</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .
82	<i>WithinGridGrassCode</i>	L	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>Grass</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .
83	<i>WithinGridBSoilCode</i>	L	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>BSoil</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .
84	<i>WithinGridWaterCode</i>	L	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>Water</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .
85	<i>AreaWall</i>	MU	Area of wall within grid (needed for ESTM calculation).
86	<i>Fr_ESTMclass_Paved1</i>	MU	Surface cover fraction of <i>Paved</i> surface class 1 used in ESTM calculations
87	<i>Fr_ESTMclass_Paved2</i>	MU	Surface cover fraction of <i>Paved</i> surface class 2 used in ESTM calculations
88	<i>Fr_ESTMclass_Paved3</i>	MU	Surface cover fraction of <i>Paved</i> surface class 3 used in ESTM calculations
89	<i>Code_ESTMclass_Paved1</i>		Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>
90	<i>Code_ESTMclass_Paved2</i>		Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>
91	<i>Code_ESTMclass_Paved3</i>		Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>
92	<i>Fr_ESTMclass_Bldgs1</i>	MU	Surface cover fraction of building class 1 used in ESTM calculations
93	<i>Fr_ESTMclass_Bldgs2</i>	MU	Surface cover fraction of building class 2 used in ESTM calculations
94	<i>Fr_ESTMclass_Bldgs3</i>	MU	Surface cover fraction of building class 3 used in ESTM calculations
95	<i>Fr_ESTMclass_Bldgs4</i>	MU	Surface cover fraction of building class 4 used in ESTM calculations
96	<i>Fr_ESTMclass_Bldgs5</i>	MU	Surface cover fraction of building class 5 used in ESTM calculations
97	<i>Code_ESTMclass_Bldgs1</i>		Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

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Table 4.3 – continued from previous page

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
98	<i>Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs2</i>		Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>
99	<i>Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs3</i>		Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>
100	<i>Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs4</i>		Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>
101	<i>Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs5</i>		Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Attention:

- Two rows of -9 should be placed at end of this file.
- In this file the **column order is important**.
- Surface cover fractions specified from *Fr_Paved* to *Fr_Water* should sum up to 1.
- Surface cover fractions specified from *Fr_ESTMClass_Paved1* to *Fr_ESTMClass_Paved3* should sum up to 1.
- Surface cover fractions specified from *Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs1* to *Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs5* should sum up to 1.
- In this file the **row order is important** for simulations of **multiple grids and multiple years**. Ensure the rows in are arranged so that all grids for a particular year appear on consecutive lines (rather than grouping all years together for a particular grid). See below for a valid example:

```
Grid Year ...
1    2001 ...
2    2001 ...
1    2002 ...
2    2002 ...
```

Tip: ! can be used to indicate comments in the file. Comments are not read by the programme so they can be used by the user to provide notes for their interpretation of the contents. This is strongly recommended.

Day Light Savings (DLS)

The dates for DLS normally vary for each year and country as they are often associated with a specific set of Sunday mornings at the beginning of summer and autumn. Note it is important to remember leap years. You can check <http://www.timeanddate.com/time/dst/> for your city.

Tip: If DLS does not occur give a start and end day immediately after it. Make certain the dummy dates are correct for the hemisphere

- For northern hemisphere, use: 180 181
- For southern hemisphere, use: 365 1

Example when running multiple years (in this case 2008 and 2009 in Canada):

Year	start of daylight savings	end of daylight savings
2008	170	240
2009	172	242

Grid Connections (water flow between grids)

Caution:

- **Not available in this version.**
- columns between *GridConnection1of8* and *GridConnection8of8* in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* can be set to zero.

This section gives an example of water flow between grids, calculated based on the relative elevation of the grids and length of the connecting surface between adjacent grids. For the square grids in the figure, water flow is assumed to be zero between diagonally adjacent grids, as the length of connecting surface linking the grids is very small. Model grids need not be square or the same size.

The table gives example values for the grid connections part of *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* for the grids shown in the figure. For each row, only water flowing out of the current grid is entered (e.g. water flows from 234 to 236 and 237, with a larger proportion of water flowing to 237 because of the greater length of connecting surface between 234 and 237 than between 234 and 236. No water is assumed to flow between 234 and 233 or 235 because there is no elevation difference between these grids. Grids 234 and 238 are at the same elevation and only connect at a point, so no water flows between them. Water enters grid 234 from grids 230, 231 and 232 as these are more elevated.

Fig. 4.1: Example grid connections showing water flow between grids.

Note: Arrows indicate the water flow in to and out of grid 234, but note that only water flowing out of each grid is entered in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*

An example *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.9 SUEWS_Snow.txt

SUEWS_Snow.txt specifies the characteristics for snow surfaces when *SnowUse=1* in *RunControl.nml*. If the snow part of the model is not run, fill this table with '-999' except for the first (Code) column and set *SnowUse=0* in *RunControl.nml*. For a detailed description of the variables, see Järvi et al. (2014) [Leena2014].

Grid	GridConnection 1of8	Fraction1of8	GridConnection 2of8	Fraction2of8	GridConnection 3of8	Fraction3of8	GridConnection 4of8	Fraction4of8	GridConnection 5of8	Fraction5of8	GridConnection 6of8	Fraction6of8	GridConnection 7of8	Fraction7of8	GridConnection 8of8	Fraction8of8
230	233	0.90	234	0.10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
231	234	1.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
232	234	0.20	235	0.80	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
233	236	1.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
234	236	0.10	237	0.90	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
235	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
236	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
237	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
238	237	1.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Fig. 4.2: Example values for the grid connections part of *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* for the grids.

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>RadMeltFactor</i>	<i>MU</i>	Hourly radiation melt factor of snow [$\text{mm W}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$]
3	<i>TempMeltFactor</i>	<i>MU</i>	Hourly temperature melt factor of snow [$\text{mm K}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$]
4	<i>AlbedoMin</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow).
5	<i>AlbedoMax</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.
6	<i>Emissivity</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface emissivity.
7	<i>tau_a</i>	<i>MD</i>	Time constant for snow albedo aging in cold snow [-]
8	<i>tau_f</i>	<i>MD</i>	Time constant for snow albedo aging in melting snow [-]
9	<i>PrecipLimAlb</i>	<i>MD</i>	Limit for hourly precipitation when the ground is fully covered with snow. Then snow albedo is reset to <i>AlbedoMax</i> [mm]
10	<i>SnowDensMin</i>	<i>MD</i>	Fresh snow density [kg m^{-3}]
11	<i>SnowDensMax</i>	<i>MD</i>	Maximum snow density [kg m^{-3}]
12	<i>tau_r</i>	<i>MD</i>	Time constant for snow density ageing [-]
13	<i>CRWMin</i>	<i>MD</i>	Minimum water holding capacity of snow [mm]
14	<i>CRWMax</i>	<i>MD</i>	Maximum water holding capacity of snow [mm]
15	<i>PrecipLimSnow</i>	<i>MD</i>	Limit for hourly snowfall when the ground is fully covered with snow [mm]
16	<i>OHMCode_SummerWet</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
17	<i>OHMCode_SummerDry</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
18	<i>OHMCode_WinterWet</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
19	<i>OHMCode_WinterDry</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
20	<i>OHMThresh_SW</i>	<i>MD</i>	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
21	<i>OHMThresh_WD</i>	<i>MD</i>	Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-]
22	<i>ESTMCode</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for ESTM coefficients linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Continued on next page

Table 4.4 – continued from previous page

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
23	<i>AnOHM_Cp</i>	<i>MU</i>	Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
24	<i>AnOHM_Kk</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
25	<i>AnOHM_Ch</i>	<i>MU</i>	Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

An example *SUEWS_Snow.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.10 SUEWS_Soil.txt

SUEWS_Soil.txt specifies the characteristics of the sub-surface soil below each of the non-water surface types (Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil). The model does not have a soil store below the water surfaces. Note that these sub-surface soil stores are different to the bare soil/unmanned surface cover type. Each of the non-water surface types need to link to soil characteristics specified here. If the soil characteristics are assumed to be the same for all surface types, use a single code value to link the characteristics here with the SoilTypeCode columns in *SUEWS_NonVeg.txt* and *SUEWS_Veg.txt*.

Soil moisture can either be provided using observational data in the met forcing file (*SMDMethod* = 1 or 2 in *RunControl.nml*) and providing some metadata information here (OBS columns), or modelled by SUEWS (*SMDMethod* = 0 in *RunControl.nml*).

Caution: The option to use observational data is not operational in the current release!

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>SoilDepth</i>	<i>MD</i>	Depth of soil beneath the surface [mm]
3	<i>SoilStoreCap</i>	<i>MD</i>	Limit value for <i>SoilDepth</i> [mm]
4	<i>SatHydraulicCond</i>	<i>MD</i>	Hydraulic conductivity for saturated soil [mm s ⁻¹]
5	<i>SoilDensity</i>	<i>MD</i>	Soil density [kg m ⁻³]
6	<i>InfiltrationRate</i>	<i>O</i>	Infiltration rate.
7	<i>OBS_SMDepth</i>	<i>O</i>	The depth of soil moisture measurements. [mm]
8	<i>OBS_SMCap</i>	<i>O</i>	The maximum observed soil moisture. [m ³ m ⁻³ or kg kg ⁻¹]
9	<i>OBS_SoilNotRocks</i>	<i>O</i>	Fraction of soil without rocks. [-]

An example *SUEWS_Soil.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.11 SUEWS_Veg.txt

SUEWS_Veg.txt specifies the characteristics for the vegetated surface cover types (EveTr, DecTr, Grass) by linking codes in column 1 of *SUEWS_Veg.txt* to the codes specified in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* (Code_EveTr, Code_DecTr, Code_Grass). Each row should correspond to a particular surface type. For suggestions on how to complete this table, see: *Typical Values*.

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>AlbedoMin</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow).
3	<i>AlbedoMax</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.

Continued on next page

Table 4.5 – continued from previous page

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
4	<i>Emissivity</i>	MU	Effective surface emissivity.
5	<i>StorageMin</i>	MD	Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy).
6	<i>StorageMax</i>	MD	Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy)
7	<i>WetThreshold</i>	MD	Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface [mm].
8	<i>StateLimit</i>	MD	Upper limit to the surface state. [mm]
9	<i>DrainageEq</i>	MD	Calculation choice for Drainage equation
10	<i>DrainageCoef1</i>	MD	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹] used in <i>DrainageEq</i>
11	<i>DrainageCoef2</i>	MD	Coefficient b [-] used in <i>DrainageEq</i>
12	<i>SoilTypeCode</i>	L	Code for soil characteristics below this surface linking to <i>Code</i> of <i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>
13	<i>SnowLimPatch</i>	O	Limit for the snow water equivalent when snow cover starts to be patchy [mm]
14	<i>BaseT</i>	MU	Base Temperature for initiating growing degree days (GDD) for leaf growth. [°C]
15	<i>BaseTe</i>	MU	Base temperature for initiating sensesance degree days (SDD) for leaf off. [°C]
16	<i>GDDFull</i>	MU	The growing degree days (GDD) needed for full capacity of the leaf area index (LAI) [°C].
17	<i>SDDFull</i>	MU	The sensesance degree days (SDD) needed to initiate leaf off. [°C]
18	<i>LAIMin</i>	MD	leaf-off wintertime value
19	<i>LAIMax</i>	MD	full leaf-on summertime value
20	<i>PorosityMin</i>	MD	leaf-off wintertime value Used only for <i>DecTr</i> (can affect roughness calculation)
21	<i>PorosityMax</i>	MD	full leaf-on summertime value Used only for <i>DecTr</i> (can affect roughness calculation)
22	<i>MaxConductance</i>	MD	The maximum conductance of each vegetation or surface type. [mm s ⁻¹]
23	<i>LAIEq</i>	MD	LAI calculation choice.
24	<i>LeafGrowthPower1</i>	MD	a parameter required by LAI calculation in <i>LAIEq</i>
25	<i>LeafGrowthPower2</i>	MD	a parameter required by LAI calculation [K ⁻¹] in <i>LAIEq</i>
26	<i>LeafOffPower1</i>	MD	a parameter required by LAI calculation [K ⁻¹] in <i>LAIEq</i>
27	<i>LeafOffPower2</i>	MD	a parameter required by LAI calculation [K ⁻¹] in <i>LAIEq</i>
28	<i>OHMCode_SummerWet</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
29	<i>OHMCode_SummerDry</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
30	<i>OHMCode_WinterWet</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
31	<i>OHMCode_WinterDry</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
32	<i>OHMThresh_SW</i>	MD	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [°C]
33	<i>OHMThresh_WD</i>	MD	Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-]
34	<i>ESTMCode</i>	L	Code for ESTM coefficients linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>
35	<i>AnOHM_Cp</i>	MU	Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
36	<i>AnOHM_Kk</i>	MU	Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
37	<i>AnOHM_Ch</i>	MU	Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]
37	<i>BiogenCO2Code</i>	MU	Code linking to the <i>Code</i> column in <i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i> .

An example *SUEWS_Veg.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.12 SUEWS_Water.txt

SUEWS_Water.txt specifies the characteristics for the water surface cover type by linking codes in column 1 of *SUEWS_Water.txt* to the codes specified in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* (*Code_Water*).

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>Code</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.
2	<i>AlbedoMin</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow).
3	<i>AlbedoMax</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.
4	<i>Emissivity</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface emissivity.
5	<i>StorageMin</i>	<i>MD</i>	Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy).
6	<i>StorageMax</i>	<i>MD</i>	Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy)
7	<i>WetThreshold</i>	<i>MD</i>	Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface [mm].
8	<i>StateLimit</i>	<i>MU</i>	Upper limit to the surface state. [mm]
9	<i>WaterDepth</i>	<i>MU</i>	Water depth [mm].
10	<i>DrainageEq</i>	<i>MD</i>	Calculation choice for Drainage equation
11	<i>DrainageCoef1</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹] used in <i>DrainageEq</i>
12	<i>DrainageCoef2</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient b [-] used in <i>DrainageEq</i>
13	<i>OHMCode_SummerWet</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
14	<i>OHMCode_SummerDry</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
15	<i>OHMCode_WinterWet</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
16	<i>OHMCode_WinterDry</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter, linking to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
17	<i>OHMThresh_SW</i>	<i>MD</i>	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [°C]
18	<i>OHMThresh_WD</i>	<i>MD</i>	Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-]
19	<i>ESTMCode</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for ESTM coefficients linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>
20	<i>AnOHM_Cp</i>	<i>MU</i>	Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
21	<i>AnOHM_Kk</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
22	<i>AnOHM_Ch</i>	<i>MU</i>	Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

An example *SUEWS_Water.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.13 SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt

SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt specifies the movement of water between surfaces within a grid/area. It allows impervious connectivity to be taken into account.

Each row corresponds to a surface type (linked by the Code in column 1 to the *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* columns: *WithinGridPavedCode*, *WithinGridBldgsCode*, ..., *WithinGridWaterCode*). Each column contains the fraction of water flowing from the surface type to each of the other surface types or to runoff or the sub-surface soil store.

Note:

- The sum of each row (excluding the Code) must equal 1.
- Water **CANNOT** flow from one surface to that same surface, so the diagonal elements should be zero.

- The row corresponding to the water surface should be zero, as there is currently no flow permitted from the water surface to other surfaces by the model.
- Currently water **CANNOT** go to both runoff and soil store (i.e. it must go to one or the other – *runoff* for impervious surfaces; *soilstore* for pervious surfaces).

In the table below, for example,

- All flow from paved surfaces goes to runoff;
- 90% of flow from buildings goes to runoff, with small amounts going to other surfaces (mostly paved surfaces as buildings are often surrounded by paved areas);
- All flow from vegetated and bare soil areas goes into the sub-surface soil store;
- The row corresponding to water contains zeros (as it is currently not used).

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>ToPaved</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Paved</i>
2	<i>ToBldgs</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Bldgs</i>
3	<i>ToEveTr</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>EveTr</i>
4	<i>ToDecTr</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>DecTr</i>
5	<i>ToGrass</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Grass</i>
6	<i>ToBSoil</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>BSoil</i>
7	<i>ToWater</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Water</i>
8	<i>ToRunoff</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Runoff</i>
9	<i>ToSoilStore</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>SoilStore</i>

An example *SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt* can be found in the online version.

4.2.14 Input Options

a1

Description Coefficient for Q^* term [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Coefficient for Q^* term [-]

a2

Description Coefficient for dQ^*/dt term [h]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Coefficient for dQ^*/dt term [h]

a3

Description Constant term [$W\ m^{-2}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Constant term [W m ⁻²]

FcEF_v_kgkm

Description CO2 emission factor [kg km⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Weekday building energy use [W m ⁻²] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

ActivityProfWD

Description Code linking to *ActivityProfWD* in *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for human activity profile (weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Used for CO2 flux calculation. Not used in this version.

ActivityProfWE

Description Code linking to *ActivityProfWE* in *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for human activity profile (weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Look the codes Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Used for CO2 flux calculation. Not used in this version.

AHMin_WD

Description Minimum QF on weekdays [W m⁻²]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

AHMin_WE

Description Minimum QF on weekends [W m^{-2}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

AHSlope_Heating_WD

Description Heating slope of QF on weekdays [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

AHSlope_Heating_WE

Description Heating slope of QF on weekends [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

AHSlope_Cooling_WD

Description Cooling slope of QF on weekdays [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

AHSlope_Cooling_WE

Description Cooling slope of QF on weekends [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

AlbedoMax

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime. View factors should be taken into account.
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Example values [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.1 EveTr Oke (1987) [Ok87] • 0.18 DecTr Oke (1987) [Ok87] • 0.21 Grass Oke (1987) [Ok87]
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Example values [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.1 Water Oke (1987) [Ok87]
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Example values [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.85 Järvi et al. (2014) [Leena2014]

AlbedoMin

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow).

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Not currently used for non-vegetated surfaces – set the same as AlbedoMax.
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Example values [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.1 EveTr Oke (1987) [Ok87] • 0.18 DecTr Oke (1987) [Ok87] • 0.21 Grass Oke (1987) [Ok87]
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Not currently used for water surface - set same as AlbedoMax.
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Example values [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.18 Järvi et al. (2014) [Leena2014]

alpha

Description The mean apparent ecosystem quantum. Represents the initial slope of the light-response curve. [$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \mu\text{mol photons}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Example values: <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 11, 12, 13, 14, 15 or 16: 0.044 Ruimy et al (1995) [<i>R95</i>], 0.0593 Schmid et al. (2000) [<i>S2000</i>], 0.0205 Flanagan et al. (2002) [<i>FWC2002</i>]. <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, or 26: 0.031 Bellucco et al. (2017) [<i>B2017</i>] <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36: 0.005 Bellucco et al. (2017) [<i>B2017</i>]

Alt

Description Used for both the radiation and water flow between grids.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Used for both the radiation and water flow between grids. Not available in this version.

AnOHM_Ch

Description Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

AnOHM_Cp

Description Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m^{-3}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]

AnOHM_Kk

Description Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]

AnthropogenicCode

Description Code for modelling anthropogenic heat flux linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt*, which contains the model coefficients for estimation of the anthropogenic heat flux (used if *EmissionsMethod* = 1, 2 in *RunControl.nml*).

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i> .

AreaWall

Description Area of wall within grid (needed for ESTM calculation).

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Area of wall within grid (needed for ESTM calculation).

BaseT

Description Base Temperature for initiating growing degree days (GDD) for leaf growth. [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	See section 2.2 Järvi et al. (2011); Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014). Example values: 5 for EveTr Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>]

BaseTe

Description Base temperature for initiating senescence degree days (SDD) for leaf off. [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	See section 2.2 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>]; Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]. Example values: 10 EveTr Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>]

BaseTHDD

Description Base temperature for heating degree days [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Base temperature for heating degree days [°C] e.g. Sailor and Vasireddy (2006) [<i>SV06</i>]

beta

Description The light-saturated gross photosynthesis of the canopy. [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Example values: <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16: 43.35 Ruimy et al. (1995) [<i>R95</i>], 35 Schmid et al. (2000) [<i>S2000</i>], 16.3 Flanagan et al. (2002) [<i>FWC2002</i>] <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26: 17.793 Bellucco et al. (2017) [<i>B2017</i>] <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36: 8.474 Bellucco et al. (2017) [<i>B2017</i>]

theta

Description The convexity of the curve at light saturation.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Example value: <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26: 0.723 Bellucco et al. (2017) [B2017] <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36: 0.96 Bellucco et al. (2017) [B2017]

alpha_enh

Description Part of the *alpha* coefficient related to the fraction of vegetation.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Example value: 0.016 Bellucco et al. (2017) [B2017]

beta_enh

Description Part of the *beta* coefficient related to the fraction of vegetation.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Example values: 33.454 Bellucco et al. (2017) [B2017]

resp_a

Description Respiration coefficient a.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Example values: 1.08 Schmid et al. (2000) [S2000], 3.229 Järvi et al. (2012) [J12]

resp_b

Description Respiration coefficient b - related to air temperature dependency.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Example values: 0.0064 Schmid et al. (2000) [S2000], 0.0329 Järvi et al. (2012) [J12].

min_respi

Description Minimum soil respiration rate (for cold-temperature limit) [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Example values: 0.6 estimate from Hyytiälä forest site.

BiogenCO2Code

Description Code linking to the *Code* column in *SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to the <i>Code</i> column in <i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i> .

QF0_BEU_WD

Description Building energy use [W m^{-2}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Weekday building energy use [W m^{-2}] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

QF0_BEU_WE

Description Building energy use [W m^{-2}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Can be used for CO2 flux calculation. set to -999 Not used in this version.

Code

Description Code linking to a corresponding look-up table.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	L	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> for paved surfaces (Code_Paved), buildings (Code_Bldgs) and bare soil surfaces (Code_BSoil). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match codes specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	L	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> for evergreen trees and shrubs (Code_EveTr), deciduous trees and shrubs (Code_DecTr) and grass surfaces (Code_Grass). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match codes specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	L	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> for water surfaces (Code_Water). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	L	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> for snow surfaces (SnowCode). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	L	Code linking to the SoilTypeCode column in <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i> (for Paved, Bldgs and BSoil surfaces) and <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i> (for EveTr, DecTr and Grass surfaces). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	L	Code linking to the CondCode column in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	L	Code linking to the AnthropogenicCode column in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .

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Table 4.41 – continued from previous page

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> for irrigation modelling (IrrigationCode). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match codes specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to the <i>OHMCode_SummerWet</i> , <i>OHMCode_SummerDry</i> , <i>OHMCode_WinterWet</i> and <i>OHMCode_WinterDry</i> columns in <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i> , <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i> , <i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i> and <i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i> files. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	For buildings and paved surfaces, set to zero if there is more than one ESTM class per grid and the codes and surface fractions specified in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> will be used instead.
<i>SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to the <i>BiogenCO2Code</i> column in <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i> .

Code_Bldgs

Description Code for *Bldgs* surface characteristics linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_NonVeg.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for Bldgs surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i> , which contains the attributes describing buildings in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i> .

Code_BSoil

Description Code for *BSoil* surface characteristics linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_NonVeg.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i> .

Code_DecTr

Description Code for *DecTr* surface characteristics linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for DecTr surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i> , which contains the attributes describing deciduous trees and shrubs in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i> .

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs1

Description Code linking to *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs2

Description Code linking to *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs3

Description Code linking to *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs4

Description Code linking to *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs5

Description Code linking to *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Code_ESTMClass_Paved1

Description Code linking to *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Code_ESTMClass_Paved2

Description Code linking to *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Code_ESTMClass_Paved3

Description Code linking to *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code linking to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>

Code_EveTr

Description Code for *EveTr* surface characteristics linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for EveTr surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i> , which contains the attributes describing evergreen trees and shrubs in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i> .

Code_Grass

Description Code for *Grass* surface characteristics linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for Grass surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i> , which contains the attributes describing grass surfaces in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i> .

Code_Paved

Description Code for *Paved* surface characteristics linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_NonVeg.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for Paved surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i> , which contains the attributes describing paved areas in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i> . e.g. 331 means use the characteristics specified in the row of input file <i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i> which has 331 in column 1 (Code).

Code_Water

Description Code for *Water* surface characteristics linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Water.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for Water surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i> , which contains the attributes describing open water in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i> .

CondCode

Description Code for surface conductance parameters linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Conductance.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for surface conductance parameters Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i> , which contains the parameters for the Jarvis (1976) [Ja76] parameterisation of surface conductance. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i> . e.g. 33 means use the characteristics specified in the row of input file <i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i> which has 33 in column 1 (Code).

CRWMax

Description Maximum water holding capacity of snow [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Maximum water holding capacity of snow [mm]

CRWMin

Description Minimum water holding capacity of snow [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Minimum water holding capacity of snow [mm]

DayWat (1)

Description Irrigation allowed on Sundays [1], if not [0]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Sundays [1], if not [0]

DayWat (2)

Description Irrigation allowed on Mondays [1], if not [0]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Mondays [1], if not [0]

DayWat (3)

Description Irrigation allowed on Tuesdays [1], if not [0]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Tuesdays [1], if not [0]

DayWat (4)

Description Irrigation allowed on Wednesdays [1], if not [0]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Wednesdays [1], if not [0]

DayWat (5)

Description Irrigation allowed on Thursdays [1], if not [0]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Thursdays [1], if not [0]

DayWat (6)

Description Irrigation allowed on Fridays [1], if not [0]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Fridays [1], if not [0]

DayWat (7)

Description Irrigation allowed on Saturdays [1], if not [0]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Irrigation allowed on Saturdays [1], if not [0]

DayWatPer (1)

Description Fraction of properties using irrigation on Sundays [0-1]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Sundays [0-1]

DayWatPer (2)

Description Fraction of properties using irrigation on Mondays [0-1]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Mondays [0-1]

DayWatPer (3)

Description Fraction of properties using irrigation on Tuesdays [0-1]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Tuesdays [0-1]

DayWatPer (4)

Description Fraction of properties using irrigation on Wednesdays [0-1]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Wednesdays [0-1]

DayWatPer (5)

Description Fraction of properties using irrigation on Thursdays [0-1]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Thursdays [0-1]

DayWatPer (6)

Description Fraction of properties using irrigation on Fridays [0-1]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Fridays [0-1]

DayWatPer (7)

Description Fraction of properties using irrigation on Saturdays [0-1]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Saturdays [0-1]

DrainageCoef1

Description Coefficient D_0 [mm h⁻¹] used in *DrainageEq*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>DrainageEq</i> = 3, 10 for <i>Paved and Bldgs</i>; – <i>DrainageEq</i> = 2, 0.013 for <i>BSoil</i>
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>DrainageEq</i> = 3, 10 for <i>Grass</i> (irrigated); – <i>DrainageEq</i> = 2, 0.013 for <i>EveTr</i>, <i>DecTr</i>, <i>Grass</i> (unirrigated)
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Not currently used for water surface

DrainageCoef2**Description** Coefficient b [-] used in *DrainageEq***Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>DrainageEq</i> = 3, 3 for <i>Paved</i> and <i>Bldgs</i> – <i>DrainageEq</i> = 2, 1.71 for <i>BSoil</i>
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>DrainageEq</i> = 3, 3 for <i>Grass</i> (irrigated) – <i>DrainageEq</i> = 2, 1.71 for <i>EveTr</i>, <i>DecTr</i>, <i>Grass</i> (unirrigated)
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Not currently used for water surface

DrainageEq**Description** Calculation choice for Drainage equation**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Options: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 1: Falk and Niemczynowicz (1978) [<i>FN78</i>] – 2: Halldin et al. (1979) [<i>Ha79</i>] (Rutter eqn corrected for c=0, see Calder & Wright (1986) [<i>CW86</i>]) – 3: for <i>BSoil</i> Falk and Niemczynowicz (1978) [<i>FN78</i>]; for <i>Paved</i> and <i>Bldgs</i> Coefficients are specified in the following two columns. Recommended in this version.

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Table 4.76 – continued from previous page

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Options: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 1: Falk and Niemczynowicz (1978) [<i>FN78</i>] – 2: Halldin et al. (1979) [<i>Ha79</i>] (Rutter eqn corrected for c=0, see Calder & Wright (1986) [<i>CW86</i>]) – 3: for <i>EveTr</i>, <i>DecTr</i>, <i>Grass</i> (unirrigated) Falk and Niemczynowicz (1978) [<i>FN78</i>] Coefficients are specified in the following two columns. Recommended in this version.
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Not currently used for water surface.

EF_umolCO2perJ

Description Emission factor for fuels used for building heating.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Weekday building energy use [W m-2] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

Emissivity

Description Effective surface emissivity.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Effective surface emissivity. View factors should be taken into account.

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Table 4.78 – continued from previous page

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Example values [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.98 EveTr Oke (1987) <i>[Ok87]</i> • 0.98 DecTr Oke (1987) <i>[Ok87]</i> • 0.93 Grass Oke (1987) <i>[Ok87]</i>
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Example values [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.95 Water Oke (1987) <i>[Ok87]</i>
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Example values [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.99 Järvi et al. (2014) <i>[Leena2014]</i>

EndDLS

Description End of the day light savings [DOY]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	End of the day light savings [DOY] See <i>Day Light Savings (DLS)</i> .

EnEF_v_Jkm

Description Emission factor for heat [J klm⁻¹].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Emission factor for heat [J klm ⁻¹]. Example values: 3.97e6 Sailor and Lu (2004) <i>[SL04]</i>

EnergyUseProfWD

Description Code linking to *EnergyUseProfWD* in *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	L	Code for energy use profile (weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Look the codes Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .

EnergyUseProfWE

Description Code linking to *EnergyUseProfWE* in *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	L	Code for energy use profile (weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .

ESTMCode

Description Code for ESTM coefficients linking to *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	L	For paved and building surfaces, it is possible to specify multiple codes per grid (3 for paved, 5 for buildings) using <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> . In this case, set ESTMCode here to zero.
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	L	Code for ESTM coefficients to use for this surface. Links to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	L	Code for ESTM coefficients to use for this surface. Links to <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i> .

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Table 4.83 – continued from previous page

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	For paved and building surfaces, it is possible to specify multiple codes per grid (3 for paved, 5 for buildings) using <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> . In this case, set ESTM code here to zero.

FAI_Bldgs

Description Frontal area index for buildings [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Frontal area index for buildings [-] Required if <i>RoughLenMomMethod</i> = 3 in <i>RunControl.nml</i> .

FAI_DecTr

Description Frontal area index for deciduous trees [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Frontal area index for deciduous trees [-] Required if <i>RoughLenMomMethod</i> = 3 in <i>RunControl.nml</i> .

FAI_EveTr

Description Frontal area index for evergreen trees [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Frontal area index for evergreen trees [-] Required if <i>RoughLenMomMethod</i> = 3 in <i>RunControl.nml</i> .

Faut

Description Fraction of irrigated area that is irrigated using automated systems

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of irrigated area that is irrigated using automated systems (e.g. sprinklers).

FcEF_v_Jkm

Description Traffic emission factor for CO2.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Weekday building energy use [W m-2] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

fcld

Description Cloud fraction [tenths]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Cloud fraction [tenths]

FlowChange

Description Difference in input and output flows for water surface [mm h⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Difference in input and output flows for water surface [mm h ⁻¹] Used to indicate river or stream flow through the grid. Currently not fully tested!

Fraction1of8

Description Fraction of water that can flow to *GridConnection1of8* [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]

Fraction2of8

Description Fraction of water that can flow to *GridConnection2of8* [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]

Fraction3of8

Description Fraction of water that can flow to *GridConnection3of8* [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]

Fraction4of8

Description Fraction of water that can flow to *GridConnection4of8* [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]

Fraction5of8

Description Fraction of water that can flow to *GridConnection5of8* [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]

Fraction6of8

Description Fraction of water that can flow to *GridConnection6of8* [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]

Fraction7of8

Description Fraction of water that can flow to *GridConnection7of8* [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]

Fracti8of8

Description Fraction of water that can flow to *GridConnection8of8* [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]

Fr_Bldgs

Description Surface cover fraction of buildings [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of buildings [-]

Fr_Bsoil

Description Surface cover fraction of bare soil or unmanaged land [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of bare soil or unmanaged land [-]

Fr_DecTr

Description Surface cover fraction of deciduous trees and shrubs [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of deciduous trees and shrubs [-]

Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs1

Description Surface cover fraction of building class 1 used in ESTM calculations

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Columns 94-98 must add up to 1

Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs2

Description Surface cover fraction of building class 2 used in ESTM calculations

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Columns 94-98 must add up to 1

Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs3

Description Surface cover fraction of building class 3 used in ESTM calculations

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Columns 94-98 must add up to 1

Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs4

Description Surface cover fraction of building class 4 used in ESTM calculations

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Columns 94-98 must add up to 1

Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs5

Description Surface cover fraction of building class 5 used in ESTM calculations

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Columns 94-98 must add up to 1

Fr_ESTMClass_Paved1

Description Surface cover fraction of *Paved* surface class 1 used in ESTM calculations

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Columns 88-90 must add up to 1

Fr_ESTMClass_Paved2

Description Surface cover fraction of *Paved* surface class 2 used in ESTM calculations

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Columns 88-90 must add up to 1

Fr_ESTMClass_Paved3

Description Surface cover fraction of *Paved* surface class 3 used in ESTM calculations

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Columns 88-90 must add up to 1

Fr_EveTr

Description Surface cover fraction of *EveTr*: evergreen trees and shrubs [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of evergreen trees and shrubs [-]

Fr_Grass

Description Surface cover fraction of *Grass* [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of grass [-]

Fr_Paved

Description Surface cover fraction of *Paved* surfaces [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Columns 14 to 20 must sum to 1

Fr_Water

Description Surface cover fraction of open water [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface cover fraction of open water [-] (e.g. river, lakes, ponds, swimming pools)

FrFossilFuel_Heat

Description Fraction of fossil fuels used for building heating [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Weekday building energy use [W m-2] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

FrFossilFuel_NonHeat

Description Fraction of fossil fuels used for building energy use [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	0	Weekday building energy use [W m ⁻²] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

G1

Description Related to maximum surface conductance [mm s⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	MD	Related to maximum surface conductance [mm s ⁻¹]

G2

Description Related to Kdown dependence [W m⁻²]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	MD	Related to Kdown dependence [W m ⁻²]

G3

Description Related to VPD dependence [units depend on *gsModel*]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	MD	Related to VPD dependence [units depend on gsChoice in <i>RunControl.nml</i>]

G4

Description Related to VPD dependence [units depend on *gsModel*]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	MD	Related to VPD dependence [units depend on gsChoice in <i>RunControl.nml</i>]

G5

Description Related to temperature dependence [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to temperature dependence [°C]

G6

Description Related to soil moisture dependence [mm⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to soil moisture dependence [mm ⁻¹]

gamq_gkgm

Description vertical gradient of specific humidity [g kg⁻¹ m⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	vertical gradient of specific humidity (g kg ⁻¹ m ⁻¹)

gamt_Km

Description vertical gradient of potential temperature [K m⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	vertical gradient of potential temperature (K m ⁻¹) strength of the inversion

GDDFull

Description The growing degree days (GDD) needed for full capacity of the leaf area index (LAI) [°C].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	This should be checked carefully for your study area using modelled LAI from the DailyState output file compared to known behaviour in the study area. See section 2.2 Järvi et al. (2011) [J11] ; Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014) [Leena2014] for more details. Example values: 300 for <i>EveTr</i> Järvi et al. (2011) [J11]

Grid

Description a unique number to represent grid

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Grid numbers do not need to be consecutive and do not need to start at a particular value. Each grid must have a unique grid number. All grids must be present for all years. These grid numbers are referred to in Grid-Connections (columns 64-79) (N.B. Not available in this version.)

GridConnection1of8

Description Number of the 1st grid where water can flow to The next 8 pairs of columns specify the water flow between grids. The first column of each pair specifies the grid that the water flows to (from the current grid, column 1); the second column of each pair specifies the fraction of water that flow to that grid. The fraction (i.e. amount) of water transferred may be estimated based on elevation, the length of connecting surface between grids, presence of walls, etc. Water cannot flow from the current grid to the same grid, so the grid number here must be different to the grid number in column 1. Water can flow to a maximum of 8 other grids. If there is no water flow between grids, or a single grid is run, set to 0. See section on Grid Connections

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	The next 8 pairs of columns specify the water flow between grids. The first column of each pair specifies the grid that the water flows to (from the current grid, column 1); the second column of each pair specifies the fraction of water that flow to that grid. The fraction (i.e. amount) of water transferred may be estimated based on elevation, the length of connecting surface between grids, presence of walls, etc. Water cannot flow from the current grid to the same grid, so the grid number here must be different to the grid number in column 1. Water can flow to a maximum of 8 other grids. If there is no water flow between grids, or a single grid is run, set to 0. See section on Grid Connections

GridConnection2of8

Description Number of the 2nd grid where water can flow to

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Number of the grid where water can flow to

GridConnection3of8

Description Number of the 3rd grid where water can flow to

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Number of the grid where water can flow to

GridConnection4of8

Description Number of the 4th grid where water can flow to

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Number of the grid where water can flow to

GridConnection5of8

Description Number of the 5th grid where water can flow to

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Number of the grid where water can flow to

GridConnection6of8

Description Number of the 6th grid where water can flow to

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Number of the grid where water can flow to

GridConnection7of8

Description Number of the 7th grid where water can flow to

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Number of the grid where water can flow to

GridConnection8of8

Description Number of the 8th grid where water can flow to

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Number of the grid where water can flow to

gsModel

Description Formulation choice for conductance calculation.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] 2 (Recommended) Ward et al. (2016) [<i>W16</i>]

H_Bldgs

Description Mean building height [m]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Mean building height [m]

H_DecTr

Description Mean height of deciduous trees [m]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Mean height of deciduous trees [m]

H_EveTr

Description Mean height of evergreen trees [m]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Mean height of evergreen trees [m]

id

Description Day of year [DOY]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Not used: set to 1 in this version.
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Day of year [DOY]
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Day of year [DOY]
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Day of year [DOY]

Ie_a1

Description Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [mm d^{-1}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [mm d^{-1}]

Ie_a2

Description Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [$\text{mm d}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [$\text{mm d}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Ie_a3

Description Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [mm d^{-2}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [mm d^{-2}]

Ie_end

Description Day when irrigation ends [DOY]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Day when irrigation ends [DOY]

Ie_m1

Description Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d -1]

Ie_m2

Description Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d -1 K ⁻¹]

Ie_m3

Description Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d⁻²]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d -2]

Ie_start

Description Day when irrigation starts [DOY]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Day when irrigation starts [DOY]

ih

Description Hour [H]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Hour [H] Not used: set to 0 in this version.

imin

Description Minute [M]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Minute [M] Not used: set to 0 in this version.
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Minute [M]
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Minute [M]

InfiltrationRate

Description Infiltration rate.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Not currently used

Internal_albedo

Description Albedo of all internal elements for building surfaces only

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Albedo of all internal elements for building surfaces only

Internal_CHbld

Description Bulk transfer coefficient of internal building elements [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Bulk transfer coefficient of internal building elements [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$] (for building surfaces only and if <i>IbldCHmod</i> == 0 in <i>ESTMinput.nml</i>)

Internal_CHroof

Description Bulk transfer coefficient of internal roof [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Bulk transfer coefficient of internal roof [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$] (for building surfaces only and if <i>IbldCHmod</i> == 0 in <i>ESTMinput.nml</i>)

Internal_CHwall

Description Bulk transfer coefficient of internal wall [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	0	Bulk transfer coefficient of internal wall [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$] (for building surfaces only and if <i>IbldCHmod</i> == 0 in <i>ESTMinput.nml</i>)

Internal_emissivity

Description Emissivity of all internal elements for building surfaces only

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Emissivity of all internal elements for building surfaces only

Internal_k1

Description Thermal conductivity of the first layer [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thermal conductivity of the first layer [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Internal_k2

Description Thermal conductivity of the second layer [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	0	Thermal conductivity of the second layer [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Internal_k3

Description Thermal conductivity of the third layer [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	0	Thermal conductivity of the third layer [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Internal_k4

Description Thermal conductivity of the fourth layer [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	O	Thermal conductivity of the fourth layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Internal_k5

Description Thermal conductivity of the fifth layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	O	Thermal conductivity of the fifth layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Internal_rhoCp1

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the first layer[J m⁻³ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	MU	Volumetric heat capacity of the first layer[J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]

Internal_rhoCp2

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the second layer [J m⁻³ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	O	Volumetric heat capacity of the second layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]

Internal_rhoCp3

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the third layer[J m⁻³ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	O	Volumetric heat capacity of the third layer[J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]

Internal_rhoCp4

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the fourth layer [J m⁻³ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	O	Volumetric heat capacity of the fourth layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]

Internal_rhoCp5

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the fifth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Volumetric heat capacity of the fifth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Internal_thick1

Description Thickness of the first layer [m] for building surfaces only

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thickness of the first layer [m] for building surfaces only; set to -999 for all other surfaces

Internal_thick2

Description Thickness of the second layer [m]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the second layer [m] (if no second layer, set to -999.)

Internal_thick3

Description Thickness of the third layer [m]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the third layer [m] (if no third layer, set to -999.)

Internal_thick4

Description Thickness of the fourth layer [m]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the fourth layer [m] (if no fourth layer, set to -999.)

Internal_thick5

Description Thickness of the fifth layer [m]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	0	Thickness of the fifth layer [m] (if no fifth layer, set to -999.)

InternalWaterUse

Description Internal water use [mm h⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Internal water use [mm h ⁻¹]

IrrFr_DecTr

Description Fraction of deciduous trees that are irrigated [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of deciduous trees that are irrigated [-]

IrrFr_EveTr

Description Fraction of evergreen trees that are irrigated [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of evergreen trees that are irrigated [-] e.g. 50% of the evergreen trees/shrubs are irrigated

IrrFr_Grass

Description Fraction of *Grass* that is irrigated [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of grass that is irrigated [-]

IrrigationCode

Description Code for modelling irrigation linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Irrigation.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for modelling irrigation Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Irrigation.txt, which contains the model coefficients for estimation of the water use (used if WU_Choice = 0 in <i>Run-Control.nml</i>). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Irrigation.txt.

it**Description** Hour [H]**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Hour [H]
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Hour [H]

iy**Description** Year [YYYY]**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Year [YYYY]
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Year [YYYY]

kdiff**Description** Diffuse radiation [W m^{-2}].**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Recommended if SOLWEIGUse = 1

kdir**Description** Direct radiation [W m^{-2}].**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Recommended if SOLWEIGUse = 1

kdown**Description** Incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Must be $> 0 \text{ W m}^{-2}$.

Kmax

Description Maximum incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Maximum incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]

lai

Description Observed leaf area index [$\text{m}^{-2} \text{ m}^{-2}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Observed leaf area index [$\text{m}^{-2} \text{ m}^{-2}$]

LAIEq

Description LAI calculation choice.

Note: North and South hemispheres are treated slightly differently.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<p>Coefficients are specified in the following parameters: <i>LeafGrowthPower1</i>, <i>LeafGrowthPower2</i>, <i>LeafOffPower1</i> and <i>LeafOffPower2</i>.</p> <p>Options</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 1 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

LAIMax

Description full leaf-on summertime value

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	full leaf-on summertime value Example values: - 5.1 EveTr Breuer et al. (2003) [<i>Br03</i>] - 5.5 DecTr Breuer et al. (2003) [<i>Br03</i>] - 5.9 Grass Breuer et al. (2003) [<i>Br03</i>]

LAIMin

Description leaf-off wintertime value

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	leaf-off wintertime value Exam- ple values: - 4. EveTr Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] - 1. DecTr Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] - 1.6 Grass Grimmond and Oke (1991) [<i>G91</i>]

lat

Description Latitude [deg].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Use coordinate system WGS84. Positive values are northern hemisphere (negative southern hemisphere). Used in radiation calculations. Note, if the total modelled area is small the lati- tude and longitude could be the same for each grid but small differences in radiation will not be determined. If you are defin- ing the latitude and longitude differently between grids make certain that you provide enough decimal places.

ldown

Description Incoming longwave radiation [W m^{-2}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Incoming longwave radiation [W m^{-2}]

LeafGrowthPower1

Description a parameter required by LAI calculation in $LAIEq$

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Example values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $LAIEq = 0$: 0.03 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • $LAIEq = 1$: 0.04 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

LeafGrowthPower2

Description a parameter required by LAI calculation [K^{-1}] in $LAIEq$

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Example values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $LAIEq = 0$: 0.0005 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • $LAIEq = 1$: 0.001 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

LeafOffPower1

Description a parameter required by LAI calculation [K^{-1}] in $LAIEq$

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Example values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $LAIEq = 0$: 0.03 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • $LAIEq = 1$: -1.5 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

LeafOffPower2

Description a parameter required by LAI calculation [K^{-1}] in $LAIEq$

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Example values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $LAIEq = 0$: 0.0005 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • $LAIEq = 1$: 0.0015 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

lng

Description longitude [deg]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Use coordinate system WGS84. For compatibility with GIS, negative values are to the west, positive values are to the east (e.g. Vancouver = -123.12; Shanghai = 121.47) Note this is a change of sign convention between v2016a and v2017a See latitude for more details.

LUMPS_Cover

Description Limit when surface totally covered with water for LUMPS [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Limit when surface totally covered with water [mm] Used for LUMPS surface wetness control. Default recommended value of 1 mm from Loridan et al. (2011) [<i>L2011</i>].

LUMPS_DrRate

Description Drainage rate of bucket for LUMPS [mm h^{-1}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Drainage rate of bucket for LUMPS [mm h^{-1}] Used for LUMPS surface wetness control. Default recommended value of 0.25 mm h^{-1} from Loridan et al. (2011) [<i>L2011</i>].

LUMPS_MaxRes

Description Maximum water bucket reservoir [mm] Used for LUMPS surface wetness control.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Maximum water bucket reservoir [mm] Used for LUMPS surface wetness control. Default recommended value of 10 mm from Loridan et al. (2011) [<i>L2011</i>] .

MaxQFMet ab

Description Maximum value for human heat emission. [W m⁻²]

Example values: 175 Sailor and Lu (2004) [*SL04*]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	○	Weekday building energy use [W m ⁻²] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

MinQFMet ab

Description Minimum value for human heat emission. [W m⁻²]

Example values: 75 Sailor and Lu (2004) [*SL04*]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	○	Weekday building energy use [W m ⁻²] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

MaxConductance

Description The maximum conductance of each vegetation or surface type. [mm s⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Example values [mm s^{-1}] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7.4: EveTr Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 11.7: DecTr Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 33.1: Grass (unirrigated) Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 40.: Grass (irrigated) Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>]

NARP_Trans

Description Atmospheric transmissivity for NARP [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Atmospheric transmissivity for NARP [-] Value must in the range 0-1. Default recommended value of 1.

nroom

Description Number of rooms per floor for building surfaces only [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Number of rooms per floor for building surfaces only

OBS_SMCap

Description The maximum observed soil moisture. [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$ or kg kg^{-1}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Use only if soil moisture is observed and provided in the met forcing file and <i>SMDMethod</i> = 1 or 2. Use of observed soil moisture not currently tested

OBS_SMDepth

Description The depth of soil moisture measurements. [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	O	Use only if soil moisture is observed and provided in the met forcing file and <i>SMDMethod</i> = 1 or 2. Use of observed soil moisture not currently tested

OBS_SoilNotRocks

Description Fraction of soil without rocks. [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	O	Use only if soil moisture is observed and provided in the met forcing file and <i>SMDMethod</i> = 1 or 2. Use of observed soil moisture not currently tested

OHMCode_SummerDry

Description Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer, linking to *SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer. Links to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer. Links to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	L	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer. Links to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .

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Table 4.203 – continued from previous page

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .

OHMCode_SummerWet

Description Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer, linking to [SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt](#).

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .

OHMCode_WinterDry

Description Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter, linking to *SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter. Links to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter. Links to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter. Links to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter. Links to <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i> .

OHMCode_WinterWet

Description Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter, linking to *SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .

OHMThresh_SW

Description Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [°C] If 5-day running mean air temperature is greater than or equal to this threshold, OHM coefficients for summertime are applied; otherwise coefficients for wintertime are applied.

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Table 4.207 – continued from previous page

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [°C] If 5-day running mean air temperature is greater than or equal to this threshold, OHM coefficients for summertime are applied; otherwise coefficients for wintertime are applied.
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [°C] If 5-day running mean air temperature is greater than or equal to this threshold, OHM coefficients for summertime are applied; otherwise coefficients for wintertime are applied.
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Not actually used for Snow surface as winter wet conditions always assumed.

OHMThresh_WD

Description Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Not actually used for building and paved surfaces (as impervious).
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Note that OHM coefficients for wet conditions are applied if the surface is wet.
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Not actually used for water surface (as no soil surface beneath).
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Not actually used for Snow surface as winter wet conditions always assumed.

PipeCapacity

Description Storage capacity of pipes [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Storage capacity of pipes [mm] Runoff amounting to less than the value specified here is assumed to be removed by pipes.

PopDensDay

Description Daytime population density (i.e. workers, tourists) [people ha⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	○	Daytime population density (i.e. workers, tourists) [people ha ⁻¹] Population density is required if EmissionsMethod = 2 in <i>Run-Control.nml</i> . The model will use the average of daytime and night-time population densities, unless only one is provided. If daytime population density is unknown, set to -999.

PopDensNight

Description Night-time population density (i.e. residents) [people ha⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	○	Night-time population density (i.e. residents) [people ha ⁻¹] Population density is required if EmissionsMethod = 2 in <i>Run-Control.nml</i> . The model will use the average of daytime and night-time population densities, unless only one is provided. If night-time population density is unknown, set to -999.

PopProfWD

Description Code for population density profile (weekdays) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	○	Weekday building energy use [W m ⁻²] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

PopProfWE

Description Code for population density profile (weekends) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Weekday building energy use [W m-2] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

PorosityMax

Description full leaf-on summertime value Used only for *DecTr* (can affect roughness calculation)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	full leaf-on summertime value Used only for DecTr (can affect roughness calculation)

PorosityMin

Description leaf-off wintertime value Used only for *DecTr* (can affect roughness calculation)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	leaf-off wintertime value Used only for DecTr (can affect roughness calculation)

PrecipiLimAlb

Description Limit for hourly precipitation when the ground is fully covered with snow [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Limit for hourly precipitation when the ground is fully covered with snow. Then snow albedo is reset to AlbedoMax [mm]

PrecipLimSnow

Description Limit for hourly snowfall when the ground is fully covered with snow [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Auer (1974) [<i>Au74</i>]

pres

Description Barometric pressure [kPa]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Barometric pressure [kPa]

qe**Description** Latent heat flux [W m^{-2}]**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Latent heat flux [W m^{-2}]

qf**Description** Anthropogenic heat flux [W m^{-2}]**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Anthropogenic heat flux [W m^{-2}]

QF_A_WD**Description** Base value for QF on weekdays [$\text{W m}^{-2} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$]**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 2 Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.3081 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 0.1 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

QF_A_WE**Description** Base value for QF on weekends [$\text{W m}^{-2} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$]**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 2 Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.3081 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 0.1 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

QF_B_WD

Description Parameter related to heating degree days on weekdays [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 2 Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0099 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 0.0099 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

QF_B_WE

Description Parameter related to cooling degree days on weekends [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 2 Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0099 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 0.0099 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

QF_C_WD

Description Parameter related to heating degree days on weekdays [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 2 Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0102 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 0.0102 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

QF_C_WE

Description Parameter related to heating degree days on weekends [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU O</i>	Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0102 Järvi et al. (2011) [<i>J11</i>] • 0.0102 Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

q+_gkg

Description specific humidity at the top of CBL [g kg^{-1}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	specific humidity at the top of CBL (g kg^{-1})

q_gkg

Description specific humidity in CBL [g kg^{-1}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	specific humidity in CBL (g kg^{-1})

qh

Description Sensible heat flux [W m^{-2}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_ft.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Sensible heat flux [W m^{-2}]

qn

Description Net all-wave radiation [W m^{-2}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Required if <i>NetRadiationMethod</i> = 1.

qs

Description Storage heat flux [W m^{-2}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Storage heat flux [W m^{-2}]

RadMeltFactor

Description Hourly radiation melt factor of snow [$\text{mm W}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Hourly radiation melt factor of snow [$\text{mm W}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$]

rain

Description Rainfall [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Rainfall [mm]

RH

Description Relative Humidity [%]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Relative Humidity [%]

RunoffToWater

Description Fraction of above-ground runoff flowing to water surface during flooding [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MD MU</i>	Fraction of above-ground runoff flowing to water surface during flooding [-] Value must be in the range 0-1. Fraction of above-ground runoff that can flow to the water surface in the case of flooding.

S1

Description A parameter related to soil moisture dependence [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to soil moisture dependence [-] These will change in the future to ensure consistency with soil behaviour

S2

Description A parameter related to soil moisture dependence [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Related to soil moisture dependence [mm] These will change in the future to ensure consistency with soil behaviour

SatHydraulicCond

Description Hydraulic conductivity for saturated soil [mm s⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Hydraulic conductivity for saturated soil [mm s ⁻¹]

SDDFull

Description The sensence degree days (SDD) needed to initiate leaf off. [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	This should be checked carefully for your study area using modelled LAI from the DailyState output file compared to known behaviour in the study area. See section 2.2 Järvi et al. (2011) [J11] ; Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014) [Leena2014] for more details. Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -450: <i>EveTr</i> Järvi et al. (2011) [J11] -450: <i>DecTr</i> Järvi et al. (2011) [J11] -450: <i>Grass</i> Järvi et al. (2011) [J11]

snow**Description** Snowfall [mm]**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Required if <i>SnowUse</i> = 1

SnowClearingProfWD**Description** Code for snow clearing profile (weekdays) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for snow clearing profile (weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . e.g. 1 means use the characteristics specified in the row of input file <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> which has 1 in column 1 (Code).

SnowClearingProfWE**Description** Code for snow clearing profile (weekends) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for snow clearing profile (weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . e.g. 1 means use the characteristics specified in the row of input file <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> which has 1 in column 1 (Code). Providing the same code for <i>SnowClearingProfWD</i> and <i>SnowClearingProfWE</i> would link to the same row in <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> , i.e. the same profile would be used for weekdays and weekends.

SnowCode

Description Code for snow surface characteristics linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for snow surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i> , which contains the attributes describing snow surfaces in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i> .

snowDensMax

Description Maximum snow density [kg m^{-3}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Maximum snow density [kg m^{-3}]

snowDensMin

Description Fresh snow density [kg m^{-3}]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Fresh snow density [kg m^{-3}]

SnowLimPatch

Description Limit for the snow water equivalent when snow cover starts to be patchy [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	0	Limit of snow water equivalent when the surface is fully covered with snow. Not needed if <i>SnowUse = 0</i> in <i>RunControl.nml</i> . Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 190: Paved Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>] • 190: Bldgs Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>] • 190: BSoil Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	0	Limit of snow water equivalent when the surface is fully covered with snow. Not needed if <i>SnowUse = 0</i> in <i>RunControl.nml</i> . Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 190: EveTr Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>] • 190: DecTr Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>] • 190: Grass Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

SnowLimRemove

Description Limit of the snow water equivalent for snow removal from roads and roofs [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	0	Not needed if <i>SnowUse = 0</i> in <i>RunControl.nml</i> . Not available in this version. Example values [mm] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 40: <i>Paved</i> Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>] • 100: <i>Bldgs</i> Järvi et al. (2014) [<i>Leena2014</i>]

SoilDensity

Description Soil density [kg m⁻³]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Soil density [kg m ⁻³]

SoilDepth

Description Depth of soil beneath the surface [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Depth of sub-surface soil store [mm] i.e. the depth of soil beneath the surface

SoilStoreCap

Description Limit value for *SoilDepth* [mm]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	SoilStoreCap must not be greater than SoilDepth.

SoilTypeCode

Description Code for soil characteristics below this surface linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Soil.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for soil characteristics below this surface Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i> , which contains the attributes describing sub-surface soil for this surface type. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i> .
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for soil characteristics below this surface Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i> , which contains the attributes describing sub-surface soil for this surface type. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i> .

StartDLS

Description Start of the day light savings [DOY]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Start of the day light savings [DOY] See <i>Day Light Savings (DLS)</i> .

StateLimit

Description Upper limit to the surface state. [mm]

Currently only used for the water surface. Set to a large value (e.g. 20000 mm = 20 m) if the water body is substantial (lake, river, etc) or a small value (e.g. 10 mm) if water bodies are very shallow (e.g. fountains). WaterDepth (column 9) must not exceed this value.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Currently only used for the water surface
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Currently only used for the water surface
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Surface state cannot exceed this value. Set to a large value (e.g. 20000 mm = 20 m) if the water body is substantial (lake, river, etc) or a small value (e.g. 10 mm) if water bodies are very shallow (e.g. fountains). WaterDepth (column 9) must not exceed this value.

StorageMax

Description Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<p>Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy) Min and max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces). Not currently used for non-vegetated surfaces - set the same as <i>StorageMin</i>.</p> <p>Example values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.48 <i>Paved</i> • 0.25 <i>Bldgs</i> • 0.8 <i>BSoil</i>
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<p>Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy) Min/max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-off/leaf-on differences for vegetated surfaces) Only used for <i>DecTr</i> surfaces - set <i>EveTr</i> and <i>Grass</i> values the same as <i>StorageMin</i>.</p> <p>Example values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.3: <i>EveTr</i> Breuer et al. (2003) [<i>Br03</i>] • 0.8: <i>DecTr</i> Breuer et al. (2003) [<i>Br03</i>] • 1.9: <i>Grass</i> Breuer et al. (2003) [<i>Br03</i>]
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	<p>Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy) Min and max values are to account for seasonal variation - not used for water surfaces so set same as <i>StorageMin</i>.</p>

StorageMin

Description Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy).

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy). Min/max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces). Not currently used for non-vegetated surfaces - set the same as <i>StorageMax</i> . Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.48 <i>Paved</i> • 0.25 <i>Bldgs</i> • 0.8 <i>BSoil</i>
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy). Min/max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-off/leaf-on differences for vegetated surfaces). Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.3 <i>EveTr</i> Breuer et al. (2003) [<i>Br03</i>] • 0.3 <i>DecTr</i> Breuer et al. (2003) [<i>Br03</i>] • 1.9 <i>Grass</i> Breuer et al. (2003) [<i>Br03</i>]
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy). Min/max values are to account for seasonal variation - not used for water surfaces. Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -0.5 <i>Water</i>

SurfaceArea

Description Area of the grid [ha].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Area of the grid [ha].

Surf_k1

Description Thermal conductivity of the first layer [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thermal conductivity of the first layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Surf_k2

Description Thermal conductivity of the second layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Thermal conductivity of the second layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Surf_k3

Description Thermal conductivity of the third layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Thermal conductivity of the third layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Surf_k4

Description Thermal conductivity of the fourth layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Thermal conductivity of the fourth layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Surf_k5

Description Thermal conductivity of the fifth layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Thermal conductivity of the fifth layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Surf_rhoCp1

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the first layer [J m⁻³ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Volumetric heat capacity of the first layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]

Surf_rhoCp2

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the second layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Volumetric heat capacity of the second layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Surf_rhoCp3

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the third layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Volumetric heat capacity of the third layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Surf_rhoCp4

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the fourth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Volumetric heat capacity of the fourth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Surf_rhoCp5

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the fifth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Volumetric heat capacity of the fifth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Surf_thick1

Description Thickness of the first layer [m] for roofs (building surfaces) and ground (all other surfaces)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thickness of the first layer [m] for roofs (building surfaces) and ground (all other surfaces)

Surf_thick2

Description Thickness of the second layer [m] (if no second layer, set to -999.)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the second layer [m] (if no second layer, set to -999.)

Surf_thick3

Description Thickness of the third layer [m] (if no third layer, set to -999.)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the third layer [m] (if no third layer, set to -999.)

Surf_thick4

Description Thickness of the fourth layer [m] (if no fourth layer, set to -999.)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the fourth layer [m] (if no fourth layer, set to -999.)

Surf_thick5

Description Thickness of the fifth layer [m] (if no fifth layer, set to -999.)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the fifth layer [m] (if no fifth layer, set to -999.)

Tair

Description Air temperature [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Air temperature [°C]

tau_a

Description Time constant for snow albedo aging in cold snow [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Time constant for snow albedo aging in cold snow [-]

tau_f

Description Time constant for snow albedo aging in melting snow [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Time constant for snow albedo aging in melting snow [-]

tau_r

Description Time constant for snow density ageing [-]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Time constant for snow density ageing [-]

TCritic_Heating_WD

Description Critical heating temperature on weekdays [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

TCritic_Heating_WE

Description Critical heating temperature on weekends [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

TCritic_Cooling_WD

Description Critical cooling temperature on weekdays [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

TCritic_Cooling_WE

Description Critical cooling temperature on weekends [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	<i>MU 0</i>	Use with <i>EmissionsMethod</i> = 1

TempMeltFactor

Description Hourly temperature melt factor of snow [mm K⁻¹ h⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Hourly temperature melt factor of snow [mm K ⁻¹ h ⁻¹] (In previous model version, this parameter was 0.12)

TH

Description Upper air temperature limit [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Upper air temperature limit [°C]

Theta+_K

Description potential temperature at the top of CBL [K]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	potential temperature at the top of CBL (K)

Theta_K

Description potential temperature in CBL [K]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	potential temperature in CBL (K)

Ti_{air}

Description Indoor air temperature [C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Indoor air temperature [C]

Timezone

Description Time zone [h] for site relative to UTC (east is positive). This should be set according

to the times given in the meteorological forcing file(s).

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Time zone [h] for site relative to UTC (east is positive). This should be set according to the times given in the meteorological forcing file(s).

TL

Description Lower air temperature limit [°C]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Lower air temperature limit [°C]

ToBldgs

Description Fraction of water going to Bldgs

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Bldgs</i>

ToBSoil

Description Fraction of water going to BSoil

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>BSoil</i>

ToDecTr

Description Fraction of water going to DecTr

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>DecTr</i>

ToEveTr

Description Fraction of water going to *EveTr*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>EveTr</i>

ToGrass

Description Fraction of water going to *Grass*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Grass</i>

ToPaved

Description Fraction of water going to *Paved*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Paved</i>

ToRunoff

Description Fraction of water going to *Runoff*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Runoff</i>

ToSoilStore

Description Fraction of water going to *SoilStore*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>SoilStore</i>

ToWater

Description Fraction of water going to *Water*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Fraction of water going to <i>Water</i>

TraffProfWD

Description Code for traffic activity profile (weekdays) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.
Not used in v2018a.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	○	Weekday building energy use [W m-2] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

TraffProfWE

Description Code for traffic activity profile (weekends) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.
Not used in v2018a.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	○	Weekday building energy use [W m-2] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

TrafficUnits

Description Units for the traffic rate for the study area. Not used in v2018a.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	○	Weekday building energy use [W m-2] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

TrafficRate_WD

Description Weekday traffic rate [veh km m⁻² s-1] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation - not used in v2018a.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	○	Weekday traffic rate [veh km m-2 s-1] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

TrafficRate_WE

Description Weekend traffic rate [veh km m⁻² s-1] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation - not used in v2018a.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	0	Weekend traffic rate [veh km m-2 s-1] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation.

Troad

Description Ground surface temperature [C] (used when *TsurfChoice* = 1 or 2)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Ground surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 1 or 2)

Troof

Description Roof surface temperature [C] (used when *TsurfChoice* = 1 or 2)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Roof surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 1 or 2)

Tsurf

Description Bulk surface temperature [C] (used when *TsurfChoice* = 0)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Bulk surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 0)

Twall

Description Wall surface temperature [C] (used when *TsurfChoice* = 1)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 1)

Twall_e

Description East-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when *TsurfChoice* = 2)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	East-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 2)

Twall_n

Description North-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when *TsurfChoice* = 2)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	North-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 2)

Twall_s

Description South-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when *TsurfChoice* = 2)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	South-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 2)

Twall_w

Description West-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when *TsurfChoice* = 2)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	West-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 2)

U

Description Wind speed. [m s⁻¹.]Height of the wind speed measurement (*z*) is needed in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Height of the wind speed measurement (<i>z</i>) is needed in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .

Wall_k1

Description Thermal conductivity of the first layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Thermal conductivity of the first layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Wall_k2

Description Thermal conductivity of the second layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Thermal conductivity of the second layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Wall_k3

Description Thermal conductivity of the third layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Thermal conductivity of the third layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Wall_k4

Description Thermal conductivity of the fourth layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Thermal conductivity of the fourth layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Wall_k5

Description Thermal conductivity of the fifth layer [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Thermal conductivity of the fifth layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]

Wall_rhoCp1

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the first layer [J m⁻³ K⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Volumetric heat capacity of the first layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]

Wall_rhoCp2

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the second layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	O	Volumetric heat capacity of the second layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Wall_rhoCp3

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the third layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	O	Volumetric heat capacity of the third layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Wall_rhoCp4

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the fourth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	O	Volumetric heat capacity of the fourth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Wall_rhoCp5

Description Volumetric heat capacity of the fifth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	O	Volumetric heat capacity of the fifth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]

Wall_thick1

Description Thickness of the first layer [m] for building surfaces only; set to -999 for all other surfaces

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	MU	Thickness of the first layer [m] for building surfaces only; set to -999 for all other surfaces

Wall_thick2

Description Thickness of the second layer [m] (if no second layer, set to -999.)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the second layer [m] (if no second layer, set to -999.)

Wall_thick3

Description Thickness of the third layer [m] (if no third layer, set to -999.)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the third layer [m] (if no third layer, set to -999.)

Wall_thick4

Description Thickness of the fourth layer [m] (if no fourth layer, set to -999.)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the fourth layer [m] (if no fourth layer, set to -999.)

Wall_thick5

Description Thickness of the fifth layer [m] (if no fifth layer, set to -999.)

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	○	Thickness of the fifth layer [m] (if no fifth layer, set to -999.)

WaterDepth

Description Water depth [mm].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Set to a large value (e.g. 20000 mm = 20 m) if the water body is substantial (lake, river, etc) or a small value (e.g. 10 mm) if water bodies are very shallow (e.g. fountains). This value must not exceed StateLimit (column 8).

WaterUseProfAutoWD

Description Code for water use profile (automatic irrigation, weekdays) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for water use profile (automatic irrigation, weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .

WaterUseProfAutoWE

Description Code for water use profile (automatic irrigation, weekends) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for water use profile (automatic irrigation, weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .

WaterUseProfManuWD

Description Code for water use profile (manual irrigation, weekdays) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for water use profile (manual irrigation, weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .

WaterUseProfManuWE

Description Code for water use profile (manual irrigation, weekends) linking to *Code* of *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code for water use profile (manual irrigation, weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i> .

wdir

Description Wind direction [deg].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Not available in this version.

WetThreshold

Description Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface [mm].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface. Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.6 Paved • 0.6 Bldgs • 1. BSoil
<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface. Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.8 EveTr • 1. DecTr • 2. Grass
<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	<i>MD</i>	Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface. Example values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.5 Water

WithinGridBldgsCode

Description Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from *Bldgs* surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of *SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt*

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from Bldgs surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .

WithinGridBSoilCode

Description Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from *BSoil* surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of *SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from BSoil surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .

WithinGridDecTrCode

Description Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from *DecTr* surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of *SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from DecTr surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .

WithinGridEveTrCode

Description Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from *EveTr* surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of *SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>EveTr</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .

WithinGridGrassCode

Description Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from *Grass* surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of *SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>Grass</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .

WithinGridPavedCode

Description Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from *Paved* surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of *SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from <i>Paved</i> surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .

WithinGridWaterCode

Description Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from *Water* surfaces to surfaces in

columns 2-10 of *SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt*.

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>L</i>	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from Water surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of <i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i> .

Wuh

Description External water use [m³]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	External water use [m ³]

xsm

Description Observed soil moisture [m³ m⁻³ or kg kg⁻¹]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt</i>	<i>O</i>	Observed soil moisture [m ³ m ⁻³ or kg kg ⁻¹]

Year

Description Year [YYYY]

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	Year [YYYY] Years must be continuous. If running multiple years, ensure the rows in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> are arranged so that all grids for a particular year appear on consecutive lines (rather than grouping all years together for a particular grid).

z

Description Measurement height [m].

Configuration

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	z must be greater than the displacement height. Forcing data should be representative of the local-scale, i.e. above the height of the roughness elements.

z0**Description** Roughness length for momentum [m]**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	0	Value supplied here is used if <i>RoughLenMomMethod</i> = 1 in <i>RunControl.nml</i> ; otherwise set to '-999' and a value will be calculated by the model (<i>RoughLenMomMethod</i> = 2, 3).

zd**Description** Zero-plane displacement [m]**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	0	Value supplied here is used if <i>RoughLenMomMethod</i> = 1 in <i>RunControl.nml</i> ; otherwise set to '-999' and a value will be calculated by the model (<i>RoughLenMomMethod</i> = 2, 3).

zi0**Description** initial convective boundary layer height (m)**Configuration**

Referencing Table	Requirement	Comment
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	<i>MU</i>	initial convective boundary layer height [m]

4.2.15 Typical Values

Other values to add - please let us know

Generic Properties

Property	General Type	Value	Description	Reference
Albedo	Non Vegetated	0.09	Paved Helsinki	Järvi et al. (2014)
Albedo	Non Vegetated	0.15	Buildings Helsinki	Järvi et al. (2014)
Albedo	Non Vegetated	0.19	Bare Soil, Helsinki	Järvi et al. (2014)
Albedo	Non Vegetated	0.12	Paved	Oke (1987)
Albedo	Non Vegetated	0.15	Buildings	Oke (1987)
Albedo	Non Vegetated	0.21	Bare Soil	Oke (1987)
Emissivity	Non Vegetated	0.95	Paved	Oke (1987)
Emissivity	Non Vegetated	0.91	Buildings	Oke (1987)
Emissivity	Non Vegetated	0.93	Bare Soil	Oke (1987)
Surface Water storage capacity	Non Vegetated	0.48	Paved	Davies and Hollis (1981)
Surface Water storage capacity	Non Vegetated	0.25	Buildings	Falk and Niemczynowicz (1978)
Albedo	Vegetation	0.10	EveTr	
Albedo	Vegetation	0.12	DecTr	
Albedo	Vegetation	0.18	Grass	
Albedo	Vegetated	0.10	EveTr Helsinki	Järvi et al. (2014)
Albedo	Vegetated	0.16	DecTr Helsinki	Järvi et al. (2014)
Albedo	Vegetated	0.19	Grass Helsinki	Järvi et al. (2014)
Albedo	Vegetated	0.10	EveTr	Oke (1987)
Albedo	Vegetated	0.18	DecTr	Oke (1987)
Albedo	Vegetated	0.21	Grass	Oke (1987)
Emissivity	Vegetated	0.98	EveTr	Oke (1987)
Emissivity	Vegetated	0.98	DecTr	Oke (1987)
Emissivity	Vegetated	0.93	Grass	Oke (1987)
water Storage Minimum capacity (mm)	Vegetated	1.3	EveTr	Breuer et al. (2003)
water Storage Minimum capacity (mm)	Vegetated	0.3	DecTr	Breuer et al. (2003)
water Storage Minimum capacity (mm)	Vegetated	1.9	Grass	Breuer et al. (2003)
Maximum water storage capacity of this surface [mm]	Vegetated	1.3	EveTr	Breuer et al. (2003)
Maximum water storage capacity of this surface [mm]	Vegetated	0.8	DecTr	Grimmond and Oke (1991)
Maximum water storage capacity of this surface [mm]	Vegetated	1.9	Grass	Breuer et al. (2003)
Albedo Max(leaf on)	Vegetated	0.12	DecTr	
Albedo Max(leaf on)	Vegetated	0.18	Grass	
Albedo Max(leaf on)	Vegetated	0.10	EveTr Helsinki	Järvi et al. (2014)
Albedo Max(leaf on)	Vegetated	0.16	DecTr Helsinki	Järvi et al. (2014)
Albedo Max(leaf on)	Vegetated	0.19	Grass Helsinki	Järvi et al. (2014)

Continued on next page

Table 4.346 – continued from previous page

Property	General Type	Value	Description	Reference
Albedo Max(leaf on)	Vegetated	0.10	EveTr	Oke (1987)
Albedo Max(leaf on)	Vegetated	0.18	DecTr	Oke (1987)
Albedo Max(leaf on)	Vegetated	0.21	Grass	Oke (1987)
Emissivity *View factors should be taken into account	Vegetated	0.98	EveTr	Oke (1987)
Emissivity *View factors should be taken into account	Vegetated	0.98	DecTr	Oke (1987)
Emissivity *View factors should be taken into account	Vegetated	0.93	Grass	Oke (1987)
Minimum water storage capacity of this surface [mm] *Min & max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces).	Vegetated	1.3	EveTr	Breuer et al. (2003)
Minimum water storage capacity of this surface [mm]*Min and max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces).	Vegetated	0.3	DecTr	Breuer et al. (2003)
Minimum water storage capacity of this surface [mm] *Min and max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces).	Vegetated	1.9	Grass	Breuer et al. (2003)

Continued on next page

Table 4.346 – continued from previous page

Property	General Type	Value	Description	Reference
Maximum water storage capacity of this surface [mm] *Min and max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces)	Vegetated	1.3	EveTr	Breuer et al. (2003)
Maximum water storage capacity of this surface [mm] *Min and max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces)	Vegetated	0.8	DecTr	Grimmond and Oke (1991)
Maximum water storage capacity of this surface [mm] *Min and max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces)	Vegetated	1.9	Grass	Breuer et al. (2003)
AlbedoMin	Water	0.1	Water	Oke (1987)
AlbedoMax	Water	0.1	Water	Oke (1987)
Emissivity	Water	0.95	Water	Oke (1987)
Minimum water storage capacity of this surface [mm]	Water	0.5	Water	
Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy)	Water	0.5	Water	
WetThreshold	water	0.5	Water	

Continued on next page

Table 4.346 – continued from previous page

Property	General Type	Value	Description	Reference
StateLimit *Upper limit to the surface state [mm] *State cannot exceed this value. *Set to a large value (e.g. 20000 mm = 20 m) if the water body is substantial (lake/river/etc) or a small value (e.g. 10 mm) if water bodies are very shallow (e.g. fountains).	Water	20000	Water	
RadMeltFactor	Snow	0.0016	Hourly radiation melt factor of snow [mm W ⁻¹ h ⁻¹]	
TempMeltFactor	Snow	0.12	Hourly temperature melt factor of snow [mm °C ⁻¹ h ⁻¹]	
AlbedoMin	Snow	0-1	Minimum snow albedo [-] - 0.18	Järvi et al. (2014)
AlbedoMax *Maximum snow albedo (fresh snow) [-]	Snow	0.85		Järvi et al. (2014)
Emissivity *Effective surface emissivity. *View factors should be taken into account	Snow	0.99	Snow	Järvi et al. (2014)
tau_a *Time constant for snow albedo aging in cold snow [-]	Snow	0.018		Järvi et al. (2014)
tau_f *Time constant for snow albedo aging in melting snow [-]	Snow	0.11		Järvi et al. (2014)
PrecipiLimAlb	Snow	2	Limit for hourly precipitation when the ground is fully covered with snow. Then snow albedo is reset to AlbedoMax [mm]	
snowDensMin	Snow	100	Fresh snow density [kg m ⁻³]	
snowDensMax	Snow	400	Maximum snow density [kg m ⁻³]	

Continued on next page

Table 4.346 – continued from previous page

Property	General Type	Value	Description	Reference
tau_r *Time constant for snow density ageing [-]	Snow	0.043		Järvi et al. (2014)
CRWMin *Minimum water holding capacity of snow [mm]	Snow	0.05		Järvi et al. (2014)
CRWMax *Maximum water holding capacity of snow [mm]	Snow	0.20		Järvi et al. (2014)
PrecipLimSnow	Snow	2.2	Temperature limit when precipitation falls as snow [°C]	Auer (1974) [Au74]
SoilDepth	Snow	350	Depth of sub-surface soil store [mm] *depth of soil beneath the surface	
SoilStoreCap	Soil	150	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity of sub-surface soil store [mm] • how much water can be stored in the sub-surface soil when at maximum capacity. • (SoilStoreCap must not be greater than SoilDepth.) 	
SatHydraulicCond	Soil	0.0005	Hydraulic conductivity for saturated soil [mm s-1]	
SoilDensity	Soil	1.16	Soil density [kg m-3]	
InfiltrationRate	Soil		Infiltration rate [mm h-1]	
OBS_SMDepth	Soil		Depth of soil moisture measurements [mm]	
OBS_SMCap	Soil		Maximum observed soil moisture [m3 m-3 or kg kg-1]	
OBS_SoilNotRocks	Soil		Fraction of soil without rocks [-]	

Storage Heat Flux Related

OHM Coefficients

- Values determined from the literature
- If you have recommendations for others to be included please let us know.
- In the model run, canyons are excluded

Surface type	Description	Author (data source)	a1	a2	a3
Canyon	E-W canyon	Yoshida et al. (1990, 1991)	0.71	0.04	-39.7
	N-S canyon	Nunez (1974)	0.32	0.01	-27.7
Vegetation	Mixed forest	McCaughey (1985)	0.11	0.11	-12.3
	Short grass	Doll et al. (1985)	0.32	0.54	-27.4
	Bare soil	Novak (1982)	0.38	0.56	-27.3
	Bare soil (wet)	Fuchs & Hadas (1972)	0.33	0.07	-34.9
	Bare soil (dry)	Fuchs & Hadas (1972)	0.65	0.43	-36.5
	Bare soil	Asaeda & Ca (1993)	0.36	0.27	-42.4
	Water Shallow – Turbid	Souch et al. (1998)	0.50	0.21	-39.1
	Unirrigated grass (Crops)	Grimmond et al. (1993)	0.21	0.11	-16.1
	Short irrigated grass	Grimmond et al. (1993)	0.35	-0.01	-26.3
	Roof	Tar and gravel, Vancouver	Yap (1973)	0.17	0.10
Uppsala		Taesler (1980)	0.44	0.57	-28.9
Membrane and concrete, Kyoto		Yoshida et al. (1990,1991)	0.82	0.34	-55.7
Average gravel/tar/conc. flat industrial, Vancouver		Meyn (2000)	0.25	0.92	-22.0
Dry –gravel/tar/conc. flat industrial, Vancouver		Meyn (2000)	0.25	0.70	-22.0
Wet – gravel/tar/conc. flat industrial, Vancouver		Meyn (2000)	0.25	0.70	-22.0
Bitumen spread over flat industrial membrane, Vancouver		Meyn (2000)	0.06	0.28	-3.0

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Table 4.347 – continued from previous page

Surface type	Description	Author (data source)	a1	a2	a3
	Asphalt shingle on plywood residential roof , Vancouver	Meyn (2000)	0.14	0.33	-6.0
	Star – high albedo asphalt shingle residential roof	Meyn (2000)	0.09	0.18	-1.0
	Star - Ceramic Tile	Meyn (2000)	0.07	0.26	-6.0
	Star - Slate Tile	Meyn (2000)	0.08	0.32	0.0
	Helsinki – Sub-urban	Järvi et al. (2014)	0.19	0.54	-15.1
	Montreal – Sub-urban	Järvi et al. (2014)	0.12	0.24	-4.5
	Montreal – Urban	Järvi et al. (2014)	0.26	0.85	-21.4
Impervious	Concrete	Doll et al. (1985)	0.81	0.10	-79.9
	Concrete	Asaeda & Ca (1993)	0.85	0.32	-28.5
	Asphalt	Narita et al. (1984)	0.36	0.23	-19.3
	Asphalt	Asaeda & Ca (1993)	0.64	0.32	-43.6
	Asphalt	Anandakumar (1999)	0.82	0.68	-20.1
	Asphalt (winter)	Anandakumar (1999)	0.72	0.54	-40.2
	Asphalt (summer)	Anandakumar (1999)	0.83	-0.83	-24.6

The above text files (used to be stored as worksheets in **SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm** for versions prior to v2018a) can be edited directly (see [Data Entry](#)). Please note this file is subject to possible changes from version to version due to new features, modifications, etc. Please be aware of using the correct copy of this worksheet that are always shipped with the SUEWS public release.

Tip: See *SUEWS input converter* for conversion of input file between different versions.

4.3 Initial Conditions file

To start the model, information about the conditions at the start of the run is required. This information is provided in initial conditions file. One file can be specified for each grid (*MultipleInitFiles=1* in *RunControl.nml*, filename includes grid number) or, alternatively, a single file can be specified for all grids (*MultipleInitFiles=0* in *RunControl.nml*, no grid number in the filename). After that, a new *InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY.nml* file will be written for each grid for the following years. It is recommended that you look at these files (written to the input directory) to check the status of various surfaces at the end or the run. This may help you get more realistic starting

values if you are uncertain what they should be. Note this file will be created for each year for multiyear runs for each grid. If the run finishes before the end of the year the InitialConditions file is still written and the file name is appended with ‘_EndofRun’.

A sample file of **InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY.nml** looks like

```
&InitialConditions
LeavesOutInitially=0
SoilstorePavedState=150
SoilstoreBldgsState=150
SoilstoreEveTrstate=150
SoilstoreDecTrState=150
SoilstoreGrassState=150
SoilstoreBSoilState=150
BoInit=10
/
```

The two most important pieces of information in the initial conditions file is the soil moisture and state of vegetation at the start of the run. This is the minimal information required; other information can be provided if known, otherwise SUEWS will make an estimate of initial conditions.

The parameters and their setting instructions are provided through the links below:

Note: Variables can be in any order

- *Soil moisture states*
 - *SoilstorePavedState*
 - *SoilstoreBldgsState*
 - *SoilstoreEveTrState*
 - *SoilstoreDecTrState*
 - *SoilstoreGrassState*
 - *SoilstoreBSoilState*
- *Vegetation parameters*
 - *LeavesOutInitially*
 - *GDD_1_0*
 - *GDD_2_0*
 - *LAIinitialEveTr*
 - *LAIinitialDecTr*
 - *LAIinitialGrass*
 - *albEveTr0*
 - *albDecTr0*
 - *albGrass0*
 - *decidCap0*
 - *porosity0*
- *Recent meteorology*
 - *DaysSinceRain*
 - *Temp_C0*
- *Above ground state*
 - *PavedState*
 - *BldgsState*
 - *EveTrState*

- *DecTrState*
- *GrassState*
- *BSoilState*
- *WaterState*

- *Snow related parameters*

- *SnowInitially*
- *SnowWaterPavedState*
- *SnowWaterBldgsState*
- *SnowWaterEveTrState*
- *SnowWaterDecTrState*
- *SnowWaterGrassState*
- *SnowWaterBSoilState*
- *SnowWaterWaterState*
- *SnowPackPaved*
- *SnowPackBldgs*
- *SnowPackEveTr*
- *SnowPackDecTr*
- *SnowPackGrass*
- *SnowPackBSoil*
- *SnowPackWater*
- *SnowFracPaved*
- *SnowFracBldgs*
- *SnowFracEveTr*
- *SnowFracDecTr*
- *SnowFracGrass*
- *SnowFracBSoil*
- *SnowFracWater*
- *SnowDensPaved*
- *SnowDensBldgs*
- *SnowDensEveTr*
- *SnowDensDecTr*
- *SnowDensGrass*
- *SnowDensBSoil*
- *SnowDensWater*
- *SnowAlb0*

4.3.1 Soil moisture states

SoilstorePavedState

Requirement Required

Description Initial water stored in soil beneath *Paved* surface [mm]

Configuration For maximum values, see the used soil code in *SUEWS_Soil.txt*

SoilstoreBldgsState

Requirement Required

Description Initial water stored in soil beneath *Bldgs* surface [mm]

Configuration For maximum values, see the used soil code in *SUEWS_Soil.txt*

SoilstoreEveTrState

Requirement Required

Description Initial water stored in soil beneath *EveTr* surface [mm]

Configuration For maximum values, see the used soil code in *SUEWS_Soil.txt*

SoilstoreDecTrState

Requirement Required

Description Initial water stored in soil beneath *DecTr* surface [mm]

Configuration For maximum values, see the used soil code in *SUEWS_Soil.txt*

SoilstoreGrassState

Requirement Required

Description Initial water stored in soil beneath *Grass* surface [mm]

Configuration For maximum values, see the used soil code in *SUEWS_Soil.txt*

SoilstoreBSoilState

Requirement Required

Description Initial water stored in soil beneath *BSoil* surface [mm]

Configuration For maximum values, see the used soil code in *SUEWS_Soil.txt*

4.3.2 Vegetation parameters

LeavesOutInitially

Requirement Optional

Description Flag for initial leave status [1 or 0]

Configuration If the model run starts in winter when trees are bare, set *LeavesOutInitially* = 0 and the vegetation parameters will be set accordingly based on the values set in *SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm*. If the model run starts in summer when leaves are fully out, set *LeavesOutInitially* = 1 and the vegetation parameters will be set accordingly based on the values set in *SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm*. Not *LeavesOutInitially* can only be set to 0, 1 or -999 (fractional values cannot be used to indicate partial leaf-out). The value of *LeavesOutInitially* overrides any values provided for the individual vegetation parameters. To prevent *LeavesOutInitially* from setting the initial conditions, either omit it from the namelist or set to -999. If values are provided individually, they should be consistent the information provided in *SUEWS_Veg.txt* and the time of year. If values are provided individually, values for all required surfaces must be provided (i.e. specifying only *albGrass0* but not *albDecTr0* nor *albEveTr0* is not permitted).

GDD_1_0

Requirement Optional

Description GDD related initial value

Configuration Cannot be negative. If leaves are already full, then this should be the same as *GDDFull* in *SUEWS_Veg.txt*. If winter, set to 0. It is important that the vegetation characteristics are set correctly (i.e. for the start of the run in summer/winter).

GDD_2_0

Requirement Optional

Description GDD related initial value

Configuration Cannot be positive If the leaves are full but in early/mid summer then set to 0. If late summer or autumn , this should be a negative value. If leaves are off , then use the values of *SDDFull* in *SUEWS_Veg.txt* to guide your minimum value. It is important that the vegetation characteristics are set correctly (i.e. for the start of the run in summer/winter).

LAIinitialEveTr

Requirement Optional

Description Initial LAI for evergreen trees *EveTr*.

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

LAIinitialDecTr

Requirement Optional

Description Initial LAI for deciduous trees *DecTr*.

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

LAIinitialGrass

Requirement Optional

Description Initial LAI for irrigated grass *Grass*.

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

albEveTr0

Requirement Optional

Description Albedo of evergreen surface *EveTr* on day 0 of run

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

albDecTr0

Requirement Optional

Description Albedo of deciduous surface *DecTr* on day 0 of run

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

albGrass0

Requirement Optional

Description Albedo of grass surface *Grass* on day 0 of run

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

decidCap0

Requirement Optional

Description Storage capacity of deciduous surface *DecTr* on day 0 of run.

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

porosity0

Requirement Optional

Description Porosity of deciduous vegetation on day 0 of run.

Configuration This varies between 0.2 (leaf-on) and 0.6 (leaf-off). The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Veg.txt*

4.3.3 Recent meteorology

DaysSinceRain

Requirement Optional

Description Days since rain [d]

Configuration Important to use correct value if starting in summer season If starting when external water use is not occurring it will be reset with the first rain so can just be set to 0. If unknown, SUEWS sets to zero by default. Used to model irrigation.

Temp_C0

Requirement Optional

Description Initial air temperature [degC]

Configuration If unknown, SUEWS uses the mean temperature for the first day of the run.

4.3.4 Above ground state

PavedState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial wetness condition on *Paved*

Configuration If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).

BldgsState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial wetness condition on *Bldgs*

Configuration If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).

EveTrState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial wetness condition on *EveTr*

Configuration If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).

DecTrState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial wetness condition on *DecTr*

Configuration If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).

GrassState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial wetness condition on *Grass*

Configuration If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).

BSoilState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial wetness condition on *BSoil*

Configuration If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).

WaterState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial wetness condition on *Water*

Configuration For a large water body (e.g. river, sea, lake) set *WaterState* to a large value, e.g. 20000 mm; for small water bodies (e.g. ponds, fountains) set *WaterState* to smaller value, e.g. 1000 mm. This value must not exceed *StateLimit* specified in *SUEWS_Water.txt* . If unknown, model uses value of *WaterDepth* specified in *SUEWS_Water.txt* .

4.3.5 Snow related parameters

SnowInitially

Requirement Optional

Description Flag for initial snow status [0 or 1]

Configuration If the model run starts when there is no snow on the ground, set *SnowInitially* = 0 and the snow-related parameters will be set accordingly. If the model run starts when there is snow on the ground, the following snow-related parameters must be set appropriately. The value of *SnowInitially* overrides any values provided for the individual snow-related parameters. To prevent *SnowInitially* from setting the initial conditions, either omit it from the namelist or set to -999. If values are provided individually, they should be consistent the information provided in *SUEWS_Snow.txt* .

SnowWaterPavedState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on paved surfaces *Paved*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowWaterBldgsState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on buildings *Bldgs*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowWaterEveTrState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on evergreen trees *EveTr*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowWaterDecTrState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on deciduous trees *DecTr*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowWaterGrassState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on grass surfaces *Grass*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowWaterBSoilState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on bare soil surfaces *BSoil*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowWaterWaterState

Requirement Optional

Description Initial amount of liquid water in the snow in water *Water*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowPackPaved

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on paved surfaces *Paved*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowPackBldgs

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on buildings *Bldgs*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowPackEveTr

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on evergreen trees *EveTr*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowPackDecTr

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on deciduous trees *DecTr*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowPackGrass

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on grass surfaces *Grass*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowPackBSoil

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on bare soil surfaces *BSoil*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowPackWater

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on water *Water*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowFracPaved

Requirement Optional

Description Initial plan area fraction of snow on paved surfaces *Paved*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowFracBldgs

Requirement Optional

Description Initial plan area fraction of snow on buildings *Bldgs*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowFracEveTr

Requirement Optional

Description Initial plan area fraction of snow on evergreen trees *EveTr*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowFracDecTr

Requirement Optional

Description Initial plan area fraction of snow on deciduous trees *DecTr*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowFracGrass

Requirement Optional

Description Initial plan area fraction of snow on grass surfaces *Grass*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowFracBSoil

Requirement Optional

Description Initial plan area fraction of snow on bare soil surfaces *BSoil*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowFracWater

Requirement Optional

Description Initial plan area fraction of snow on water *Water*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowDensPaved

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow density on paved surfaces *Paved*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowDensBldgs

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow density on buildings *Bldgs*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowDensEveTr

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow density on evergreen trees *EveTr*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowDensDecTr

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow density on deciduous trees *DecTr*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowDensGrass

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow density on grass surfaces *Grass*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowDensBSoil

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow density on bare soil surfaces *BSoil*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowDensWater

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow density on *Water*

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

SnowAlb0

Requirement Optional

Description Initial snow albedo

Configuration The recommended values can be found from *SUEWS_Snow.txt*

4.4 Meteorological Input File

SUEWS is designed to run using commonly measured meteorological variables.

- Required inputs must be continuous – i.e. **gap fill** any missing data.
- The table below gives the must-use (MU) and optional (O) additional input variables.
- If an optional input variable is not available or will not be used by the model, enter ‘-999.0’ for this column.

- Since v2017a forcing files no longer need to end with two rows containing ‘-9’ in the first column.
- One single meteorological file can be used for all grids (**MultipleMetFiles=0** in *RunControl.nml*, no grid number in file name) if appropriate for the study area, or
- separate met files can be used for each grid if data are available (**MultipleMetFiles=1** in *RunControl.nml*, filename includes grid number).
- The meteorological forcing file names should be appended with the temporal resolution in minutes (SS_YYYY_data_tt.txt, or SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt for multiple grids).
- Separate met forcing files should be provided for each year.
- Files do not need to start/end at the start/end of the year, but they must contain a whole number of days.
- The meteorological input file should match the information given in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*.
- If a *partial year* is used that specific year must be given in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*.
- If *multiple years* are used, all years should be included in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*.
- If a *whole year* (e.g. 2011) is intended to be modelled using an hourly resolution dataset, the number of lines in the met data file should be 8760 and begin and end with:

```
iy      id  it  imin
2011    1   1   0 ...
...
2012    1   0   0 ...
```

4.4.1 SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt

Main meteorological data file.

No.	Use	Column Name	Description
1	<i>MU</i>	iy	Year [YYYY]
2	<i>MU</i>	id	Day of year [DOY]
3	<i>MU</i>	it	Hour [H]
4	<i>MU</i>	imin	Minute [M]
5	<i>O</i>	qn	Net all-wave radiation [W m^{-2}] Required if <i>NetRadiationMethod</i> = 0.
6	<i>O</i>	qh	Sensible heat flux [W m^{-2}]
7	<i>O</i>	qe	Latent heat flux [W m^{-2}]
8	<i>O</i>	qs	Storage heat flux [W m^{-2}]
9	<i>O</i>	qf	Anthropogenic heat flux [W m^{-2}]
10	<i>MU</i>	U	Wind speed [m s ⁻¹] Height of the wind speed measurement (z) is needed in <i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i> .
11	<i>MU</i>	RH	Relative Humidity [%]
12	<i>MU</i>	Tair	Air temperature [°C]
13	<i>MU</i>	pres	Barometric pressure [kPa]
14	<i>MU</i>	rain	Rainfall [mm]
15	<i>MU</i>	kdown	Incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}] Must be > 0 W m^{-2} .
16	<i>O</i>	snow	Snow [mm] Required if <i>SnowUse</i> = 1
17	<i>O</i>	ldown	Incoming longwave radiation [W m^{-2}]
18	<i>O</i>	fclد	Cloud fraction [tenths]
19	<i>O</i>	Wuh	External water use [m ³]
20	<i>O</i>	xsmd	Observed soil moisture [m ³ m ⁻³] or [kg kg ⁻¹]
21	<i>O</i>	lai	Observed leaf area index [m ² m ⁻²]
22	<i>O</i>	kdiff	Diffuse radiation [W m^{-2}] Recommended in this version. if <i>SOLWEIGUse</i> = 1
23	<i>O</i>	kdir	Direct radiation [W m^{-2}] Recommended in this version. if <i>SOLWEIGUse</i> = 1
24	<i>O</i>	wdir	Wind direction [°] Not available in this version.

4.5 CBL input files

Main references for this part of the model: Onomura et al. (2015) [*Shiho2015*] and Cleugh and Grimmond (2001) [*CG2001*].

If CBL slab model is used (*CBLuse* = 1 in *RunControl.nml*) the following files are needed.

Filename	Purpose
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	Gives initial data every morning * when CBL slab model starts running. * filename must match the InitialData_FileName in CBLInput.nml * fixed formats.
<i>CBLInput.nml</i>	Specifies run options, parameters and input file names. * Can be in any order

4.5.1 CBL_initial_data.txt

This file should give initial data every morning when CBL slab model starts running. The file name should match the InitialData_FileName in CBLInput.nml.

Definitions and example file of initial values prepared for Sacramento.

No.	Column name	Description
1	id	Day of year [DOY]
2	zi0	Initial convective boundary layer height (m)
3	gamt_Km	Vertical gradient of potential temperature (K m^{-1}) strength of the inversion
4	gamq_gkgm	Vertical gradient of specific humidity ($\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$)
5	Theta+_K	Potential temperature at the top of CBL (K)
6	q+_gkg	Specific humidity at the top of CBL (g kg^{-1})
7	Theta_K	Potential temperature in CBL (K)
8	q_gkg	Specific humidity in CBL (g kg^{-1})

- gamt_Km and gamq_gkgm written to two significant figures are required for the model performance in appropriate ranges [*Shiho2015*].

id	zi0	gamt_Km	gamq_gkgm	Theta+_K	q+_gkg	theta_K	q_gkg
234	188	0.0032	0.00082	290.4	9.6	288.7	8.3
235	197	0.0089	0.089	290.2	8.4	288.3	8.7

4.5.2 CBLInput.nml

sample file of **CBLInput.nml** looks like

```
&CBLInput
EntrainmentType=1      ! 1.Tennekes and Driedonks(1981), 2.McNaughton and
↳Springgs(1986), 3.Rayner and Watson(1991),4.Tennekes(1973),
QH_choice=1           ! 1.suews 2.lumps 3.obs
CO2_included=0
cblday(236)=1
cblday(258)=1
cblday(259)=1
cblday(260)=1
cblday(285)=1
cblday(297)=1
wsb=-0.01
InitialData_use=1
InitialDataFileName='CBLinputfiles/CBL_initial_data.txt'
sondeflag=0
FileSonde(234)='CBLinputfiles\Sonde_Sc_1991_0822_0650.txt'
FileSonde(235)='CBLinputfiles\Sonde_Sc_1991_0823_0715.txt'
FileSonde(236)='CBLinputfiles\Sonde_Sc_1991_0824_0647.txt'
FileSonde(238)='CBLinputfiles\Sonde_Sc_1991_0826_0642.txt'
FileSonde(239)='CBLinputfiles\Sonde_Sc_1991_0827_0640.txt'
FileSonde(240)='CBLinputfiles\Sonde_Sc_1991_0828_0640.txt'
/
```

Note: The file contents can be in any order.

The parameters and their setting instructions are provided through *the links below*:

- *EntrainmentType*
- *QH_Choice*

- *InitialData_use*
- *Sondeflag*
- *CBLday(id)*
- *CO2_included*
- *FileSonde(id)*
- *InitialDataFileName*
- *Wsb*

CBLinput

EntrainmentType

Requirement Required

Description Determines entrainment scheme. See Cleugh and Grimmond 2000 [16] for details.

Configuration

Value	Comments
1	Tennekes and Driedonks (1981) - Recommended in this version.
2	McNaughton and Springs (1986)
3	Rayner and Watson (1991)
4	Tennekes (1973)

QH_Choice

Requirement Required

Description Determines QH used for CBL model.

Configuration

Value	Comments
1	QH modelled by SUEWS
2	QH modelled by LUMPS
3	Observed QH values are used from the meteorological input file

InitialData_use

Requirement Required

Description Determines initial values (see *CBL_initial_data.txt*)

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	All initial values are calculated. Not available in this version.
1	Take <i>zi0</i> , <i>gamt_Km</i> and <i>gamq_gkgm</i> from input data file. <i>Theta+_K</i> , <i>q+_gkg</i> , <i>Theta_K</i> and <i>q_gkg</i> are calculated using <i>Temp_C</i> , <i>avrh</i> and <i>Pres_kPa</i> in meteorological input file.
2	Take all initial values from input data file (see <i>CBL_Initial_data.txt</i>).

Sondeflag

Requirement Required

Description to fill

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	Does not read radiosonde vertical profile data - Recommended in this version.
1	Reads radiosonde vertical profile data

CBLday (id)

Requirement Required

Description Set CBLday(id) = 1 If CBL model is set to run for DOY 175–177, CBLday(175) = 1, CBLday(176) = 1, CBLday(177) = 1

Configuration to fill

CO2_included

Requirement Required

Description Set to zero in current version

Configuration to fill

FileSonde (id)

Requirement Required

Description If Sondeflag=1, write the file name including the path from site directory e.g. FileSonde(id)= 'CBLinputfilesXXX.txt', XXX is an arbitrary name.

Configuration to fill

InitialDataFileName

Requirement Required

Description If InitialData_use 1, write the file name including the path from site directory e.g. InitialDataFileName='CBLinputfilesCBL_initial_data.txt'

Configuration to fill

Wsb

Requirement Required

Description Subsidence velocity (m s^{-1}) in eq. 1 and 2 of Onomura et al. (2015) [17]. (-0.01 m s^{-1} **Recommended in this version.**)

Configuration to fill

4.6 ESTM-related files

4.6.1 SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt

Note ESTM is under development in this release and should not be used!

The Element Surface Temperature Method (ESTM) (Offerle et al., 2005) calculates the net storage heat flux from surface temperatures. In the method the three-dimensional urban volume is reduced to four 1-d elements (i.e. building roofs, walls, and internal mass and ground (road, vegetation, etc)). The storage heat flux is calculated from the heat conduction through the different elements. For the inside surfaces of the roof and walls, and both surfaces for the internal mass (ceilings/floors, internal walls), the surface temperature of the element is determined by setting the

conductive heat transfer out of (in to) the surface equal to the radiative and convective heat losses (gains). Each element (roof, wall, internal element and ground) can have maximum five layers and each layer has three parameters tied to it: thickness (x), thermal conductivity (k), volumetric heat capacity (rhoCp).

If ESTM is used (QSchoice=4), the files *SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt*, *ESTMinput.nml* and *SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt* should be prepared.

SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt contains the parameters for the layers of each of the elements (roofs, wall, ground, internal mass).

- If less than five layers are used, the parameters for unused layers should be set to -999.
- The ESTM coefficients with the prefix *Surf_* must be specified for each surface type (plus snow) but the *Wall_* and *Internal_* variables apply to the building surfaces only.
- For each grid, one set of ESTM coefficients must be specified for each surface type; for paved and building surfaces it is possible to specify up to three and five sets of coefficients per grid (e.g. to represent different building materials) using the relevant columns in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*. For the model to use these columns in site select, the ESTMCode column in *SUEWS_NonVeg.txt* should be set to zero.

The following input files are required if ESTM is used to calculate the storage heat flux.

4.6.2 ESTMinput.nml

ESTMinput.nml specifies the model settings and default values.

A sample file of **ESTMinput.nml** looks like

```
&ESTMinput
TsurfChoice= 0
evolveTibld= 0      ! !!!!!FO!!!! 0 originally
ibldCHmod = 0
LBC_soil  = 13.00      !!FO!! 4, 8 or 17 degC - could be set as the annual_
↳mean air temperature (12.8 degC for London)
THEAT_ON  = 18.
THEAT_OFF = 22.
THEAT_FIX = 19.
/
```

Note: The file contents can be in any order.

The parameters and their setting instructions are provided through [the links below](#):

- *TsurfChoice*
- *evolveTibld*
- *IbldCHmod*
- *LBC_soil*
- *Theat_fix*
- *Theat_off*
- *Theat_on*

ESTMinput

TsurfChoice

Requirement Required

Description Source of surface temperature data used.

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	<i>Tsurf</i> in <i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i> used for all surface elements.
1	Input surface temperature are different for ground, roof and wall.
2	Wall surface temperature is different for four directions.

evolveTibld

Requirement Required

Description Source of internal building temperature (Tibld)

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	<i>Tair</i> in <i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i> used.
1	Tibld calculated considering the effect of anthropogenic heat from HVAC
2	Tibld calculated without considering the influence of HVAC.

IbldCHmod

Requirement Required

Description Method to calculate internal convective heat exchange coefficients (CH) for internal building, wall and roof if evolveTibld is 1 or 2.

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	CHs are read from SUEWS_ESTMcoefficients.txt.
1	CHs are calculated based on ASHRAE (2001)
2	CHs are calculated based on Awbi (1998).

LBC_soil

Requirement Required

Description Soil temperature at lowest boundary condition [C]

Configuration to fill

Theat_fix

Requirement Required

Description Ideal internal building temperature [C]

Configuration to fill

Theat_off

Requirement Required

Description Temperature at which heat control is turned off (used when evolveTibld=1) [C]

Configuration to fill

Theat_on

Requirement Required

Description Temperature at which heat control is turned on (used when evolveTibld =1) [C]

Configuration to fill

4.6.3 SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt

SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt contains a time-series of input surface temperature for roof, wall, ground and internal elements.

No.	Column Name	Use	Description
1	<i>iy</i>	<i>MU</i>	Year [YYYY]
2	<i>id</i>	<i>MU</i>	Day of year [DOY]
3	<i>it</i>	<i>MU</i>	Hour [H]
4	<i>imin</i>	<i>MU</i>	Minute [M]
5	<i>Tiair</i>	<i>MU</i>	Indoor air temperature [C]
6	<i>Tsurf</i>	<i>MU</i>	Bulk surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfCoice</i> = 0)
7	<i>Troof</i>	<i>MU</i>	Roof surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 1 or 2)
8	<i>Troad</i>	<i>MU</i>	Ground surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 1 or 2)
9	<i>Twall</i>	<i>MU</i>	Wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 1)
10	<i>Twall_n</i>	<i>MU</i>	North-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 2)
11	<i>Twall_e</i>	<i>MU</i>	East-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 2)
12	<i>Twall_s</i>	<i>MU</i>	South-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 2)
13	<i>Twall_w</i>	<i>MU</i>	West-facing wall surface temperature [C] (used when <i>TsurfChoice</i> = 2)

4.7 SOLWEIG input files

If the SOLWEIG model option is used (SOLWEIGout=1), spatial data and a SOLWEIGInput.nml file need to be prepared. The Digital Surface Models (DSMs) as well as derivatives originating from DSMs, e.g. Sky View Factors (SVF) must have the same spatial resolution and extent. Since SOLWEIG is a 2D model it will considerably increase computation time and should be used with care.

Description of choices in SOLWEIGinput_file.nml file. The file can be in any order.

- *SOLWEIGinput*
 - *Posture*
 - *usevegdem*
 - *onlyglobal*
 - *SOLWEIGpoi_out*
 - *Tmrt_out*
 - *Lup2d_out*
 - *Ldown2d_out*
 - *Kup2d_out*
 - *Kdown2d_out*
 - *GVF_out*
 - *SOLWEIG_ldown*
 - *RunForGrid*
 - *absK*
 - *absL*
 - *BuildingName*
 - *CDSMname*

- *col*
- *DSMname*
- *DSMPath*
- *heightgravity*
- *OutInterval*
- *row*
- *SVFPath*
- *SVFSuffix*
- *TDSMname*
- *TransMax*
- *TransMin*

4.7.1 SOLWEIGinput

Posture

Requirement Required

Description Determines the posture of a human for which the radiant fluxes should be considered

Configuration

Value	Comments
1	Standing (default)
2	Sitting

usevegdem

Requirement Required

Description Vegetation scheme

Configuration

Value	Comments
1	Vegetation scheme is active (Lindberg and Grimmond 2011 [19])
2	No vegetation scheme used

onlyglobal

Requirement Required

Description Global radiation

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	Diffuse and direct shortwave radiation taken from met forcing file.
1	Diffuse and direct shortwave radiation calculated from Reindl et al. (1990) [Re90]

SOLWEIGpoi_out

Requirement Required

Description Write output variables at point of interest (see below)

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	No POI output

Tmrt_out**Requirement** Required**Description**

•

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	No grid output
1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)

Lup2d_out**Requirement** Required**Description**

•

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	No grid output
1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)

Ldown2d_out**Requirement** Required**Description**

•

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	No grid output
1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)

Kup2d_out**Requirement** Required**Description**

•

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	No grid output
1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)

Kdown2d_out

Requirement Required

Description

•

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	No grid output
1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)

GVF_out

Requirement Required

Description

•

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	No grid output
1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)

SOLWEIG_1down

Requirement Required

Description

•

Configuration

Value	Comments
0	Not active (use SUEWS to estimate Ldown above canyon)
1	Use SOLWEIG to estimate Ldown above canyon

RunForGrid

Requirement Required

Description Grid for which SOLWEIG should be run.

Configuration

Value	Comments
-999	All grids (use with care)

absK

Requirement Required

Description Recommended value: 0.70

Configuration to fill

absL**Requirement** Required**Description** Recommended value: 0.97**Configuration** to fill**BuildingName****Requirement** Required**Description** Boolean matrix for locations of building pixels**Configuration** to fill**CDSMname****Requirement** Required**Description** Vegetation canopy DSM**Configuration** to fill**col****Requirement** Required**Description** Y coordinate for point of interest. Here all variables from the model will written to SOLWEIGpoiOUT.txt**Configuration** to fill**DSMname****Requirement** Required**Description** Ground and Building DSM**Configuration** to fill**DSMPath****Requirement** Required**Description** Path to Digital Surface Models (DSM).**Configuration** to fill**heightgravity****Requirement** Required**Description** Recommended value for a standing man: 1.1 m**Configuration** to fill**OutInterval****Requirement** Required**Description** Output interval. Set to 60 in current version.**Configuration** to fill**row****Requirement** Required**Description** X coordinate for point of interest. Here all variables from the model will written to SOLWEIGpoiOUT.txt

Configuration to fill

SVFPath

Requirement Required

Description Path to SVFs matrices (See Lindberg and Grimmond (2011) [19] for details)

Configuration to fill

SVFSuffix

Requirement Required

Description Suffix used (if any)

Configuration to fill

TDSMname

Requirement Required

Description Vegetation trunk zone DSM

Configuration to fill

TransMax

Requirement Required

Description Recommended value: 0.50 (Konarska et al. 2014 [*Ko14*])

Configuration to fill

TransMin

Requirement Required

Description Recommended value: 0.02 (Konarska et al. 2014 [*Ko14*])

Configuration to fill

4.8 SUEWS input converter

SUEWS input converter is a Python 3 script to convert input files between different versions based on pre-defined rules.

4.8.1 How to use

Download the converter script and rule.csv below, and specify these arguments in the script:

1. `fromVer`: which version to convert from.
2. `toVer`: which version to convert to.
3. `fromDir`: where the input files are located.
4. `toDir`: where the converted files are produced.

4.8.2 Downloads

- SUEWS input converter in python
SUEWS_TableConverter.py
- Rules for conversions between different SUEWS versions
rules.csv

4.8.3 Description of rules

The converter currently picks up the following types of actions:

1. Add: New entries or files to be added with default values.
2. Rename: Entries to be renamed from one version to another.
3. Delete: Entries to be deleted from one version to another.

Note: For entries introduced in a version via a new file, the new file will be created to hold the new entries without extra delaration for new files.

The current available rules are listed below:

From	To	Action	File	Variable	Column	Value
2017a	2018a	Delete	RunControl.nml	anthropco2method	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Rename	RunControl.nml	AnthropHeatMethod	-999	EmissionsMethod
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	AHMin_WD	9	15
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	AHMin_WE	10	15
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	AHSlope_Heating_WD	11	2.7
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	AHSlope_Heating_WE	12	2.7
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	AHSlope_Cooling_WD	13	2.7
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	AHSlope_Cooling_WE	14	2.7
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	TCritic_Heating_WD	15	7
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	TCritic_Heating_WE	16	7
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	TCritic_Cooling_WD	17	7
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	TCritic_Cooling_WE	18	7
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	EnergyUseProfWD	19	44
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	EnergyUseProfWE	20	45
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	ActivityProfWD	21	55663
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	ActivityProfWE	22	55664
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	TraffProfWD	23	701
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	TraffProfWE	24	702
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	PopProfWD	25	801
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	PopProfWE	26	802
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	MinQFMetab	27	75
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	MaxQFMetab	28	175
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	FrFossilFuel_Heat	29	0.05
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	FrFossilFuel_NonHeat	30	0
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	EF_umolCO2perJ	31	1.159
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	EnEF_v_Jkm	32	3.97E+06
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	FcEF_v_kgkm	33	0.285

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Table 4.348 – continued from previous page

From	To	Action	File	Variable	Column	Value
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	TrafficUnits	34	1
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	EnergyUseProfWD	19	-999
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	EnergyUseProfWE	20	-999
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	ActivityProfWD	21	-999
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	ActivityProfWE	22	-999
2017a	2018a	Delete	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	AHMin	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Delete	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	AHSlope	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Delete	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	TCritic	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Rename	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	QF_A_Weekday	-999	QF_A_WD
2017a	2018a	Rename	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	QF_B_Weekday	-999	QF_B_WD
2017a	2018a	Rename	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	QF_C_Weekday	-999	QF_C_WD
2017a	2018a	Rename	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	QF_A_Weekend	-999	QF_A_WE
2017a	2018a	Rename	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	QF_B_Weekend	-999	QF_B_WE
2017a	2018a	Rename	SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt	QF_C_Weekend	-999	QF_C_WE
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt	Code	1	31
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt	alpha	2	0.004
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt	beta	3	8.747
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt	theta	4	0.96
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt	alpha_enh	5	0.016
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt	beta_enh	6	33.353
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt	resp_a	7	2.43
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt	resp_b	8	0
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt	min_respi	9	0.6
2017a	2018a	Delete	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	TrafficRate	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Delete	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	BuildEnergyUse	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Delete	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	EnergyUseProfWD	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Delete	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	EnergyUseProfWE	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Delete	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	ActivityProfWD	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Delete	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	ActivityProfWE	-999	-999
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	TrafficRate_WD	34	0.01
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	TrafficRate_WE	35	0.01
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	QF0_BEU_WD	36	0.88
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	QF0_BEU_WE	37	0.88
2017a	2018a	Add	SUEWS_Veg.txt	BiogenCO2Code	38	31
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Conductance.txt	gsModel	13	1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_NonVeg.txt	OHMThresh_SW	19	10
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_NonVeg.txt	OHMThresh_WD	20	0.9
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_NonVeg.txt	ESTMCode	21	806
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_NonVeg.txt	AnOHM_Cp	22	20000000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_NonVeg.txt	AnOHM_Kk	23	1.2
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_NonVeg.txt	AnOHM_Ch	24	4
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Snow.txt	OHMThresh_SW	20	10
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Snow.txt	OHMThresh_WD	21	0.9
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Snow.txt	ESTMCode	22	61
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Snow.txt	AnOHM_Cp	23	100000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Snow.txt	AnOHM_Kk	24	1.2
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Snow.txt	AnOHM_Ch	25	4
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Water.txt	WaterDepth	9	0
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Water.txt	OHMThresh_SW	17	10

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Table 4.348 – continued from previous page

From	To	Action	File	Variable	Column	Value
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Water.txt	OHMThresh_WD	18	0.9
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Water.txt	ESTMCode	19	60
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Water.txt	AnOHM_Cp	20	100000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Water.txt	AnOHM_Kk	21	1.2
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Water.txt	AnOHM_Ch	22	4
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Veg.txt	PorosityMin	20	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Veg.txt	PorosityMax	21	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Veg.txt	OHMThresh_SW	32	10
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Veg.txt	OHMThresh_WD	33	0.9
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Veg.txt	ESTMCode	34	200
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Veg.txt	AnOHM_Cp	35	100000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Veg.txt	AnOHM_Kk	36	1.2
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_Veg.txt	AnOHM_Ch	37	4
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Code	1	800
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_thick1	2	0.1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_k1	3	0.74
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_rhoCp1	4	1500000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_thick2	5	0.1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_k2	6	0.93
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_rhoCp2	7	1500000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_thick3	8	0.05
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_k3	9	0.06
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_rhoCp3	10	70000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_thick4	11	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_k4	12	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_rhoCp4	13	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_thick5	14	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_k5	15	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Surf_rhoCp5	16	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_thick1	17	0.1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_k1	18	1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_rhoCp1	19	1600000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_thick2	20	0.1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_k2	21	1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_rhoCp2	22	1600000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_thick3	23	0.1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_k3	24	1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_rhoCp3	25	1600000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_thick4	26	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_k4	27	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_rhoCp4	28	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_thick5	29	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_k5	30	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Wall_rhoCp5	31	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_thick1	32	0.05
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_k1	33	0.5
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_rhoCp1	34	1500000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_thick2	35	0.05
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_k2	36	0.5

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Table 4.348 – continued from previous page

From	To	Action	File	Variable	Column	Value
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_rhoCp2	37	1500000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_thick3	38	0.05
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_k3	39	0.5
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_rhoCp3	40	1500000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_thick4	41	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_k4	42	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_rhoCp4	43	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_thick5	44	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_k5	45	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_rhoCp5	46	-999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	nroom	47	10
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_albedo	48	0.5
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_emissivity	49	1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_CHwall	50	0.001
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_CHroof	51	0.001
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt	Internal_CHbld	52	0.001
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Timezone	7	0
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	z	10	999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	TrafficRate	34	99999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	BuildEnergyUse	35	99999
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	ActivityProfWD	54	5663
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	ActivityProfWE	55	5664
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	AreaWall	87	7000
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Fr_ESTMClass_Paved1	88	0
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Fr_ESTMClass_Paved2	89	1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Fr_ESTMClass_Paved3	90	0
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Code_ESTMClass_Paved1	91	806
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Code_ESTMClass_Paved2	92	807
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Code_ESTM_Paved3	93	808
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs1	94	1
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs2	95	0
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs3	96	0
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs4	97	0
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs5	98	0
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs1	99	801
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs2	100	802
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs3	101	803
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs4	102	804
2016a	2017a	Add	SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs5	103	805
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	AnthropHeatChoice	-999	AnthropHeatMethod
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	CBLuse	-999	CBLUse
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	NetRadiationChoice	-999	NetRadiationMethod
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	RoughLen_heat	-999	RoughLenHeatMethod
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	smd_choice	-999	SMDMethod
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	WU_choice	-999	WaterUseMethod
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	z0_method	-999	RoughLenMomMethod
2016a	2017a	Delete	RunControl.nml	gsChoice	-999	-999
2016a	2017a	Delete	RunControl.nml	SkipHeaderSiteInfo	-999	-999
2016a	2017a	Delete	RunControl.nml	SkipHeaderMet	-999	-999

Continued on next page

Table 4.348 – continued from previous page

From	To	Action	File	Variable	Column	Value
2016a	2017a	Delete	RunControl.nml	SnowFractionChoice	-999	-999
2016a	2017a	Delete	RunControl.nml	TIMEZONE	-999	-999
2016a	2017a	Delete	RunControl.nml	z	-999	-999
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	SOLWEIGuse	-999	SOLWEIGUse
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	QSChoice	-999	StorageHeatMethod
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	AnthropCO2Method	-999	1
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	MultipleMetFiles	-999	0
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	MultipleInitFiles	-999	0
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	MultipleESTMFiles	-999	0
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	ResolutionFilesIn	-999	3600
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	ResolutionFilesInESTM	-999	3600
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	ResolutionFilesOut	-999	3600
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	DissagMethod	-999	1
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	RainDissagMethod	-999	100
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	SuppressWarnings	-999	1
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	ncMode	-999	0
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	nRow	-999	0
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	nCol	-999	0
2016a	2017a	Add	RunControl.nml	Diagnose	-999	0
2016a	2017a	Rename	RunControl.nml	WriteSurfsFile	-999	WriteOutOption

5.1 Runtime diagnostic information

5.1.1 Error messages: problems.txt

If there are problems running the program serious error messages will be written to problems.txt.

- Serious problems will usually cause the program to stop after writing the error message. If this is the case, the last line of problems.txt will contain a non-zero number (the error code).
- If the program runs successfully, problems.txt file ends with:

```
Run completed.  
0
```

SUEWS has a large number of error messages included to try to capture common errors to help the user determine what the problem is. If you encounter an error that does not provide an error message please capture the details so we can hopefully provide better error messages in future.

See [Troubleshooting](#) section for help solving problems. If the file paths are not correct the program will return an error when run (see [Preparing to run the model](#)).

5.1.2 Warning messages: warnings.txt

- If the program encounters a more minor issue it will not stop but a warning may be written to warnings.txt. It is advisable to check the warnings to ensure there is not a more serious problem.
- The warnings.txt file can be large (over several GBs) given warning messages are written out during a large scale simulation, you can use `tail/head` to view the ending/starting part without opening the whole file on Unix-like systems (Linux/mac OS), which may slow down your system.
- To prevent warnings.txt from being written, set `SuppressWarnings` to 1 in `RunControl.nml`.
- Warning messages are usually written with a grid number, timestamp and error count. If the problem occurs in the initial stages (i.e. before grid numbers and timestamps are assigned, these are printed as 00000).

5.1.3 Summary of model parameters: SS_FileChoices.txt

For each run, the model parameters specified in the input files are written out to the file SS_FileChoices.txt.

5.2 Model output files

5.2.1 SSss_YYYY_SUEWS_TT.txt

SUEWS produces the main output file (SSss_YYYY_SUEWS_tt.txt) with time resolution (TT min) set by *ResolutionFilesOut* in *RunControl.nml*.

Before these main data files are written out, SUEWS provides a summary of the column names, units and variables included in the file Ss_YYYY_TT_OutputFormat.txt (one file per run).

The variables included in the main output file are determined according to *WriteOutOption* set in *RunControl.nml*.

Column	Name	WriteOutOption	Description
1	Year	0,1,2	Year [YYYY]
2	DOY	0,1,2	Day of year [DOY]
3	Hour	0,1,2	Hour [H]
4	Min	0,1,2	Minute [M]
5	Dectime	0,1,2	Decimal time [-]
6	Kdown	0,1,2	Incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]
7	Kup	0,1,2	Outgoing shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]
8	Ldown	0,1,2	Incoming longwave radiation [W m^{-2}]
9	Lup	0,1,2	Outgoing longwave radiation [W m^{-2}]
10	Tsurf	0,1,2	Bulk surface temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
11	QN	0,1,2	Net all-wave radiation [W m^{-2}]
12	QF	0,1,2	Anthropogenic heat flux [W m^{-2}]
13	QS	0,1,2	Storage heat flux [W m^{-2}]
14	QH	0,1,2	Sensible heat flux (calculated using SUEWS) [W m^{-2}]
15	QE	0,1,2	Latent heat flux (calculated using SUEWS) [W m^{-2}]
16	QHlumps	0,1	Sensible heat flux (calculated using LUMPS) [W m^{-2}]
17	QElumps	0,1	Latent heat flux (calculated using LUMPS) [W m^{-2}]
18	QHresis	0,1	Sensible heat flux (calculated using resistance method) [W m^{-2}]
19	Rain	0,1,2	Rain [mm]
20	Irr	0,1,2	Irrigation [mm]
21	Evap	0,1,2	Evaporation [mm]
22	RO	0,1,2	Runoff [mm]
23	TotCh	0,1,2	Change in surface and soil moisture stores [mm]
24	SurfCh	0,1,2	Change in surface moisture store [mm]
25	State	0,1,2	Surface wetness state [mm]
26	NWtrState	0,1,2	Surface wetness state (for non-water surfaces) [mm]
27	Drainage	0,1,2	Drainage [mm]
28	SMD	0,1,2	Soil moisture deficit [mm]
29	FlowCh	0,1	Additional flow into water body [mm]
30	AddWater	0,1	Additional water flow received from other grids [mm]
31	ROSoil	0,1	Runoff to soil (sub-surface) [mm]
32	ROPipe	0,1	Runoff to pipes [mm]
33	ROImp	0,1	Above ground runoff over impervious surfaces [mm]

Continued on next page

Table 5.1 – continued from previous page

Column	Name	WriteOutOption	Description
34	ROVeg	0,1	Above ground runoff over vegetated surfaces [mm]
35	ROWater	0,1	Runoff for water body [mm]
36	WUInt	0,1	Internal water use [mm]
37	WUEveTr	0,1	Water use for irrigation of evergreen trees [mm]
38	WUDecTr	0,1	Water use for irrigation of deciduous trees [mm]
39	WUGrass	0,1	Water use for irrigation of grass [mm]
40	SMDPaved	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for paved surface [mm]
41	SMDBldgs	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for building surface [mm]
42	SMDEveTr	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for evergreen surface [mm]
43	SMDDecTr	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for deciduous surface [mm]
44	SMDGrass	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for grass surface [mm]
45	SMDBSoil	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for bare soil surface [mm]
46	StPaved	0,1	Surface wetness state for paved surface [mm]
47	StBldgs	0,1	Surface wetness state for building surface [mm]
48	StEveTr	0,1	Surface wetness state for evergreen tree surface [mm]
49	StDecTr	0,1	Surface wetness state for deciduous tree surface [mm]
50	StGrass	0,1	Surface wetness state for grass surface [mm]
51	StBSoil	0,1	Surface wetness state for bare soil surface [mm]
52	StWater	0,1	Surface wetness state for water surface [mm]
53	Zenith	0,1,2	Solar zenith angle [°]
54	Azimuth	0,1,2	Solar azimuth angle [°]
55	AlbBulk	0,1,2	Bulk albedo [-]
56	Fcld	0,1,2	Cloud fraction [-]
57	LAI	0,1,2	Leaf area index [$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$]
58	z0m	0,1	Roughness length for momentum [m]
59	zdm	0,1	Zero-plane displacement height [m]
60	ustar	0,1,2	Friction velocity [m s^{-1}]
61	Lob	0,1,2	Obukhov length [m]
62	RA	0,1	Aerodynamic resistance [s m^{-1}]
63	RS	0,1	Surface resistance [s m^{-1}]
64	Fc	0,1,2	CO ₂ flux [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] Not available in this version.
65	FcPhoto	0,1	CO ₂ flux from photosynthesis [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] Not available in this version.
66	FcRespi	0,1	CO ₂ flux from respiration [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] Not available in this version.
67	FcMetab	0,1	CO ₂ flux from metabolism [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] Not available in this version.
68	FcTraff	0,1	CO ₂ flux from traffic [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] Not available in this version.
69	FcBuild	0,1	CO ₂ flux from buildings [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] Not available in this version.
70	QNSnowFr	1	Net all-wave radiation for snow-free area [W m^{-2}]
71	QNSnow	1	Net all-wave radiation for snow area [W m^{-2}]
72	AlbSnow	1	Snow albedo [-]
73	QM	1	Snow-related heat exchange [W m^{-2}]
74	QMFreeze	1	Internal energy change [W m^{-2}]
75	QMRain	1	Heat released by rain on snow [W m^{-2}]
76	SWE	1	Snow water equivalent [mm]
77	MeltWater	1	Meltwater [mm]
78	MeltWStore	1	Meltwater store [mm]
79	SnowCh	1	Change in snow pack [mm]
80	SnowRPaved	1	Snow removed from paved surface [mm]
81	SnowRBldgs	1	Snow removed from building surface [mm]
82	Ts	0,1,2	Skin temperature [°C]

Continued on next page

Table 5.1 – continued from previous page

Column	Name	WriteOutOption	Description
83	T2	0,1,2	Air temperature at 2 m agl [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
84	Q2	0,1,2	Air specific humidity at 2 m agl [g kg^{-1}]
85	U10	0,1,2	Wind speed at 10 m agl [m s^{-1}]

5.2.2 SSss_YYYY_nn_TT.nc

SUEWS can also produce the main output file in netCDF format by setting `ncMode = 1` (set in `RunControl.nml`).

As the date and time information is incorporated in the netCDF output as separate dimension, the first five variables in the normal text output file (in `.txt`) are not included in the netCDF output but other variables are all kept.

N.B., considering the file size limit by the classic netCDF format, the output frequency is determined automatically by the internal SUEWS program setting to avoid the oversize problem in the netCDF files.

5.2.3 SSss_DailyState.txt

Contains information about the state of the surface and soil and vegetation parameters at a time resolution of one day. One file is written for each grid so it may contain multiple years.

Column	Name	Description
1	Year	Year [YYYY]
2	DOY	Day of year [DOY]
3	Hour	Hour of the last timestep of a day [HH]
4	Min	Minute of the last timestep of a day [MM]
5	HDD1_h	Heating degree days [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
6	HDD2_c	Cooling degree days [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
7	HDD3_Tmean	Average daily air temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
8	HDD4_T5d	5-day running-mean air temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
9	P_day	Daily total precipitation [mm]
10	DaysSR	Days since rain [days]
11	GDD1_g	Growing degree days for leaf growth [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
12	GDD2_s	Growing degree days for senescence [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
13	GDD3_Tmin	Daily minimum temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
14	GDD4_Tmax	Daily maximum temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
15	GDD5_DLHrs	Day length [h]
16	LAI_EveTr	Leaf area index of evergreen trees [$\text{m}^{-2} \text{m}^{-2}$]
17	LAI_DecTr	Leaf area index of deciduous trees [$\text{m}^{-2} \text{m}^{-2}$]
18	LAI_Grass	Leaf area index of grass [$\text{m}^{-2} \text{m}^{-2}$]
19	DecidCap	Moisture storage capacity of deciduous trees [mm]
20	Porosity	Porosity of deciduous trees [-]
21	AlbEveTr	Albedo of evergreen trees [-]
22	AlbDecTr	Albedo of deciduous trees [-]
23	AlbGrass	Albedo of grass [-]
24	WU_EveTr1	Total water use for evergreen trees [mm]
25	WU_EveTr2	Automatic water use for evergreen trees [mm]
26	WU_EveTr3	Manual water use for evergreen trees [mm]
27	WU_DecTr1	Total water use for deciduous trees [mm]
28	WU_DecTr2	Automatic water use for deciduous trees [mm]
29	WU_DecTr3	Manual water use for deciduous trees [mm]

Continued on next page

Table 5.2 – continued from previous page

Column	Name	Description
30	WU_Grass1	Total water use for grass [mm]
31	WU_Grass2	Automatic water use for grass [mm]
32	WU_Grass3	Manual water use for grass [mm]
33	deltaLAI	Change in leaf area index (normalised 0-1) [-]
34	LAIlumps	Leaf area index used in LUMPS (normalised 0-1) [-]
35	AlbSnow	Snow albedo [-]
36	DensSnow_Paved	Snow density - paved surface [kg m^{-3}]
37	DensSnow_Bldgs	Snow density - building surface [kg m^{-3}]
38	DensSnow_EveTr	Snow density - evergreen surface [kg m^{-3}]
39	DensSnow_DecTr	Snow density - deciduous surface [kg m^{-3}]
40	DensSnow_Grass	Snow density - grass surface [kg m^{-3}]
41	DensSnow_BSoil	Snow density - bare soil surface [kg m^{-3}]
42	DensSnow_Water	Snow density - water surface [kg m^{-3}]
43	a1	OHM coefficient a1 - [-]
44	a2	OHM coefficient a2 [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$]
45	a3	OHM coefficient a3 - [W m^{-2}]

5.2.4 InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY.nml

At the end of the model run (or the end of each year in the model run) a new InitialConditions file is written out (to the input folder) for each grid, see *Initial Conditions file*

5.2.5 SSss_YYYY_snow_TT.txt

SUEWS produces a separate output file for snow (when `snowUse = 1` in *RunControl.nml*) with details for each surface type.

File format of SSss_YYYY_snow_60.txt

Column	Name	Description
1	iy	Year [YYYY]
2	id	Day of year [DOY]
3	it	Hour [H]
4	imin	Minute [M]
5	dectime	Decimal time [-]
6	SWE_Paved	Snow water equivalent – paved surface [mm]
7	SWE_Bldgs	Snow water equivalent – building surface [mm]
8	SWE_EveTr	Snow water equivalent – evergreen surface [mm]
9	SWE_DecTr	Snow water equivalent – deciduous surface [mm]
10	SWE_Grass	Snow water equivalent – grass surface [mm]
11	SWE_BSoil	Snow water equivalent – bare soil surface [mm]
12	SWE_Water	Snow water equivalent – water surface [mm]
13	Mw_Paved	Meltwater – paved surface [mm h^{-1}]
14	Mw_Bldgs	Meltwater – building surface [mm h^{-1}]
15	Mw_EveTr	Meltwater – evergreen surface [mm h^{-1}]
16	Mw_DecTr	Meltwater – deciduous surface [mm h^{-1}]
17	Mw_Grass	Meltwater – grass surface [mm h^{-1}]
18	Mw_BSoil	Meltwater – bare soil surface [mm h^{-1}]

Continued on next page

Table 5.3 – continued from previous page

Column	Name	Description
19	Mw_Water	Meltwater – water surface [mm h ⁻¹]
20	Qm_Paved	Snowmelt-related heat – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
21	Qm_Bldgs	Snowmelt-related heat – building surface [W m ⁻²]
22	Qm_EveTr	Snowmelt-related heat – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]
23	Qm_DecTr	Snowmelt-related heat – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
24	Qm_Grass	Snowmelt-related heat – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
25	Qm_BSoil	Snowmelt-related heat – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
26	Qm_Water	Snowmelt-related heat – water surface [W m ⁻²]
27	Qa_Paved	Advective heat – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
28	Qa_Bldgs	Advective heat – building surface [W m ⁻²]
29	Qa_EveTr	Advective heat – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]
30	Qa_DecTr	Advective heat – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
31	Qa_Grass	Advective heat – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
32	Qa_BSoil	Advective heat – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
33	Qa_Water	Advective heat – water surface [W m ⁻²]
34	QmFr_Paved	Heat related to freezing of surface store – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
35	QmFr_Bldgs	Heat related to freezing of surface store – building surface [W m ⁻²]
36	QmFr_EveTr	Heat related to freezing of surface store – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]
37	QmFr_DecTr	Heat related to freezing of surface store – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
38	QmFr_Grass	Heat related to freezing of surface store – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
39	QmFr_BSoil	Heat related to freezing of surface store – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
40	QmFr_Water	Heat related to freezing of surface store – water [W m ⁻²]
41	fr_Paved	Fraction of snow – paved surface [-]
42	fr_Bldgs	Fraction of snow – building surface [-]
43	fr_EveTr	Fraction of snow – evergreen surface [-]
44	fr_DecTr	Fraction of snow – deciduous surface [-]
45	fr_Grass	Fraction of snow – grass surface [-]
46	Fr_BSoil	Fraction of snow – bare soil surface [-]
47	RainSn_Paved	Rain on snow – paved surface [mm]
48	RainSn_Bldgs	Rain on snow – building surface [mm]
49	RainSn_EveTr	Rain on snow – evergreen surface [mm]
50	RainSn_DecTr	Rain on snow – deciduous surface [mm]
51	RainSn_Grass	Rain on snow – grass surface [mm]
52	RainSn_BSoil	Rain on snow – bare soil surface [mm]
53	RainSn_Water	Rain on snow – water surface [mm]
54	qn_PavedSnow	Net all-wave radiation – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
55	qn_BldgsSnow	Net all-wave radiation – building surface [W m ⁻²]
56	qn_EveTrSnow	Net all-wave radiation – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]
57	qn_DecTrSnow	Net all-wave radiation – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
58	qn_GrassSnow	Net all-wave radiation – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
59	qn_BSoilSnow	Net all-wave radiation – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
60	qn_WaterSnow	Net all-wave radiation – water surface [W m ⁻²]
61	kup_PavedSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
62	kup_BldgsSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – building surface [W m ⁻²]
63	kup_EveTrSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]
64	kup_DecTrSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
65	kup_GrassSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
66	kup_BSoilSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
67	kup_WaterSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – water surface [W m ⁻²]

Continued on next page

Table 5.3 – continued from previous page

Column	Name	Description
68	frMelt_Paved	Amount of freezing melt water – paved surface [mm]
69	frMelt_Bldgs	Amount of freezing melt water – building surface [mm]
70	frMelt_EveTr	Amount of freezing melt water – evergreen surface [mm]
71	frMelt_DecTr	Amount of freezing melt water – deciduous surface [mm]
72	frMelt_Grass	Amount of freezing melt water – grass surface [mm]
73	frMelt_BSoil	Amount of freezing melt water – bare soil surface [mm]
74	frMelt_Water	Amount of freezing melt water – water surface [mm]
75	MwStore_Paved	Melt water store – paved surface [mm]
76	MwStore_Bldgs	Melt water store – building surface [mm]
77	MwStore_EveTr	Melt water store – evergreen surface [mm]
78	MwStore_DecTr	Melt water store – deciduous surface [mm]
79	MwStore_Grass	Melt water store – grass surface [mm]
80	MwStore_BSoil	Melt water store – bare soil surface [mm]
81	MwStore_Water	Melt water store – water surface [mm]
82	DensSnow_Paved	Snow density – paved surface [kg m^{-3}]
83	DensSnow_Bldgs	Snow density – building surface [kg m^{-3}]
84	DensSnow_EveTr	Snow density – evergreen surface [kg m^{-3}]
85	DensSnow_DecTr	Snow density – deciduous surface [kg m^{-3}]
86	DensSnow_Grass	Snow density – grass surface [kg m^{-3}]
87	DensSnow_BSoil	Snow density – bare soil surface [kg m^{-3}]
88	DensSnow_Water	Snow density – water surface [kg m^{-3}]
89	Sd_Paved	Snow depth – paved surface [mm]
90	Sd_Bldgs	Snow depth – building surface [mm]
91	Sd_EveTr	Snow depth – evergreen surface [mm]
92	Sd_DecTr	Snow depth – deciduous surface [mm]
93	Sd_Grass	Snow depth – grass surface [mm]
94	Sd_BSoil	Snow depth – bare soil surface [mm]
95	Sd_Water	Snow depth – water surface [mm]
96	Tsnow_Paved	Snow surface temperature – paved surface [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
97	Tsnow_Bldgs	Snow surface temperature – building surface [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
98	Tsnow_EveTr	Snow surface temperature – evergreen surface [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
99	Tsnow_DecTr	Snow surface temperature – deciduous surface [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
100	Tsnow_Grass	Snow surface temperature – grass surface [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
101	Tsnow_BSoil	Snow surface temperature – bare soil surface [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
102	Tsnow_Water	Snow surface temperature – water surface [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

5.2.6 SSss_YYYY_BL.txt

Meteorological variables modelled by CBL portion of the model are output in to this file created for each day with time step (see section CBL Input).

Column	Name	Description	Units
1	iy	Year [YYYY]	
2	id	Day of year [DoY]	
3	it	Hour [H]	
4	imin	Minute [M]	
5	dectime	Decimal time [-]	
6	zi	Convective boundary layer height	m
7	Theta	Potential temperature in the inertial sublayer	K
8	Q	Specific humidity in the inertial sublayer	g kg ⁻¹
9	theta+	Potential temperature just above the CBL	K
10	q+	Specific humidity just above the CBL	g kg ⁻¹
11	Temp_C	Air temperature	°C
12	RH	Relative humidity	%
13	QH_use	Sensible heat flux used for calculation	W m ⁻²
14	QE_use	Latent heat flux used for calculation	W m ⁻²
15	Press_hPa	Pressure used for calculation	hPa
16	avul	Wind speed used for calculation	m s ⁻¹
17	ustar	Friction velocity used for calculation	m s ⁻¹
18	avdens	Air density used for calculation	kg m ⁻³
19	lv_J_kg	Latent heat of vaporization used for calculation	J kg ⁻¹
20	avcp	Specific heat capacity used for calculation	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
21	gamt	Vertical gradient of potential temperature	K m ⁻¹
22	gamq	Vertical gradient of specific humidity	kg kg ⁻¹ m ⁻¹

5.2.7 SOLWEIGpoiOut.txt

Calculated variables from POI, point of interest (row, col) stated in SOLWEIGinput.nml.

SOLWEIG model output file format: SOLWEIGpoiOUT.txt

Column	Name	Description	Units
1	id	Day of year	
2	dectime	Decimal time	
3	azimuth	Azimuth angle of the Sun	°
4	altitude	Altitude angle of the Sun	°
5	GlobalRad	Input Kdn	W m ⁻²
6	DiffuseRad	Diffuse shortwave radiation	W m ⁻²
7	DirectRad	Direct shortwave radiation	W m ⁻²
8	Kdown2d	Incoming shortwave radiation at POI	W m ⁻²
9	Kup2d	Outgoing shortwave radiation at POI	W m ⁻²
10	Ksouth	Shortwave radiation from south at POI	W m ⁻²
11	Kwest	Shortwave radiation from west at POI	W m ⁻²
12	Knorth	Shortwave radiation from north at POI	W m ⁻²
13	Keast	Shortwave radiation from east at POI	W m ⁻²
14	Ldown2d	Incoming longwave radiation at POI	W m ⁻²
15	Lup2d	Outgoing longwave radiation at POI	W m ⁻²
16	Lsouth	Longwave radiation from south at POI	W m ⁻²
17	Lwest	Longwave radiation from west at POI	W m ⁻²
18	Lnorth	Longwave radiation from north at POI	W m ⁻²
19	Least	Longwave radiation from east at POI	W m ⁻²
20	Tmrt	Mean Radiant Temperature	°C
21	I0	theoretical value of maximum incoming solar radiation	W m ⁻²
22	CI	clearness index for Ldown (Lindberg et al. 2008)	
23	gvf	Ground view factor (Lindberg and Grimmond 2011)	
24	shadow	Shadow value (0= shadow, 1 = sun)	
25	svf	Sky View Factor from ground and buildings	
26	svfbuveg	Sky View Factor from ground, buildings and vegetation	
27	Ta	Air temperature	°C
28	Tg	Surface temperature	°C

5.2.8 SSss_YYYY_ESTM_TT.txt

If the ESTM model option is run, the following output file is created. **Note: First time steps of storage output could give NaN values during the initial converging phase.**

ESTM output file format

Column	Name	Description	Units
1	iy	Year	
2	id	Day of year	
3	it	Hour	
4	imin	Minute	
5	dectime	Decimal time	
6	QSnet	Net storage heat flux (QSwall+QSground+QS)	W m ⁻²
7	QSair	Storage heat flux into air	W m ⁻²
8	QSwall	Storage heat flux into wall	W m ⁻²
9	QSroof	Storage heat flux into roof	W m ⁻²
10	QSground	Storage heat flux into ground	W m ⁻²
11	QSibld	Storage heat flux into internal elements in building	W m ⁻²
12	Twall1	Temperature in the first layer of wall (outer-most)	K

Continued on next page

Table 5.4 – continued from previous page

Column	Name	Description	Units
13	Twall2	Temperature in the first layer of wall	K
14	Twall3	Temperature in the first layer of wall	K
15	Twall4	Temperature in the first layer of wall	K
16	Twall5	Temperature in the first layer of wall (inner-most)	K
17	Troof1	Temperature in the first layer of roof (outer-most)	K
18	Troof2	Temperature in the first layer of roof	K
19	Troof3	Temperature in the first layer of roof	K
20	Troof4	Temperature in the first layer of roof	K
21	Troof5	Temperature in the first layer of ground (inner-most)	K
22	Tground1	Temperature in the first layer of ground (outer-most)	K
23	Tground2	Temperature in the first layer of ground	K
24	Tground3	Temperature in the first layer of ground	K
25	Tground4	Temperature in the first layer of ground	K
26	Tground5	Temperature in the first layer of ground (inner-most)	K
27	Tibld1	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K
28	Tibld2	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K
29	Tibld3	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K
30	Tibld4	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K
31	Tibld5	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K
32	Tabld	Air temperature in buildings	K

6.1 How to report an issue of this manual?

Please submit your issue via our [GitHub page](#).

6.2 How to join your email-list?

Please join our email-list [here](#).

6.3 How to create a directory?

Please search the web using this phrase if you do not know how to create a folder or directory

6.4 How to unzip a file

Please search the web using this phrase if you do not know how to unzip a file

6.5 A text editor

A program to edit plain text files. If you search on the web using the phrase 'text editor' you will find numerous programs. These include for example, NotePad, EditPad, Text Pad etc

6.6 Command prompt

From Start select run –type cmd – this will open a window. Change directory to the location of where you stored your files. The following website may be helpful if you do not know what a command prompt is: <http://dosprompt.info/>

6.7 Day of year [DOY]

January 1st is day 1, February 1st is day 32. If you search on the web using the phrase ‘day of year calendar’ you will find tables that allow rapid conversions. Remember that after February 28th DOY will be different between leap years and non-leap years.

6.8 ESTM output

First time steps of storage output could give NaN values during the initial converging phase.

6.9 First things to Check if the program seems to have problems

- Check the problems.txt file.
- Check file options – in RunControl.nml.
- Look in the output directory for the SS_FileChoices.txt. This allows you to check all options that were used in the run. You may want to compare it with the original version supplied with the model.
- Note there can not be missing time steps in the data. If you need help with this you may want to checkout [UMEP](#)

6.9.1 A pop-up saying “file path not found”

This means the program cannot find the file paths defined in RunControl.nml file. Possible solutions:

- Check that you have created the folder that you specified in RunControl.nml.
- Check does the output directory exist?
- Check that you have a single or double quotes around the FileInputPath, FileOutputPath and FileCode

====“%sat_vap_press.f temp=0.0000 pressure dectime”==== Temperature is zero in the calculation of water vapour pressure parameterization.

- You don’t need to worry if the temperature should be (is) 0°C.
- If it should not be 0°C this suggests that there is a problem with the data.

6.9.2 %T changed to fit limits

- [TL =0.1]/ [TL =39.9] You may want to change the coefficients for surface resistance. If you have data from these temperatures, we would happily determine them.

6.9.3 %Iteration loop stopped for too stable conditions.

- [zL]/[USTAR] This warning indicates that the atmospheric stability gets above 2. In these conditions [MO theory](#) is not necessarily valid. The iteration loop to calculate the [Obukhov length](#) and [friction velocity](#) is stopped so that stability does not get too high values. This is something you do not need to worry as it does not mean wrong input data.

6.9.4 “Reference to undefined variable, array element or function result”

- Parameter(s) missing from input files.

See also the error messages provided in `problems.txt` and `warnings.txt`

6.9.5 Email list

- SUEWS email list

<https://www.lists.reading.ac.uk/mailman/listinfo/met-suews>

- UMEP email list

<https://www.lists.reading.ac.uk/mailman/listinfo/met-umep>

Recent publications

Note: If you have papers to add to this list please let us and others know via the [email list](#).

- [Järvi et al. \(2017\)](#)
topic Application and evaluation in cold climates. Implications of warming
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- [Kokkonen et al. \(2017\)](#)
topic Downscaling climate (rainfall) data to 1 h
citation Kokkonen T, CSB Grimmond, O Rätty, HC Ward, A Christen, T Oke, S Kotthaus, L Järvi 2017: Sensitivity of Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS)
- [Ward and Grimmond \(2017\)](#)
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- [Ward et al. \(2016\)](#)
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citation Ward HC, Kotthaus S, Järvi L and Grimmond CSB (2016) Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS): Development and evaluation at two UK sites. *Urban Climate*

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topic Evaluation of radiation in Shanghai

citation Ao XY, CSB Grimmond, DW Liu, ZH Han, P Hu, YD Wang, XR Zhen, JG Tan 2016: Radiation fluxes in a business district of Shanghai JAMC, 55, 2451-2468

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topic Boundary layer modelling

citation Onomura S, Grimmond CSB, Lindberg F, Holmer B & Thorsson S (2015) Meteorological forcing data for urban outdoor thermal comfort models from a coupled convective boundary layer and surface energy balance scheme Urban Climate, 11, 1-23

- Järvi et al. (2014)

topic Snow melt model development

citation Järvi L, Grimmond CSB, Taka M, Nordbo A, Setälä H & Strachan IB 2014: Development of the Surface Urban Energy and Water balance Scheme (SUEWS) for cold climate cities Geosci. Model Dev. 7, 1691-1711

Other papers

8.1 SuPy

SuPy is a Python-enhanced urban climate model with [SUEWS](#) as its computation core.

The scientific rigour in SuPy results is thus gurranteed by SUEWS (see *SUEWS publications* and *Parameterisations and sub-models within SUEWS*).

Meanwhile, the data analysis ability of SuPy is greatly enhanced by the Python-based SciPy Stack, notably [numpy](#) and [pandas](#).

- **How to get SuPy?**

SuPy is available on all major platforms (macOS, Windows, Linux) for Python 3.5+ via [PyPI](#):

```
python3 -m pip install supy --upgrade
```

- **How to use SuPy?**

- Please follow [Quickstart of SuPy](#) and [other tutorials](#).
- Please see [SuPy API](#) for usage details of SuPy functions.

8.2 SUEWS and UMEP

SUEWS can be run as a standalone model but also can be used within [UMEP](#). There are numerous tools included within UMEP to help a user get started. The [SUEWS \(Simple\)](#) within UMEP is a fast way to start using SUEWS.

The version of SUEWS within UMEP is the complete model. Thus all options that are listed in this manual are available to the user. In the UMEP [SUEWS \(Simple\)](#) runs all options are set to values to allow intial exploration of the model behaviour.

- **Pre-Processor**

- **Meteorological Data**

- * **Prepare Existing Data** Transforms meteorological data into UMEP format
- * **Download data (WATCH)** Prepare meteorological dataset from *WATCH*
- **Spatial Data**
 - * **Spatial Data Downloader** Plugin for retrieving geodata from online services suitable for various UMEP related tools - **LCZ Converter** Conversion from Local Climate Zones (LCZs) in the WUDAPT database into SUEWS input data
- **Urban land cover**
 - * **Land Cover Reclassifier** Reclassifies a grid into UMEP format land cover grid. Land surface models
 - * **Land Cover Fraction (Point)** Land cover fractions estimates from a land cover grid based on a specific point in space
 - * **Land Cover Fraction (Grid)** Land cover fractions estimates from a land cover grid based on a polygon grid
- **Urban Morphology**
 - * **Morphometric Calculator (Point)** Morphometric parameters from a DSM based on a specific point in space
 - * **Morphometric Calculator (Grid)** Morphometric parameters estimated from a DSM based on a polygon grid
 - * **Source Area Model (Point)** Source area calculated from a DSM based on a specific point in space.
- **SUEWS input data**
 - * **SUEWS Prepare** Preprocessing and preparing input data for the SUEWS model
- **Processor**
 - **Anthropogenic Heat (Q_F)**
 - * **LQF** Spatial variations anthropogenic heat release for urban areas
 - * **GQF** Anthropogenic Heat (Q_F).
 - **Urban Energy Balance**
 - * **SUEWS (Simple)** Urban Energy and Water Balance.
 - * **SUEWS (Advanced)** Urban Energy and Water Balance.
- **Post-Processor**
 - **Urban Energy Balance**
 - * **SUEWS analyser** Plugin for plotting and statistical analysis of model results from SUEWS simple and SUEWS advanced
 - **Benchmark**
 - * **Benchmark System** For statistical analysis of model results, such as SUEWS

8.3 Differences between SUEWS, LUMPS and FRAISE

The largest difference between LUMPS and SUEWS is that the latter simulates the urban water balance in detail while LUMPS takes a simpler approach for the sensible and latent heat fluxes and the water balance (“water bucket”). The

calculation of evaporation/latent heat in SUEWS is more biophysically based. Due to its simplicity, LUMPS requires less parameters in order to run. SUEWS gives turbulent heat fluxes calculated with both models as an output.

Similarities and differences between LUMPS and SUEWS.

	LUMPS	SUEWS
Net all-wave radiation (Q^*)	Input or NARP	Input or NARP
Storage heat flux (ΔQS)	Input or from OHM	Input or from OHM
Anthropogenic heat flux (QF)	Input or calculated	Input or calculated
Latent heat (QE)	DeBruin and Holtslag (1982)	Penman-Monteith equation2
Sensible heat flux (QH)	DeBruin and Holtslag (1982)	Residual from available energy minus QE
Water balance	No water balance included	Running water balance of canopy and water balance of soil
Soil moisture	Not considered	Modelled
Surface wetness	Simple water bucket model	Running water balance
Irrigation	Only fraction of surface area that is irrigated	Input or calculated with a simple model
Surface cover	Buildings, paved, vegetation	Buildings, paved, coniferous and deciduous trees/shrubs, irrigated and unirrigated grass

8.4 FRAISE Flux Ratio – Active Index Surface Exchange

FRAISE provides an estimate of mean midday (± 3 h around solar noon) energy partitioning from information on the surface characteristics and estimates of the mean midday incoming radiative energy and anthropogenic heat release. Please refer to Loridan and Grimmond (2012) [[LG2012](#)] for further details.

Topic	FRAISE	LUMPS	SUEWS
Complexity	Simplest: FRAISE		More complex: SUEWS
Software provided:	R code	Windows exe (written in Fortran)	Windows exe (written in Fortran) - other versions available
Applicable period:	Midday (within 3 h of solar noon)	hourly	5 min-hourly-annual
Unique features:	Calculates active surface and fluxes	Radiation and energy balances	Radiation, energy and water balance (includes LUMPS)

To help users getting started with SUEWS, the community is working on setting up tutorials and instructions for different parts of SUEWS and related tool. The tutorials are available are found in the table below.

Topic	Application
<i>Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Introduction</i>	Energy, water and radiation fluxes for one location
<i>Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Advanced</i>	Energy, water and radiation fluxes for one location
<i>Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Spatial</i>	Energy, water and radiation fluxes for a spatial grid
<i>Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS and WUDAPT</i>	Making use of WUDAPT local climate zones in SUEWS

9.1 Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Introduction

9.1.1 Introduction

In this tutorial you will use a land-surface model, [SUEWS](#) to simulate energy exchanges in a city (London is the test case).

SUEWS (Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme) allows the energy and water balance exchanges for urban areas to be modelled (Järvi et al. 2011, 2014, Ward et al. 2016a). The model is applicable at the neighbourhood scale (e.g. 10^2 to 10^4 m). The fluxes calculated are applicable to height of about 2-3 times the mean height of the roughness elements; i.e. above the [roughness sublayer \(RSL\)](#). The use of SUEWS within Urban Multi-scale Environmental Predictor (UMEP) provides an introduction to the model and the processes simulated, the parameters used and the impact on the resulting fluxes.

Tools such as this, once appropriately assessed for an area, can be used for a broad range of applications. For example, for climate services (e.g. <http://www.wmo.int/gfcs/>). Running a model can allow analyses, assessments, and long-term projections and scenarios. Most applications require not only meteorological data but also information about the activities that occur in the area of interest (e.g. agriculture, population, road and infrastructure, and socio-economic variables).

Model output may be needed in many formats depending on a users' needs. Thus, the format must be useful, while ensuring the science included within the model is appropriate. The figure below provides an overview of [UMEP](#), a

city based climate service tool (CBCST). Within UMEP there are a number of models which can predict and diagnose a range of meteorological processes. In this activity we are concerned with SUEWS, initially the central components of the model. See [manual](#) or published papers for more detailed information of the model.

Fig. 9.1: Overview of the climate service tool UMEP (from Lindberg et al. 2018)

SUEWS can be run in a number of different ways:

1. Within UMEP via the Simple selection. This is useful for becoming familiar with the model (Part 1)
2. Within UMEP via the Advanced selection. This can be used to exploit the full capabilities of the model (Part 2)
3. SUEWS standalone (see [manual](#))
4. Within other larger scale models (e.g. WRF).

9.1.2 SUEWS Simple Objectives

This tutorial introduces SUEWS and demonstrates how to run the model within UMEP (Urban Multi-scale Environmental Predictor). [Help with Abbreviations](#).

Steps

1. An introduction to the model and how it is designed.
2. Different kinds of input data that are needed to run the model
3. How to run the model
4. How to examine the model output

9.1.3 Initial Steps

UMEP is a python plugin used in conjunction with [QGIS](#). To install the software and the UMEP plugin see the [getting started](#) section in the UMEP manual.

As UMEP is under development, some documentation may be missing and/or there may be instability. Please report any issues or suggestions to our [repository](#).

9.1.4 SUEWS Model Inputs

Details of the model inputs and outputs are provided in the [SUEWS manual](#). As this tutorial is concerned with a **simple application** only the most critical parameters are shown. Other versions allow many other parameters to be modified to more appropriate values if applicable. The table below provides an overview of the parameters that can be modified in the Simple application of SUEWS.

Type	Definition	Reference/Comments
	Building/ Tree Morphology	
Mean height of Building/Trees (m)		Grimmond and Oke (1999)
Frontal area index	Area of the front face of a roughness element exposed to the wind relative to the plan area.	Grimmond and Oke (1999), Fig 2
Plan area index	Area of the roughness elements relative to the total plan area.	Grimmond and Oke (1999), Fig 2
	Land cover fraction	Should sum to 1
Paved	Roads, sidewalks, parking lots, impervious surfaces that are not buildings	
Buildings	Buildings	Same as the plan area index of buildings in the morphology section.
Evergreen trees	Trees/shrubs that retain their leaves/needles all year round	Tree plan area index will be the sum of evergreen and deciduous area. Note: this is the same as the plan area index of vegetation in the morphology section.
Deciduous trees	Trees/shrubs that lose their leaves	Same as above
Grass	Grass	
Bare soil	Bare soil – non vegetated but water can infiltrate	
Water	River, ponds, swimming pools, fountains	
	Initial conditions	What is the state of the conditions when the model run begins?
Days since rain (days)	This will influence irrigation behaviour in the model. If there has been rain recently then it will be longer before irrigation occurs.	If this is a period or location when no irrigation is permitted/occurring then this is not critical as the model will calculate from this point going forward.
Daily mean temperature (°C)	Influences irrigation and anthropogenic heat flux	
Soil moisture status (%)	This will influence both evaporation and runoff processes	If close to 100% then there is plenty of water for evaporation but also a higher probability of flooding if intense precipitation occurs.
	Other	
Year	What days are weekdays/weekends	
Latitude (°)	Solar related calculations	
Longitude (°)	Solar related calculations	
UTC (h)	Time zone	Influences solar related calculations

9.1.5 How to Run SuewsSimple from the UMEP-plugin

1. Open SuewsSimple from UMEP -> Processor -> Urban Energy Balance -> Urban Energy Balance, SUEWS (Simple). The GUI that opens looks quite extensive but it is actually not that complicated to start a basic model

run (figure below). Some additional information about the plugin is found in the left window. As you can read, a **test dataset** from observations for London, UK (Kotthaus and Grimmond 2014, Ward et al. 2016a) is included in within the plugin.

Fig. 9.2: The interface for SUEWS, simple version (click on image to make it larger).

1. To make use of this dataset click on **Add settings from test dataset** (see near bottom of the box). The land cover fractions and all other settings originate from Kotthaus and Grimmond (2014). They used a source area model to obtain the different input parameters (their Fig. 7 in Kotthaus and Grimmond, 2014).
2. Before you start the model, change the location of the output data to any location of your choice. Also, make notes on the settings such as *Year* etc.
3. Do a model run and explore the results by clicking **Run**. A command window appears, when SUEWS performs the calculations using the settings from the interface. Once the calculations are done, some of the results are shown in two summary plots.

9.1.6 Model results

The graphs in the upper figure are the monthly mean energy (left) and water balance (right). The lower graphs show the radiation fluxes, energy fluxes, and water related outputs throughout the year. This plot includes a lot of data and it might be difficult to examine it in detail.

To zoom into the plot: use the tools in the top left corner, to zoom to a period of interest. For example, the Zoom in to about the last ten days in March (figure below). This was a period with clear relatively weather.

9.1.7 Saving a Figure

Use the disk tool in the upper left corner.

Fig. 9.3: Model output from SUEWS (simple) using the default settings and data (click on image to make it larger).

Fig. 9.4: Model output from SUEWS (simple) using the default settings and data (click on image to make it larger).

Fig. 9.5: Zoom in on end of March from the daily plot (click on image to make it larger).

1. .jpg
2. .pdf
3. .tif (Recommended)
4. .png

9.1.8 Output data Files

In the output folder (you selected earlier) you will find (at least) three files:

1. **Kc98_2012_60.txt** – provides the 60 min model results for site “KC1” for the year 2012
2. **Kc_FilesChoices.txt** – this indicates all options used in the model run see the SUEWS Manual for interpretation of content (this is for when you are doing large number of runs so you know exactly what options were used in each run)
3. **Kc98_DailyState.txt** – this provides the daily mean state (see SUEWS manual for detailed explanation). This allows you to see, for example, the daily state of the LAI (leaf area index).
4. **Kc_OutputFormat.txt** – provides detailed information about the output files such as extended descriptions for each column including units.

If you open these files in a text editor. To understand the header variables read the [SUEWS manual](#).

9.1.9 Sensitivity to land surface fractions

The previous results are for a densely build-up area in London, UK. In order to test the sensitivity of SUEWS to some surface properties you can think about

Land cover fractions	
<input type="checkbox"/> Land cover fractions generated from land cover grid	
Fetch file from Land Cover Fraction calculation	
Open tool to generate fractions	
Paved/impervious:	0.10
Buildings:	0.10
Evergreen trees:	0.00
Deciduous trees:	0.20
Grass:	0.60
Bare Soil:	0.00
Water:	0.14

changing some of the surface properties in the SUEWS Simple. For example, change the land cover fraction by:

1. Change the land cover fractions as seen in the figure. Feel free to select other values as long as all the fractions *add up to 1.0*.
2. Save the output to a different folder by selecting *output folder*.
3. Click *Run*.

9.1.10 References

- Grimmond CSB and Oke 1999: Aerodynamic properties of urban areas derived, from analysis of surface form. *Journal of Applied Climatology* 38:9, 1262-1292
- Grimmond et al. 2015: Climate Science for Service Partnership: China, Shanghai Meteorological Service, Shanghai, China, August 2015.
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- Ward HC, L Järvi, S Onomura, F Lindberg, A Gabey, CSB Grimmond 2016 SUEWS Manual V2016a, <http://urban-climate.net/umep/SUEWS> Department of Meteorology, University of Reading, Reading, UK
- Ward HC, Kotthaus S, Järvi L and Grimmond CSB 2016b: Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS): Development and evaluation at two UK sites. *Urban Climate* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2016.05.001>
- Ward HC, S Kotthaus, CSB Grimmond, A Björkegren, M Wilkinson, WTJ Morrison, JG Evans, JIL Morison, M Iamarino 2015b: Effects of urban density on carbon dioxide exchanges: observations of dense urban, suburban and woodland areas of southern England. *Env Pollution* 198, 186-200

Authors this document: Lindberg and Grimmond (2016)

9.1.11 Definitions and Notation

To help you find further information about the acronyms they are classified by **T**: Type of term: **C**: computer term, **S**: science term, **G**: GIS term.

	Definition	T	Ref./Comment
DEM	Digital elevation model	G	
DSM	Digital surface model	G	
FAI (λ_F)	Frontal area index	S	Grimmond and Oke (1999)
GUI	Graphical User Interface	C	
LAI	Leaf Area Index	S	
PAI (λ_P)	Plan area index	S	
png	Portable Network Graphics	C	format for saving plots/figures
QGIS		G	www.qgis.org
SUEWS	Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme	S	
Tif	Tagged Image File Format	C	format for saving plots/figures
UI	user interface	C	
UMEP	Urban Multi-scale Environmental predictor	C	
z_0	Roughness length for momentum	S	Grimmond and Oke (1999)
z_d	Zero plane displacement length for momentum	S	Grimmond and Oke (1999)

9.1.12 Further explanation

Morphometric Methods to determine Roughness parameters:

For more and overview and details see [Grimmond and Oke \(1999\)](#) and [Kent et al. \(2017a\)](#). This uses the height and spacing of roughness elements (e.g. buildings, trees) to model the roughness parameters. For more details see [Kent et al. \(2017a\)](#), [Kent et al. \(2017b\)](#) and [[Kent et al. \(2017c\)](#)]. UMEP has tools for doing this: *Pre-processor -> Urban Morphology*

Source Area Model

For more details see [Kotthaus and Grimmond \(2014b\)](#) and [Kent et al. \(2017a\)](#). The [Kormann and Meixner \(2001\)](#) model is used to determine the probable area that a turbulent flux measurement was impacted by. This is a function of wind direction, stability, turbulence characteristics (friction velocity, variance of the lateral wind velocity) and roughness parameters.

9.2 Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Advanced

9.2.1 Introduction

The tutorial *Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Introduction* should be completed first. This tutorial is designed to work with QGIS 2.18.

Objectives

1. To explore the link between QGIS and SUEWS to include new site-specific information
2. To examine how it affects the energy fluxes

Overview of steps

1. Initially become familiar with SUEWS advanced which is a plugin that makes it possible for you to set all parameters that can be manipulated in SUEWS as well as execute the model on multiple grids (*Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Spatial*).
2. Derive new surface information
3. Run the model

9.2.2 How to Run from the UMEP-plugin

How to run SUEWS Advanced:

1. Open the plugin which is located at *UMEP -> Processor -> Urban Energy Balance -> Urban Energy Balance, SUEWS/BLUEWS (Advanced)*. This has most of the general settings (e.g. activate the snow module etc.) which are related to [RunControl.nml](#).
2. Use the Input folder:
 - `C:/Users/your_user_name/.qgis2/python/plugins/UMEP/suewsmodel/Input`
3. Create or enter an **Output directory** of your choice.
4. From the **Input folder** - confirm the data are in there.
5. Tick in **Obtain temporal...** and set **Temporal resolution of output (minutes)** to 60.
6. Click Run
7. Make sure that output files are created.
8. You can now close the **SUEWS/BLUEWS (Advanced)**-plugin again.

Sensitivity Test

The default dataset included in **Suews Simple** has parameters calculated from a [source area model](#) to obtain the appropriate values for the input parameters. Roughness parameters such as roughness length (z_0) and zero plane displacement length (z_d) are calculated using [morphometric models](#). Now you will explore the differences in fluxes using the default settings or using input parameters from the geodata included in the test datasets available for this tutorial. Download the zip-file (see below) and extract the files to a suitable location where you both have reading and writing capabilities.

Data for the tutorial can be downloaded [here](#)

Geodata	Name
Ground and building DSM	DSM_LondonCity_1m.tif (m asl)
Vegetation DSM	CDSM_LondonCity_1m.tif (m agl)
DEM (digital elevation model)	DEM_LondonCity_1m.tif (masl)
Land cover	LC_londoncity_UMEP_32631

They are all projected in UTM 31N (EPSG:32631). The three surface models originate from a LiDAR dataset. The land cover data is a mixture of Ordnance Survey and the LiDAR data.

1. Open the geodatasets. Go to *Layer > Add layer > Add Raster Layer*. Locate the files you downloaded before (see above).

The screenshot shows the SUEWS Advanced version interface. The window title is "SUEWS" with a question mark and close button in the top right corner. The interface is organized into several sections:

- Configuration Parameters:** A list of nine parameters, each with a dropdown menu:
 - Anthropogenic heat flux: [2] Järvi et al. 2011 (RECOMMENDED)
 - Net radiation: [3] Modelled, Ldown from Ta and RH
 - Storage heat flux: [1] Objective hysteresis model (OHM)
 - OHM option: [0] From Q* (RECOMMENDED)
 - Roughness length of heat: [2] Kawai et al. (2009) (RECOMMENDED)
 - Soil moisture deficit: [0] Modelled (RECOMMENDED)
 - Atmospheric stability: [2] Dyer (1974) etc. (RECOMMENDED)
 - External water use: [0] Modelled
 - Aerodynamic properties: [1] Observed
- Optional Modules:** Two checkboxes:
 - Use snow module
 - Obtain temporal resolution of forcing data and file code from input folder
- Temporal Resolution and File Code:** Three input fields:
 - Temporal resolution of forcing data (minutes): []
 - File code (e.g. SS): []
 - Temporal resolution of output (minutes): []
- Spin-up Option:** A checkbox:
 - Apply spin-up using existing meteorological data (only possible if one full year of data is used)
- Folder Selection:** Two input fields for folder paths, with "Input folder" and "Output folder" buttons to the right.
- Control Buttons:** "Run" and "Close" buttons are located at the bottom right, and a "Help" button is at the bottom left.

Fig. 9.7: Interface for SUEWS Advanced version.

2. A QGIS style file (.qml) is available for the land cover grid. It can be found in *C:\Users\your_user_name\qgis2pythonplugins\UMEP\ LandCoverReclassifier*. Load it in the *Layer > Properties > Style > Style* (lower left) **Load file**.
3. Click Apply before you close so that the names of the classes also load. You can also get the properties of a layer by right-click on a layer in the Layers-window.
4. If you have another land cover dataset you can use the *LandCoverReclassifier* in the UMEP pre-processor to populate with the correct values suitable for the UMEP plugin environment.
5. Now take a moment and investigate the different geodatasets. What is the spatial (pixel) resolution? How is ground represented in the CDSM?

9.2.3 Generating data from the geodatasets

1. Make certain that you have the geodatafiles open. The file at the top (left hand side (LHS)) of the list is the one that is shown in the centre (figure below). You can swap their order using the LHS box.
2. Open SUEWS Simple.
3. Begin by adding the test dataset again.
4. Update the building morphology parameters (top left panel in SUEWS Simple).
5. To generate new values, click on Open tool.
6. This is another plugin within UMEP that can be used to generate morphometric parameters

Fig. 9.8: QGIS where SUEWS Simple and Image Morphometric Parameters (Point) is opened.

7. First, clear the map canvas from your two other plugin windows, e.g. as figure above.
8. If you use the default test data in SUEWS Simple - you can overwrite it as you go.
9. Locate the eddy covariance tower position on the Strand building, King's College London. To find the position, consult Figure 1 (KSS) in [Kotthaus and Grimmond \(2014\)](#).
10. Use Select point on canvas and put a point at that location (left).
11. Generate a study area. Use 500 m search distance, 5 degree interval and click Generate study area.
12. A circular area will be considered. Enter the DSM and DEM files (i.e. the files you currently have in the viewer)
13. Click Run.

Fig. 9.9: Figure 3. Settings for Image Morphometric Parameters for buildings.

14. In the folder you specified two additional files will be present (i) isotropic - averages of the morphometric parameters (ii) anisotropic - values for each wind sector you specified (5 degrees).
15. Close this plugin
16. Click on Fetch file from... in the building morphology panel
17. Choose the isotropic file (just generated).
18. Do the same for vegetation (upper left panel, right). See figure below.
19. Instead of locating the point again you can use the existing point.
20. You still need to generate a separate study area for the vegetation calculation.
21. Examine the CDSM (vegetation file) in your map canvas. As you can see, this data has no ground heights (ground = 0). Therefore, this time Tick in the box Raster DSM (only buildings) exist.
22. Enter the CDSM as your Raster DSM (only buildings).
23. A warning appears that your vegetation fractions between the morphology dataset and land cover dataset are large. You can ignore this for now since the land cover dataset also will change.
24. Repeat the same procedure for land cover as you did for buildings and vegetation but instead using the Land Cover Fraction (Point) plugin.
25. Enter the meteorological file, Year etc. This should be the same as for the first run you made.
26. Now you are ready to run the model. Click Run.

If you get an error window (figure below). This error is generate by SUEWS as the sum of the land cover fractions is not 1. If you calculate carefully, one part of a thousand is missing (this is probably a rounding error during data extraction). To fix this issue: add 0.001 to e.g. bare soil. Now run again.

You are now familiar with the Suews Simple plugin. Your next task is to choose another location within the geodataset domain, generate data and run the model. If you choose an area where the fraction of buildings and paved surfaces are low, consider lowering the population density to get more realistic model outputs. Compare the results for the different area.

9.2.4 References

- Grimmond CSB and Oke 1999: Aerodynamic properties of urban areas derived, from analysis of surface form. *Journal of Applied Climatology* 38:9, 1262-1292
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Fig. 9.10: Settings for Image Morphometric Parameters for vegetation

Fig. 9.11: Possible error window from running SUEWS with new settings.

Fig. 9.12: The settings for running with geodata derived parameters (old version of GUI).

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Authors of this document: Lindberg and Grimmond (2016)

9.2.5 Definitions and Notation

To help you find further information about the acronyms they are classified by **T**: Type of term: **C**: computer term, **S**: science term, **G**: GIS term.

	Definition	T	Reference/Comment
DEM	Digital elevation model	G	
DSM	Digital surface model	G	
FAI (λ_F)	Frontal area index	S	Grimmond and Oke (1999), their figure 2
GUI	Graphical User Interface	C	
LAI	Leaf Area Index	S	
PAI (λ_P)	Plan area index	S	
png	Portable Network Graphics	C	format for saving plots/figures
QGIS		G	www.qgis.org
SUEWS	Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme	S	
Tif	Tagged Image File Format	C	format for saving plots/figures
UI	user interface	C	
UMEP	Urban Multi-scale Environmental predictor	C	
z_0	Roughness length for momentum	S	Grimmond and Oke (1999)
z_d	Zero plane displacement length for momentum	S	Grimmond and Oke (1999)

9.2.6 Further explanation

Morphometric Methods to determine Roughness parameters:

For more and overview and details see [Grimmond and Oke \(1999\)](#). This uses the height and spacing of roughness elements (e.g. buildings, trees) to model the roughness parameters. UMEP has tools for doing this: *Pre-processor -> Urban Morphology*

Source Area Model

For more details see [Kotthaus and Grimmond \(2014b\)](#). The Kormann and Meixner (2001) model is used to determine the probable area that a turbulent flux measurement was impacted by. This is a function of wind direction, stability, turbulence characteristics (friction velocity, variance of the lateral wind velocity) and roughness parameters.

9.3 Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Spatial

9.3.1 Introduction

In this tutorial you will generate input data for the SUEWS model and simulate spatial (and temporal) variations of energy exchanges within a small area on Manhattan (New York City) with regards to a heat wave event.

Tools such as this, once appropriately assessed for an area, can be used for a broad range of applications. For example, for climate services (e.g. <http://www.wmo.int/gfcs/>, Baklanov et al. 2018). Running a model can allow analyses, assessments, and long-term projections and scenarios. Most applications require not only meteorological data but also information about the activities that occur in the area of interest (e.g. agriculture, population, road and infrastructure, and socio-economic variables).

This tutorial makes use of local high resolution detailed spatial data. If this kind of data are unavailable, other datasets such as local climate zones (LCZ) from the WUDAPT database could be used. The tutorial *Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS and WUDAPT* is available if you want to know more about using LCZs in SUEWS. However, it is strongly recommended to go through this tutorial before moving on to the WUDAPT/SUEWS tutorial.

Model output may be needed in many formats depending on a users' needs. Thus, the format must be useful, while ensuring the science included within the model is appropriate. Fig. 9.13 shows the overall structure of UMEP, a city based climate service tool (CBCST) used in this tutorial. Within UMEP there are a number of models which can predict and diagnose a range of meteorological processes.

Fig. 9.13: Overview of the climate service tool UMEP (from Lindberg et al. 2018)

Note: This tutorial is currently designed to work with QGIS 2.18. It is recommended that you have a look at the tutorials *Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Introduction* and *Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Advanced* before you go

through this tutorial.

9.3.2 Objectives

To perform and analyse energy exchanges within a small area on Manhattan, NYC.

Steps to be performed

1. Pre-process the data and create input datasets for the SUEWS model
2. Run the model
3. Analyse the results
4. Perform simple mitigation measures to see how it affects the model results (optional)

9.3.3 Initial Steps

UMEP is a Python plugin used in conjunction with [QGIS](#). To install the software and the UMEP plugin see the [getting started](#) section in the UMEP manual.

As UMEP is under development, some documentation may be missing and/or there may be instability. Please report any issues or suggestions to our [repository](#).

Loading and analyzing the spatial data

All the geodata used in this tutorial are from open access sources, primarily from the New York City. Information about the data are found in the table below.

Note: You can download the all the data from [here](#). Unzip and place in a folder that you have read and write access to.

Table 9.1: Spatial data used in this tutorial

Geodata	Year	Source	Description
Digital surface model (DSM)	2013 (Lidar), 2016 (building polygons)	United States Geological Survey (USGS). New York CMGP Sandy 0.7m NPS Lidar and NYC Open Data Portal. link	A raster grid including both buildings and ground given in meter above sea level.
Digital elevation model (DEM)	2013	United States Geological Survey (USGS). New York CMGP Sandy 0.7m NPS Lidar. link	A raster grid including only ground heights given in meter above sea level.
Digital canopy model (CDSM)	2013 (August)	United States Geological Survey (USGS). New York CMGP Sandy 0.7m NPS Lidar. link	A vegetation raster grid where vegetation heights is given in meter above ground level. Vegetation lower than 2.5 meter pixels with no vegetation should be zero.
Land cover (UMEP formatted)	2010	New York City Landcover 2010 (3ft version). University of Vermont Spatial Analysis Laboratory and New York City Urban Field Station. link	A raster grid including: 1. Paved surfaces, 2. Building surfaces, 3. Evergreen trees and shrubs, 4. Deciduous trees and shrubs, 5. Grass surfaces, 6. Bare soil, 7. Open water
Population density (residential)	2010	2010 NYC Population by Census Tracts, Department of City Planning (DCP). link	People per census tract converted to pp/ha. Converted from vector to raster.
Land use	2018	NYC Department of City Planning, Technical Review Division. link	Used to redistribute population during daytime (see text). Converted from vector to raster

- Start by loading all the raster datasets into an empty QGIS project.

The order in the *Layers Panel* determines what layer is visible. You can choose to show a layer (or not) with the tick box. You can modify layers by right-clicking on a layer in the *Layers Panel* and choose *Properties*. Note for example that that CDSM (vegetation) is given as height above ground (meter) and that all non-vegetated pixels are set to zero. This makes it hard to get an overview of all 3D objects (buildings and trees). QGIS default styling for a raster is using the 98 percentile of the values. Therefore, not all the range of the data is shown in the layer window to the left.

- Right-click on your **CDSM** layer and go to *Properties > Style* and choose **Singleband pseudocolor** with a min value of 0 and max of 35. Choose a colour scheme of your liking.
- Go to *Transparency* and add an additional no data value of 0. Click ok.
- Now put your **CDSM** layer at the top and your **DSM** layer second in your *Layers Panel*. Now you can see both buildings and vegetation 3D object in your map canvas.

The land cover grid comes with a specific QGIS style file.

- Right-click on the land cover layer (**landcover_2010_nyc**) and choose *Properties*. Down to the left you see a *Style*-button. Choose *Load Style* and open **landcoverstyle.qml** and click OK.
- Make only your land cover class layer visible to examine the spatial variability of the different land cover classes.

The land cover grid has already been classified into the seven different classes used in most UMEP applications (see [Land Cover Reclassifier](#)). If you have a land cover dataset that is not UMEP formatted you can use the *Land Cover*

Fig. 9.14: DSM and CDSM visible at the same time (click for larger image)

Reclassifier found at *UMEP > Pre-processor > Urban Land Cover > Land Cover Reclassifier* in the menubar to reclassify your data.

Furthermore, a polygon grid (500 m x 500 m) to define the study area and individual grids is included (*Grid_500m.shp*). Such a grid can be produced directly in QGIS (e.g. *Vector > Research Tools > Vector Grid*) or an external grid can be used.

- Load the vector layer **Grid_500m.shp** into your QGIS project.
- In the *Style* tab in layer *Properties*, choose a *Simple fill* with a *No Brush* fill style to be able to see the spatial data within each grid.
- Also, add the label IDs for the grid to the map canvas in *Properties > Labels* to make it easier to identify the different grid squares later on in this tutorial.

As you can see the grid does not cover the whole extent of the raster grids. This is to reduce computation time during the tutorial. One grid cell takes ~20 s to model with SUEWS with meteorological forcing data for a full year.

Meteorological forcing data

Meteorological forcing data are mandatory for most of the models within UMEP. The UMEP specific format is given in [Table 9.2](#). Some of the variables are optional and if not available or needed should be set to -999. The columns can not be empty. The needed data for this tutorial are discussed below.

Table 9.2: Variables included in UMEP meteorological input file.

No.	Header	Description	Accepted range	Comments
1	iy	Year [YYYY]	Not applicable	
2	id	Day of year [DOY]	1 to 365 (366 if leap year)	
3	it	Hour [H]	0 to 23	
4	imin	Minute [M]	0 to 59	
5	qn	Net all-wave radiation [W m^{-2}]	-200 to 800	
6	qh	Sensible heat flux [W m^{-2}]	-200 to 750	
7	qe	Latent heat flux [W m^{-2}]	-100 to 650	
8	qs	Storage heat flux [W m^{-2}]	-200 to 650	
9	qf	Anthropogenic heat flux [W m^{-2}]	0 to 1500	
10	U	Wind speed [m s^{-1}]	0.001 to 60	
11	RH	Relative Humidity [%]	5 to 100	
12	Tair	Air temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	-30 to 55	
13	pres	Surface barometric pressure [kPa]	90 to 107	
14	rain	Rainfall [mm]	0 to 30	(per 5 min) this should be scaled based on time step used
15	kdown	Incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]	0 to 1200	
16	snow	Snow [mm]	0 to 300	(per 5 min) this should be scaled based on time step used
17	ldown	Incoming longwave radiation [W m^{-2}]	100 to 600	
18	fcd	Cloud fraction [tenths]	0 to 1	
19	wuh	External water use [m^3]	0 to 10	(per 5 min) scale based on time step being used
20	xsm	(Observed) soil moisture	0.01 to 0.5	$[\text{m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ or } \text{kg kg}^{-1}]$
21	lai	(Observed) leaf area index [$\text{m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$]	0 to 15	
22	kdif	Diffuse shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]	0 to 600	
23	kdir	Direct shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]	0 to 1200	Should be perpendicular to the Sun beam. One way to check this is to compare direct and global radiation and see if kdir is higher than global radiation during clear weather. Then kdir is measured perpendicular to the solar beam.
24	wdir	Wind direction [$^{\circ}$]	0 to 360	

The meteorological dataset used in this tutorial (**MeteorologicalData_NYC_2010.txt**) is from NOAA (most of the meteorological variables) and NREL (solar radiation data). It consists of *tab-separated* hourly air temperature, relative humidity, incoming shortwave radiation, pressure, precipitation and wind speed for 2010. There are other possibilities within UMEP to acquire meteorological forcing data. The pre-processor plugin **WATCH** can be used to download the variables needed from the global **WATCH** forcing datasets (Weedon et al. 2011, 2014).

- Open the meteorological dataset (**MeteorologicalData_NYC_2010.txt**) in a text editor of your choice. As you can see it does not include all the variables shown in Table 9.2. However, these variables are the mandatory ones that are required to run SUEWS. In order to format (and make a quality check) the data provided into UMEP standard, you will use the **MetPreProcessor**.
- Open **MetDataPreprocessor** (*UMEP> Pre-Processor -> Meteorological Data > Prepare existing data*).

- Load `MeteorologicalData_NYC_2010.txt` and make the settings as shown below. Name your new dataset `NYC_metdata_UMEPformatted.txt`.

Fig. 9.15: The settings for formatting met data into UMEP format (click for a larger image)

- Close the Metdata preprocessor and open your newly formatted dataset in a text editor of your choice. Now you see that the forcing data is structured into the UMEP pre-defined format.
- Close your text file and move on to the next section of this tutorial.

9.3.4 Preparing input data for the SUEWS model

A key capability of UMEP is to facilitate preparation of input data for the various models. SUEWS requires input information to model the urban energy balance. The plugin *SUEWS Prepare* is for this purpose. This tutorial makes use of high resolution data but *WUDAPT* datasets in-conjunction with the *LCZ Converter* can be used (*UMEP > Pre-Processor > Spatial data > LCZ Converter*).

- Open SUEWS Prepare (*UMEP > Pre-Processor > SUEWS prepare*).

Fig. 9.16: The dialog for the SUEWS Prepare plugin (click for a larger image).

Here you can see the various settings that can be modified. You will focus on the *Main Settings* tab where the mandatory settings are chosen. The other tabs include the settings for e.g. different land cover classes, human activities etc.

There are 10 frames included in the *Main Settings* tab where 8 need to be filled in for this tutorial:

1. **Polygon grid**
2. **Building morphology**
3. **Tree morphology**
4. **Land cover fractions**
5. **Meteorological data**
6. **Population density**
7. **Daylight savings and UTC**
8. **Initial conditions**

The two optional frames (*Land use fractions* and *Wall area*) should be used if the ESTM model is used to estimate the storage energy term (ΔQ_S). In this tutorial we use the *OHM* modelling scheme so these two tabs can be ignored for now.

- Close *SUEWS Prepare*

Building morphology

First you will calculate roughness parameters based on the building geometry within your grids.

- Open *UMEP > Pre-Processor > Urban Morphology > Morphometric Calculator (Grid)*.
- Use the settings as in the figure below and press *Run*.
- When calculation is done, close the plugin.

Note: For mac users, use this workaround: manually create a directory, go into the folder above and type the folder name. It will give a warning “—folder name—” already exists. Do you want to replace it? Click *replace*.

Fig. 9.17: The settings for calculating building morphology.

This operation should have produced 17 different text files; 16 (*anisotropic*) that include morphometric parameters from each 5 degree section for each grid and one file (*isotropic*) that includes averaged values for each of the 16 grids. You can open **build_IMPGrid_isotropic.txt** and compare the different values for a park grid (3054) and an urban grid (3242). Header abbreviations are explained [here](#).

Tree morphology

Now you will calculate roughness parameters based on the vegetation (trees and bushes) within your grids. As you noticed there is only one surface dataset for vegetation present (**CDSM_nyc**) and if you examine your land cover grid (**landcover_2010_nyc**) you can see that there is only one class of high vegetation (*Deciduous trees*) present with

our model domain. Therefore, you will not separate between evergreen and deciduous vegetation in this tutorial. As shown in Table 9.1, the tree surface model represents height above ground.

- Again, Open *UMEP > Pre-Processor > Urban Morphology > Morphometric Calculator (Grid)*.
- Use the settings as in the figure below and press *Run*.
- When calculation is done, close the plugin.

Fig. 9.18: The settings for calculating vegetation morphology.

Land cover fractions

Moving on to land cover fraction calculations for each grid.

- Open *UMEP > Pre-Processor > Urban Land Cover > Land Cover Fraction (Grid)*.
- Use the settings as in the figure below and press *Run*.
- When calculation is done, close the plugin.

Fig. 9.19: The settings for calculating land cover fractions

Population density

Population density will be used to estimate the anthropogenic heat release (Q_F) in SUEWS. There is a possibility to use both night-time and daytime population densities to make the model more dynamic. You have two different raster grids for night-time (**pop_nighttime_perha**) and daytime (**pop_daytime_perha**), respectively. This time you will make use of QGIS built-in function to acquire the population density for each grid.

- Go to *Plugins > Manage and Install Plugins* and make sure that the *Zonal statistics plugin* is ticked. This is a build-in plugin which comes with the QGIS installation.
- Close the *Plugin manager* and open *Raster > Zonal Statistics > Zonal Statistics*.
- Choose your **pop_daytime_perha** layer as **Raster layer** and your **Grid_500m** and polygon layer. Use a *Output column prefix* of **PPday** and chose only to calculate *Mean*. Click OK.
- Run the tool again but this time use the night-time dataset.

SUEWS Prepare

Now you are ready to organise all the input data into the SUEWS input format.

- Open *SUEWS Prepare*
- In the *Polygon grid* frame, choose your polygon grid (**Grid_500m**) and choose **id** as your *ID field*
- In the *Building morphology* frame, fetch the file called **build_IMPGrid_isotropic.txt**.
- In the *Land cover fractions* frame, fetch the file called **lc_LCFG_isotropic.txt**.
- In the *Tree morphology* frame, fetch the file called **veg_IMPGrid_isotropic.txt**.
- In the *Meteorological data* frame, fetch your UMEP formatted met forcing data text file.
- In the *Population density* frame, choose the appropriate attributes created in the previous section for daytime and night-time population density.
- In the *Daylight savings and UTC* frame, set start and end of the daylight saving to 87 and 304, respectively and choose -5 (i.e. the time zone).
- In the *Initial conditions* frame, choose **Winter (0%)** in the *Leaf Cycle*, *100% Soil moisture state* and **nyc** as a *File code*.
- In the *Anthropogenic* tab, change the code to 771. This will make use of settings adjusted for NYC according to Sailor et al. 2015.
- Choose an empty directory as your *Output folder* in the main tab.
- Press *Generate*
- When processing is finished, close *SUEWS Prepare*.

9.3.5 Running the SUEWS model in UMEP

To perform modelling energy fluxes for multiple grids, *Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Advanced* can be used.

- Open *UMEP > Processor > Urban Energy Balance > SUEWS/BLUEWS, Advanced*. Here you can change some of the run control settings in SUEWS. SUEWS can also be executed outside of UMEP and QGIS (see [SUEWS Manual](#)). This is recommended when modelling long time series (multiple years) of large model domains (many grid points).
- Change the OHM option to [1]. This allows the anthropogenic energy to be partitioned also into the storage energy term.

- Leave the rest of the combobox settings at the top as default and tick both the *Use snow module* and the *Obtain temporal resolution...* box.
- Set the *Temporal resolution of output (minutes)* to 60.
- Locate the directory where you saved your output from *SUEWSPrepare* earlier and choose an output folder of your choice.
- Also, Tick the box *Apply spin-up using...* This will force the model to run twice using the conditions from the first run as initial conditions for the second run.
- Click *Run*. This computation will take a while so be patient.

9.3.6 Analysing model results

UMEP has a tool for basic analysis of any modelling performed with the SUEWS model. The *SUEWSAnalyzer* tool is available from the post-processing section in UMEP.

- Open *UMEP > Post-Processor > Urban Energy Balance > SUEWS Analyzer*. There are two main sections in this tool. The *Plot data*-section can be used to make temporal analysis as well as making simple comparisons between two grids or variables. This *Spatial data*-section can be used to make aggregated maps of the output variables from the SUEWS model. This requires that you have loaded the same polygon grid into your QGIS project that was used when you prepared the input data for SUEWS using *SUEWS Prepare* earlier in this tutorial.

Fig. 9.20: The dialog for the SUEWS Analyzer tool.

To access the output data from a model run, the **RunControl.nml** file for that particular run must be located. If your run has been made through UMEP, this file can be found in your output folder. Otherwise, this file can be located in the same folder from where the model was executed.

- In the top panel of *SUEWS Analyzer*, load the **RunControl.nml** located in the output folder.

You will start by plotting basic data for grid 3242 which is one of the most dense urban area in the World.

- In the left panel, choose grid 3242 and year 2010. Tick *plot basic data* and click *Plot*. This will display some of the most essential variables such as radiation balance and budget etc. You can use the tools such as the zoom to examine a shorter time period more in detail.

Fig. 9.21: Basic plot for grid 3242. Click on image for enlargement.

Notice e.g. the high Q_F values during winter as well as the low Q_E values throughout the year.

- Close the plot and make the same kind of plot for grid 3054 which is a grid mainly within Central Park. Consider the differences between the plot generated for grid 3242. Close the plot when you are done.

In the left panel, there is also possibilities to examine two different variables in time, either from the same grid or between two different grid points. There is also possible to examine different parameters through scatterplots.

The right panel in SUEWS Analyzer can be used to perform basic spatial analysis on your model results by producing aggregated maps etc. using different variables and time spans. Sensible heat (Q_H) is one variable to visualise warm areas as it is a variable that show the amount of the available energy that will be partitioned into heat.

- Make the settings as shown in the figure below but change the location where you will save your data on your own system.

Note that the warmest areas are located in the most dense urban environments and the coolest are found where either vegetation and/or water bodies are present. During 2010 there was a 3-day heat-wave event in the region around NYC that lasted from 5 to 8 July 2010 (Day of Year: 186-189).

- Make a similar average map but this time of 2m air temperature and choose only the heat wave period. Save it as a separate geoTiff.

9.3.7 The influence of mitigation measures on the urban energy balance (optional)

There are different ways of manipulating the data using UMEP as well directly changing the input data in SUEWS to examine the influence of mitigation measures on the UEB. The most detailed way would be to directly changing the surface data by e.g. increasing the number of street trees. This can be done by e.g. using the [TreeGenerator](#)-plugin in UMEP. This method would require that you go through the workflow of this tutorial again before you do your new

Fig. 9.22: The dialog for the SUEWS Analyzer tool to produce a mean Q_H for each grid. Click on image for enlargement.

model run. Another way is to directly manipulate input data to SUEWS at grid point level. This can be done by e.g. changing the land cover fractions in **SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt**, the file that includes all grid-specific information used in SUEWS.

- Make a copy of your whole input folder created from SUEWSPRepare earlier and rename it to e.g. *Input_mitigation*.
- In that folder remove all the files beginning with *InitialConditions* **except** the one called **InitialCondition-snyc_2010.nml**.
- Open **SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt** in Excel (or similar software).
- Now increase the fraction of deciduous trees (*Fr_DecTr*) for grid 3242 and 3243 by 0.2. As the total land cover fraction has to be 1 you also need to reduce the paved fraction (*Fr_Paved*) by the same amount.
- Save and close. Remember to keep the format (tab-separated text).
- Create an empty folder called *Output_mitigation*
- Open [SuewsAdvanced](#) and make the same settings as before but change the input and output folders.
- Run the model.
- When finished, create a similar average air temperature map for the heat event and compare the two maps. You can do a difference map by using the Raster Calculator in QGIS (*Raster>Raster Calculator...*).

Tutorial finished.

9.4 Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS and WUDAPT

9.4.1 Introduction

Note: This tutorial is not ready for use. Work in progress.

In this tutorial you will generate input data for the [SUEWS](#) model and simulate spatial (and temporal) variations of energy exchanges within an area in New York City using local climate zones derived within the [WUDAPT](#) project. The World Urban Database and Access Portal Tools project is a community-based project to gather a census of cities around the world.

Note: This tutorial is currently designed to work with QGIS 2.18. It is strongly recommended that you go through the *Urban Energy Balance - SUEWS Spatial* tutorial before you go through this tutorial.

9.4.2 Objectives

To prepare input data for the SUEWS model using a WUDAPT dataset and analyse energy exchanges within an area in New York City, US.

9.4.3 Initial Steps

UMEP is a python plugin used in conjunction with [QGIS](#). To install the software and the UMEP plugin see the [getting started](#) section in the UMEP manual.

As UMEP is under development, some documentation may be missing and/or there may be instability. Please report any issues or suggestions to our [repository](#).

Loading and analyzing the spatial data

Note: You can download the all the data from [here](#). Unzip and place in a folder where you have read and write access to. The LCZ data for various cities are also available from the [WUDAPT](#) portal.

- Start by loading the raster dataset (**NYC_LCZ.tif**) into an empty QGIS project. This dataset is referenced to the WGS84 CRS (ESPG:4326).
- You can set the correct colors for your LCZ raster by opening the LCZ converter at *UMEP > Pre-Processor > Spatial data > LCZ converter*. In the upper right corner, choose the LCZ raster and press *Color Raster* and then close the *LCZ Converter*.

9.4.4 Vector grid generation

A vector polygon grid is required for specifying the extent and resolution of the modelling. You will make use of a built-in tool in QGIS to generate such a grid.

1. First zoom in to Manhattan as shown in the figure below

Fig. 9.23: Zoom in the Manhattan island.

1. As WGS84 (EPSG:4326) is in degree coordinates and maybe you want to specify your grid in meters, you need to change the CRS of your current QGIS-project. Click on the globe at the bottom right of your QGIS window and select *ESPG:26918* as your ‘on the fly’ CRS.
2. Open vector grid at *Vector > Research Tools > Vector grid*.
3. Select the extend of your canvas by clicking the ... next to *Grid extent (xmin, xmax, ymin, ymax)* and select *Use layer/canvas extent*.
4. Select *Use Canvas Extent*.
5. As you can see the units is now in meters and not in degrees. Specify the desired grid spacing to 5000 meters. This will save time later on. Of course you can set it a much smaller number if you have the time to wait when the model performs the calculations later on.
6. Make sure the output is in polygons, not lines.
7. Create as temporary layer.
8. Save your grid by right-click on the new layer in the *Layers Panel* and choose *Save as...*. Here it is very important that you save in the same CRS as you other layers (EPSG:4326). Save as a shape file.

9.4.5 Population density

Population density is required to estimate the anthropogenic heat release (Q_F) in SUEWS. There is a possibility to make use of both night-time and daytime population densities to make the model more dynamic. In this tutorial you will only use a night-time dataset. This dataset can be acquired from the *Spatial Data Downloader* in UMEP.

1. Open the spatial downloader at *UMEP > Pre-Processor > Spatial data > Spatial Data Downloader*.
2. Select *population density* and select the *GPWv4: UN-Adjusted Population Density* closest to the year you intend to model (2010). The values will be in (pp / square kilometer).
3. Make sure your canvas is zoomed out to the entire LCZ map and click *Use canvas extent*
4. Now click *Get data*.
5. Save as a geoTiff (.tif) with the name **GPWv4_2010**.
6. Now you need to calculate population density per grid in units *pp/hectare*. First open the QGIS built-in tool *Zonal statistics (Raster > Zonal Statistics)*. If the tool is absent you need to activate it by going to *Plugins > Manage and Install Plugins* and add *Zonal statistics plugin*. Open the tool and make the settings as shown below. This will calculate mean population density per grid.
7. Open the attribute table for your **Grid_5000m**-layer (right-click on layer and choose *(Open attribute Table)*).
8. Click the abacus shaped symbol this is the *Field calculator*.
9. Under *Output field name* write “pp_ha, the *Output field type* should be “Decimal number (real)”, and the *Output Precision* can be set to 2.
10. In the expression dialog box write $gpw_mean/100$, here *gpw_mean* is the name of your population density field and the 100 is to convert the data from km^2 to ha.
11. Click *OK* and you should have a new field called “pp_ha”.
12. Click the yellow pencil in the top left corner of the attribute table to stop editing and save your changes and close the attribute table.

Fig. 9.24: Settings for the Zonal statistics plugin.

9.4.6 LCZ converter

Now you will make use of the *LCZ Converter*-plugin to generate input data for the SUEWS model.

1. Open the LCZ converter at *UMEP > Pre-Processor > Spatial data > LCZ converter*.
2. Select the LCZ raster layer at ‘‘ LCZ raster’‘.
3. Select the vector grid you have just created in step 3 at *Vector grid* and select the ID field of the polygon grid at *ID field*.
4. By clicking *Adjust default parameters* you can edit the table. This table specifies the pervious, trees, grass, etc. fractions for each of the LCZ classes. For more information about each of the classes see [LCZConverter](#). If you choose to edit the table, make sure all fractions add up to 1.0.
5. If you are unsure about the exact fractions for each of the LCZ click the tab *Pervious distribution*. Select *Same for all LCZ's*

Fig. 9.25: Settings for the LCZ converter plugin.

1. Now you can select your best estimate about the distribution of the pervious surface fractions for urban and the tree distribution for rural. In addition, also specify the expected height of the trees.
2. Once you are satisfied click *Update Table*.
3. Select add results to polygon.

4. Add a file prefix if desired.
5. Finally select an output folder where you would like to receive the text files and click *Run*.

Note: For mac users use this workaround: manually create a directory, go into the folder above and type the folder name. It will give a warning “—folder name—” already exists. Do you want to replace it? Click *replace*.

This should generate 3 text files, one with the land cover fractions, one with morphometric parameters for buildings and one for trees for each grid cell of the polygon grid.

9.4.7 SUEWS

Before running SUEWS, you will need to prepare some of the data required to run it.

1. SUEWS prepare requires the grid CRS to be in metres not degrees, therefore we need to reproject the grid. Right-click the vector grid and click *save as...* Assign a different file name, use CRS *ESPG:26918* and click *OK*.
2. Open SUEWS prepare at: *UMEP > Pre-Processor > SUEWS prepare*.
3. Under *vector polygon grid* specify your reprojected vector grid and the *ID field*.
4. Select the location of the *Meteorological file* that was included in the input data, the building morphology (*_build_*), tree morphology (*_veg_*) and land cover fractions (*_LCFGrid_*) from the step above and the population density (*pp_ha*) in the dropdown list.
5. Enter the start and end of day light savings time for 2010 and the UTC offset of New York.
6. Specify the *Leaf cycle* = winter when initialising in January. Unless the user has better information initialise the *Soil moisture state* at 100 %.
7. Select an output folder where the initial data to run SUEWS should be saved and press *Generate*.
8. Open SUEWS at *UMEP > Processor > Urban Energy Balance > Urban Energy Balance (SUEWS/BLUEWS, advanced)*. Using this for the first time, the system will ask you to download the latest version of SUEWS, click *OK*.
9. Change the OHM option to [1]. This allows the anthropogenic energy to be partitioned also into the storage energy term.
10. Leave the rest of the combobox settings at the top as default and tick both the *Use snow module* and the *Obtain temporal resolution...* box.
11. Set the *Temporal resolution of output (minutes)* to 60.
12. Locate the directory where you saved your output from SUEWSPrepare earlier and choose an output folder of your choice.
13. Also, Tick the box *Apply spin-up using...* This will force the model to run twice using the conditions from the first run as initial conditions for the second run.
14. Click *Run*. This computation will take a while so be patient. If it only takes a very short time (a few seconds) the model has probably crashed. Please consult the *problems.txt* file for more information.

9.4.8 Analysing model results

When the model has successfully run, it is time to look at some of the output of the model. The SUEWSAnalyser tool is available from the post-processing section in UMEP.

1. To better visualise what would be interesting to plot, label the grid ID's of your vector grid. Do this by right-clicking the vector grid, going to *properties*, under the *Labels* tab click *Show labels for this layer*, label with **id** and select a text format of your choosing.
2. Open *UMEP > Post-Processor > Urban Energy Balance > SUEWS Analyzer*. There are two main sections in this tool. The Plot data-section can be used to make temporal analysis as well as making simple comparisons between two grids or variables. This Spatial data-section can be used to make aggregated maps of the output variables from the SUEWS model. This requires that you have loaded the same polygon grid into your QGIS project that was used when you prepared the input data for SUEWS using SUEWS Prepare earlier in this tutorial.
3. To access the output data from the a model run, the **RunControl.nml** file for that particular run must be located. If your run has been made through UMEP, this file can be found in your output folder. Otherwise, this file can be located in the same folder from where the model was executed. In the top panel of *SUEWS Analyzer*, load the **RunControl.nml** located in the output folder.

Feel free to try plotting different variables, first let's try and look at a variable for two different grid cells.

1. Load the **RunControl.nml** located in the output folder.
2. On the left hand specify a *Grid* cell that is largely urban, select *Year* to investigate. Select the desired time period and a variable, for example *Sensible heat flux*.
3. Comparing with another less urbanised gridcell turn on *include another variable* and specify the desired *Grid*, selecting the same *Variable* (Sensible heat flux).
4. Click *plot*.

Fig. 9.26: Example of the comparison of the heat flux for two grid cell in the vector grid.

Now we will look at the horizontal distribution of the storage flux. #. On the right-hand side of *SUEWS analyser* specify the **Net Storage flux** as a *variable to analyse*. #. Select the *Year to investigate* and a time period during the summer season. #. Select the *Median* and *Only daytime*. #. Select the *Vector polygon grid* you have been using and *save as a GeoTiff*. #. Specify an *output filename*, and tick *Add Geotiff to map canvas* and *Generate*.

This should generate a geotiff file with a median, night-time net storage flux in the selected timeperiod.

Tutorial finished.

Fig. 9.27: Example of the median, night-time net storage flux.

Development, Suggestions and Support

If you are interested in contributing to the code please contact Sue Grimmond. Please follow *Coding Guidelines* for coding SUEWS.

Please provide your feedbacks via *channels listed here*.

10.1 Coding Guidelines

If you are interested in contributing to the code please contact Sue Grimmond.

10.1.1 Coding

1. Core physics and calculatoin schemes of SUEWS are written in Fortran 90
2. Code is hosted in GitHub as private repository
3. Variables
 - Names should be defined at least in one place in the code – ideally when defined
 - Implicit None should be used in all subroutines
 - Variable name should include units. e.g. Temp_C, Temp_K
 - Output variable attributes should be provided in the TYPE structure defined in the ctrl_output module as follows:

```
: TYPE varAttr
: CHARACTER(len = 15) :: header ! short name in headers
: CHARACTER(len = 12) :: unit   ! unit
: CHARACTER(len = 14) :: fmt    ! output format
: CHARACTER(len = 50) :: longNm ! long name for detailed description
: CHARACTER(len = 1)  :: aggreg ! aggregation method
: CHARACTER(len = 10) :: group  ! group: datetime, default, ESTM, Snow,
: etc.
```

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(continued from previous page)

```
: INTEGER          :: level ! output priority level: 0 for highest_  
↔(default output)  
: END TYPE varAttr
```

4. Code should be written generally
5. Data set for testing should be provided
6. Demonstration that the model performance has improved when new code has been added or that any deterioration is warranted.
7. Additional requirements for modelling need to be indicated in the manual
8. All code should be commented in the program (with initials of who made the changes – name specified somewhere and institution)
9. The references used in the code and in the equations will be collected to a webpage
10. Current developments that are being actively worked on

10.1.2 Testing

1. The testing of SUEWS is done using Python 3
2. The following tests are done for each release of SUEWS:
 1. Working status of *all physics schemes*
 2. Year-grid looping logic
 3. Identity of output results with internal test dataset

Please use pre-defined `make test` option to check if your code can pass all tests or not. If not, the correctness of added code should be justified with caution.

10.1.3 Preparation of SUEWS Manual

1. The SUEWS manual is written in reStructuredText (aka rst) with a Sphinx flavour
2. The SUEWS manual is hosted by readthedocs.org
3. CSV tables used in following pages are automatically generated from the *Description* field in *Input Options* by each build, so **DON'T** manually edit them as your edits will be swiped automatically:
 - *SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt*
 - *SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt*
 - *SUEWS_Conductance.txt*
 - *SUEWS_Irrigation.txt*
 - *SUEWS_NonVeg.txt*
 - *SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt*
 - *SUEWS_Profiles.txt*
 - *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt*
 - *SUEWS_Snow.txt*
 - *SUEWS_Soil.txt*

- *SUEWS_Veg.txt*
- *SUEWS_Water.txt*
- *SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt*

10.2 Suggestions and Support

Please provide your feedbacks via these channels:

- [GitHub issues page](#) of this repository
- Mailing lists:
 - [SUEWS](#)
 - [UMEP](#): As UMEP has a number of tools to support SUEWS you may want to join it as well.

Benchmark Report

Since *v2018a*, SUEWS is benchmarked against observations for assessment of model performance. A site based benchmark report generation system is introduced in *v2018c* to produce detailed reports for testing sites; the number of sites is expanding and more cases will be added as they are benchmarked.

Each report includes the following parts:

1. **Overall performance:**

1. Performance Score: Large scores indicate better performance. The scores are calculated according to weighted averages of statistics for selected benchmark variables.
2. Detailed Statistics: Grids are coloured based relative performance between different versions: a **greener** grid indicates better performance in the chosen variable using the specific release whereas a **redder** one shows poorer performance; and those with **gray** backgrounds indicate the same performance across different releases.

2. **Cross-comparison in model variables between releases:**

1. Detailed statistics tables: statistics for each variable.
2. Pair plots: comparison in simulation results between different version-pairs.
3. Time series plots: comparison in simulated monthly climatologies of diurnal cycles of each variable between different version-pairs.

The benchmark report can be found in the online version.

12.1 Version 2018c (released on 21 February 2019)

- **Improvement**

1. SuPy (SUEWS in Python): a Python-enhanced wrapper of SUEWS, which can facilitate a more fluent workflow of SUEWS-centred urban climate research. More details refer to [SuPy documentation site](#).
2. Improved benchmark report: More testing sites are added thanks to an automated benchmark report system.

- **Changes**

None.

- **Fix**

1. Fixed a bug in LAI calculation for longterm runs.
2. Fixed a bug in net all-wave radiation differential calculation for OHM.
3. Fixed water redistribution bug in snow module.

- **Known issues**

1. BLUEWS is disabled
2. Observed soil moisture can not be used as an input
3. Wind direction is not currently downscaled so non -999 values will cause an error.

12.2 Version 2018b (released 17 December 2018)

- **Improvement**

1. Improved calculation of OHM-related radiation terms:

The temporal difference term dQ^*/dt is now calculated using the time-step-weighted dQ^* of previous time step instead of a series of Q^* values from previous time steps, which improves the usage of memory and allows time-step-varying simulations (needed by WRF-SUEWS coupling).

- **Changes**

None.

- **Fix**

1. Fixed a bug in picking up external water use from meteorological forcing file.

- **Known issues**

1. BLUEWS is disabled
2. Observed soil moisture can not be used as an input
3. Wind direction is not currently downscaled so non -999 values will cause an error.

12.3 Version 2018a (released 2 August 2018)

- **New**

1. Many under-the-hood improvements:
 - Added explicit interface intent for confusion-less coupling between SUEWS modules
 - Restructured layout of physics schemes for better modularity
 - Improved the alignment in output txt files
2. New `readthedocs.org`-based documentation system
3. Added *SUEWS input converter* for conversion of input files between versions
4. Added *Benchmark Report* for recent releases.

- **Improvement**

1. Improved the near surface diagnostics scheme (T2, Q2, U10)
2. Improved skin temperature calculation (Ts)

- **Changes**

1. *StabilityMethod*: recommended option is change from 2 to 3 as options other than 3 have been noticed with numerical issues under several scenarios, which will be fixed in the next release.
2. Model run - changes in selections moved from *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* to *SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt*: *EnergyUseProfWD*, *EnergyUseProfWE*, *ActivityProfWD*, *ActivityProfWE*.
3. *BiogenCO2Code* is added to *SUEWS_Veg.txt* for looking up biogenic characteristics in the new *SUEWS_BiogenCO2.txt* file.
4. *TrafficRate* and *BuildEnergyUse* in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* are expanded to allow weekday and weekend values: *TrafficRate_WD*, *TrafficRate_WE*, *QF0_BEU_WD*, *QF0_BEU_WE*.
5. *AnthropCO2Method* is removed from *RunControl.nml*.
6. *AnthropHeatMethod* is renamed to *EmissionsMethod*.

7. AHMin, AHSlope and TCritic are expanded to allow weekday and weekend values by adding `_WD` and `_WE` as suffix, of which AHSlope and TCritic are also expanded to allow cooling and heating settings.

- **Known issues**

1. BLUEWS is disabled
2. Observed soil moisture can not be used as an input
3. Wind direction is not currently downscaled so non -999 values will cause an error.

12.4 Version 2017b (released 2 August 2017)

PDF Manual for v2017b

1. Surface-level diagnostics: T2 (air temperature at 2 m agl), Q2 (air specific humidity at 2 m agl) and U10 (wind speed at 10 m agl) added as default output.
2. Output in netCDF format. Please note this feature is **NOT** enabled in the public release due to the dependency of netCDF library. Assistance in enabling this feature may be requested to the development team via [SUEWS mail list](#).
3. Edits to the manual.
4. New capabilities being developed, including two new options for calculating storage heat flux (AnOHM, ESTM) and modelling of carbon dioxide fluxes. These are currently under development and **should not be used** in Version 2017b.
5. Known issues
 - (a) BLUEWS parameters need to be checked
 - (b) Observed soil moisture can not be used as an input
 - (c) Wind direction is not currently downscaled so non -999 values will cause an error.

12.5 Version 2017a (Feb 2017)

1. Changes to input file formats (including RunControl.nml and InitialConditions files) to facilitate setting up and running the model. Met forcing files no longer need two rows of -9 at the end to indicate the end of the file.
2. Changes to output file formats (now option to write out only a subset of variables, rather than all variables).
3. SUEWS can now disaggregate forcing files to the model time-step and aggregate output at the model time-step to lower resolution. This removes the need for the python wrapper used with previous versions.
4. InitialConditions format and requirements changed. A single file can now be provided for multiple grids. SUEWS will approximate most (but not all) of the required initial conditions if values are unknown. (However, if detailed information about the initial conditions is known, this can still be provided to and used by SUEWS.)
5. Leaf area index calculations now use parameters provided for each vegetated surface (previously only the deciduous tree LAI development parameters were applied to all vegetated surfaces).
6. For compatibility with GIS, **the sign convention for longitude has been changed**. Now negative values are to the west, positive values are to the east. Note this appears to have been incorrectly coded in previous versions (but may not necessarily have been problematic).

7. Storage heat flux calculation adapted for shorter (sub-hourly) model time-step: hysteresis calculation now based on running means over the previous hour.
8. Improved error handling, including separate files for serious errors (problems.txt) and less critical issues (warnings.txt).
9. Edits to the manual.
10. New capabilities being developed, including two new options for calculating storage heat flux (AnOHM, ESTM) and modelling of carbon dioxide fluxes. These are currently under development and **should not be used** in Version 2017a.

12.6 Version 2016a (released 21 June 2016)

PDF Manual for v2016a

1. Major changes to the input file formats to facilitate the running of multiple grids and multiple years. Surface characteristics are provided in *SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt* and other input files are cross-referenced via codes or profile types.
2. The surface types have been altered:
 - Previously, grass surfaces were entered separately as irrigated grass and unirrigated grass surfaces, whilst the ‘unmanaged’ land cover fraction was assumed by the model to behave as unirrigated grass. There is now a single surface type for grass (total for irrigated plus unirrigated) and a new bare soil surface type.
 - The proportion of irrigated vegetation must now be specified for grass, evergreen trees and deciduous trees individually.
3. The entire model now runs at a time step specified by the user. Note that 5 min is strongly recommended. (Previously only the water balance calculations were done at 5 min with the energy balance calculations at 60 min).
4. Surface conductance now depends on the soil moisture under the vegetated surfaces only (rather than the total soil moisture for the whole study area as previously).
5. Albedo of evergreen trees and grass surfaces can now change with leaf area index as was previously possible for deciduous trees only.
6. New suggestions in Troubleshooting section.
7. Edits to the manual.
8. CBL model included.
9. SUEWS has been incorporated into UMEP

12.7 Version 2014b (released 8 October 2014)

PDF Manual for v2014b

These affect the run configuration if previously run with older versions of the model:

1. New input of three additional columns in the Meteorological input file (diffusive and direct solar radiation, and wind direction)
2. Change of input variables in InitialConditions.nml file. Note we now refer to CT as ET (ie. Evergreen trees rather than coniferous trees)
3. In GridConnectionsYYYY.txt, the site names should now be without the underscore (e.g S_m and not S_m_)

Other issues:

1. Number of grid areas that can be modelled (for one grid, one year 120; for one grid two years 80)
2. Comment about Time interval of input data
3. Bug fix: Column headers corrected in 5 min file
4. Bug fix: Surface state 60 min file - corrected to give the last 5 min of the hour (rather than cumulating through the hour)
5. Bug fix: units in the Horizontal soil water transfer
6. ErrorHints: More have been added to the problems.txt file.
7. Manual: new section on running the model appropriately
8. Manual: notation table updated
9. Possibility to add snow accumulation and melt: new paper

Järvi L, Grimmond CSB, Taka M, Nordbo A, Setälä H, and Strachan IB Version 2014: Development of the Surface Urban Energy and Water balance Scheme (SUEWS) for cold climate cities, *Geosci. Model Dev.* 7, 1691-1711, doi:10.5194/gmd-7-1691-Version 2014.

12.8 Version 2014a.1 (released 26 February 2014)

1. Please see the large number of changes made in the Version 2014a release.
2. This is a minor change to address installing the software.
3. Minor updates to the manual

12.9 Version 2014a (released 21 February 2014)

1. Bug fix: External irrigation is calculated as combined from automatic and manual irrigation and during precipitation events the manual irrigation is reduced to 60% of the calculated values. In previous version of the model, the irrigation was in all cases taken 60% of the calculated value, but now this has been fixed.
2. In previous versions of the model, irrigation was only allowed on the irrigated grass surface type. Now, irrigation is also allowed on evergreen and deciduous trees/shrubs surfaces. These are not however treated as separate surfaces, but the amount of irrigation is evenly distributed to the whole surface type in the modelled area. The amount of water is calculated using same equation as for grass surface (equation 5 in Järvi et al. Version 2011), and the fraction of irrigated trees/shrubs (relative to the area of tree/shrubs surface) is set in the gis file (See Table 4.11: SSss_YYYY.gis)
3. In the current version of the model, the user is able to adjust the leaf-on and leaf-off lengths in the Functional-Types. nml file. In addition, user can choose whether to use temperature dependent functions or combination of temperature and day length (advised to be used at high-latitudes)
4. In the gis-file, there is a new variable Alt that is the area altitude above sea level. If not known exactly use an approximate value.
5. Snow removal profile has been added to the HourlyProfileSSss_YYYY.txt. Not yet used!
6. Model time interval has been changed from minutes to seconds. Preferred interval is 3600 seconds (1 hour)
7. Manual correction: input variable Soil moisture said soil moisture deficit in the manual – word removed

8. Multiple compiled versions of SUEWS released. There are now users in Apple, Linux and Windows environments. So we will now release compiled versions for more operating systems (section 3).
9. There are some changes in the output file columns so please, check the respective table of each used output file.
10. Bug fix: with very small amount of vegetation in an area – impacted Phenology for LUMPS

12.10 Version 2013a

1. Radiation selection bug fixed
2. Aerodynamic resistance – when very low - no longer reverts to neutral (which caused a large jump) – but stays low
3. Irrigation day of week fixed
4. New error messages
5. min file – now includes a decimal time column – see Section 5.4 – Table 5.3

12.11 Version 2012b

1. Error message generated if all the data are not available for the surface resistance calculations
2. Error message generated if wind data are below zero plane displacement height.
3. All error messages now written to ‘Problem.txt’ rather than embedded in an ErrorFile. Note some errors will be written and the program will continue others will stop the program.
4. Default variables removed (see below). Model will stop if any data are problematic. File should be checked to ensure that reasonable data are being used. If an error occurs when there should not be one let us know as it may mean we have made the limits too restrictive.

Contents no longer used File defaultFclD=0.1 defaultPres=1013 defaultRH=50 defaultT=10 defaultU=3 RunControl.nml

- Just delete lines from file
- Values you had were likely different from these example value shown here

12.12 Version 2012a

1. Improved error messages when an error is encountered. Error message will generally be written to the screen and to the file ‘problems.txt’
2. Format of all input files have changed.
3. New excel spreadsheet and R programme to help prepare required data files. (Not required)
4. Format of coef flux (OHM) input files have changed.
 - This allows for clearer identification for users of the coefficients that are actually to be used
 - This requires an additional file with coefficients. These do not need to be adjusted but new coefficients can be added. We would appreciate receiving additional coefficients so they can be included in future releases – Please email Sue.
5. Storage heat flux (OHM) coefficients can be changed by

- time of year (summer, winter)
 - surface wetness state
6. New files are written: DailyState.txt
 - Provides the status of variables that are updated on a daily or basis or a snapshot at the end of each day.
 7. Surface Types
 - Clarification of surface types has been made. See GIS and OHM related files

12.13 Version 2011b

1. Storage heat flux (ΔQ_s) and anthropogenic heat flux (QF) can be set to be 0 W m^{-2}
2. Calculation of hydraulic conductivity in soil has been improved and HydraulicConduct in SUEWSInput.nml is replaced with name SatHydraulicConduct
3. Following removed from HeaderInput.nml
 - HydraulicConduct
 - GrassFractionIrrigated
 - PavedFractionIrrigated
 - TreeFractionIrrigated

The lower three are now determined from the water use behaviour used in SUEWS

1. Following added to HeaderInput.nml
 - SatHydraulicConduct
 - defaultQf
 - defaultQs
2. If ΔQ_s and QF are not calculated in the model but are given as an input, the missing data is replaced with the default values.
3. Added to SAHP input file
 - AHDIUPRF – diurnal profile used if EmissionsMethod = 1

Version 2012a this became obsolete OHM file (SSss_YYYY.ohm)

Acknowledgements

- Current contributors:

Name	Affiliation	Contributions
Dr Ting Sun, Current Lead Developer	University of Reading, UK	AnOHM; Documentation system; WRF-SUEWS coupling; SuPy (python wrapper of SUEWS)
Dr Leena Järvi, Lead Developer	University of Helsinki, Finland	Snow-related physics; Anthropogenic emission calculation, CO ₂
Prof C.S.B. Grimmond, Team Leader	University of Reading; previously, Indiana University, USA, King's College London, UK, University of British Columbia, Canada	OHM, Evaporation-Interception, Resistances, NARP, irrigation, anthropogenic heat, etc
Dr Fredrik Lindberg	Göteborg University, Sweden	UMEP-related work, NARP, ESTM
Dr Zhenkun Li	Shanghai Climate Centre, China	WRF-SUEWS coupling
Yihao Tang	University of Reading	Stability, air temperature
Dr Helen Ward, Past Lead Developer	University of Reading, UK	OHM improvement; Resistance calculation; Anthropogenic heat calculation

- Past Contributors:

Name	Affiliation	Contributions
Dr Shiho Onomura	Göteborg University, Sweden	BLUEWS, ESTM
Dr Thomas Loridan	King's College London, UK	NARP
Dr Brian Offerle	Indiana University, USA	ESTM, NARP

- Libraries/code that SUEWS uses as dependency:

Note: We gratefully acknowledge the libraries/code that SUEWS uses as dependency and greatly appreciate

their developers for the excellent work. Please let us know if any inappropriate use of these code and we will remove/modify the related parts accordingly.

Library	Comments
datetime-fortran	date and time related processing
minpack	AnOHM-related sinusoidal curve fitting
Recursive Fortran 95 quicksort routine	netCDF output for QGIS-compliant grid layout
Fortran Strings Module by Dr George Benthien	string processing

- Funding to support development:

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Newton/Met Office	CSSP-China
NERC	ClearfLo
NERC/Belmont	TRUC
H2020	UrbanFluxes
EPSRC	LoHCool
NERC	Independent Research Fellowship

λF Frontal area index

ΔQ_S Storage heat flux

BLUEWS Boundary Layer part of SUEWS

Fig. 14.1: Relation between BLUEWS and SUEWS

CDD Cooling degree days

GDD Growing degree days

HDD Heating degree days

Bldgs Building surface

- CBL** Convective boundary layer
- DEM** Digital Elevation Model
- DSM** Digital surface model
- DTM** Digital Terrain Model
- DecTr** Deciduous trees and shrubs
- EveTr** Evergreen trees and shrubs
- ESTM** Element Surface Temperature Method (Offerle et al.,2005 [*OGF2005*])
- Grass** Grass surface
- BSoil** Unmanaged land and/or bare soil
- Runoff** The water that drains freely off the impervious surface
- SoilStore** The water stored in the underlying soil that infiltrates from the pervious surface
- L↓** Incoming longwave radiation
- LAI** Leaf area index
- LUMPS** Local-scale Urban Meteorological Parameterization Scheme (Loridan et al. 2011 [*L2011*])
- MU** Parameters which must be supplied and must be specific for the site/grid being run.
- MD** Parameters which must be supplied and must be specific for the site/grid being run (but default values may be ok if these values are not known specifically for the site).
- O** Parameters that are optional, depending on the model settings in *RunControl.nml*. Set any parameters that are not used/not known to '-999'.
- L** Codes that are used to link between the input files. These codes are required but their values are completely arbitrary, providing that they link the input files in the correct way. The user should choose these codes, bearing in mind that the codes they match up with in column 1 of the corresponding input file must be unique within that file. Codes must be integers. Note that the codes must match up with column 1 of the corresponding input file, even if those parameters are not used (in which case set all columns except column 1 to '-999' in the corresponding input file), otherwise the model run will fail.
- NARP** Net All-wave Radiation Parameterization (Offerle et al. 2003 [*O2003*], Loridan et al. 2011 [*L2011*])
- OHM** Objective Hysteresis Model (Grimmond et al. 1991 [*G91OHM*], Grimmond & Oke 1999a [*GO99QS*], 2002 [*GO2002*])
- Paved** Paved surface
- Q*** Net all-wave radiation
- QE** Latent heat flux
- QF** Anthropogenic heat flux
- QH** Sensible heat flux
- SOLWEIG** The solar and longwave environmental irradiance geometry model (Lindberg et al. 2008 [*FL2008*], Lindberg and Grimmond 2011 [*FL2011*])
- SVF** Sky view factor
- θ Potential temperature
- tt** Time step of data
- UMEP** Urban Multi-scale Environmental Predictor

Water Water surface

WATCH The WATCH project has produced a large number of data sets which should be of considerable use in regional and global studies of climate and water. see [WATCH webpage](#)

zi Convective boundary layer height

References

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Symbols

ΔQS , **241**

λF , **241**

θ , **242**

A

a1
command line option, 45

a2
command line option, 45

a3
command line option, 45

absK
command line option, 156

absL
command line option, 156

ActivityProfWD
command line option, 46

ActivityProfWE
command line option, 46

AHMin_WD
command line option, 46

AHMin_WE
command line option, 47

AHSlope_Cooling_WD
command line option, 47

AHSlope_Cooling_WE
command line option, 47

AHSlope_Heating_WD
command line option, 47

AHSlope_Heating_WE
command line option, 47

albDecTr0
command line option, 140

AlbedoMax
command line option, 47

AlbedoMin
command line option, 48

albEveTr0

command line option, 140

albGrass0
command line option, 140

alpha
command line option, 48

alpha_enh
command line option, 52

Alt
command line option, 49

AnOHM_Ch
command line option, 49

AnOHM_Cp
command line option, 49

AnOHM_Kk
command line option, 50

AnthropogenicCode
command line option, 50

AreaWall
command line option, 50

B

BaseT
command line option, 50

BaseTe
command line option, 51

BaseTHDD
command line option, 51

beta
command line option, 51

beta_enh
command line option, 52

BiogenCO2Code
command line option, 53

Bldgs, **241**

BldgsState
command line option, 141

BLUEWS, **241**

BSoil, **242**

BSoilState
command line option, 141

BuildingName
command line option, 157

C

CBL, 242

CBLday(id)
command line option, 150

CBLuse
command line option, 19

CDD, 241

CDSMname
command line option, 157

CO2_included
command line option, 150

Code
command line option, 53

Code_Bldgs
command line option, 55

Code_BSoil
command line option, 55

Code_DecTr
command line option, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs1
command line option, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs2
command line option, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs3
command line option, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs4
command line option, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs5
command line option, 57

Code_ESTMClass_Paved1
command line option, 57

Code_ESTMClass_Paved2
command line option, 57

Code_ESTMClass_Paved3
command line option, 57

Code_EveTr
command line option, 57

Code_Grass
command line option, 58

Code_Paved
command line option, 58

Code_Water
command line option, 58

col
command line option, 157

command line option

a1, 45

a2, 45

a3, 45

absK, 156

absL, 156

ActivityProfWD, 46

ActivityProfWE, 46

AHMin_WD, 46

AHMin_WE, 47

AHSlope_Cooling_WD, 47

AHSlope_Cooling_WE, 47

AHSlope_Heating_WD, 47

AHSlope_Heating_WE, 47

albDecTr0, 140

AlbedoMax, 47

AlbedoMin, 48

albEveTr0, 140

albGrass0, 140

alpha, 48

alpha_enh, 52

Alt, 49

AnOHM_Ch, 49

AnOHM_Cp, 49

AnOHM_Kk, 50

AnthropogenicCode, 50

AreaWall, 50

BaseT, 50

BaseTe, 51

BaseTHDD, 51

beta, 51

beta_enh, 52

BiogenCO2Code, 53

BldgsState, 141

BSoilState, 141

BuildingName, 157

CBLday(id), 150

CBLuse, 19

CDSMname, 157

CO2_included, 150

Code, 53

Code_Bldgs, 55

Code_BSoil, 55

Code_DecTr, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs1, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs2, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs3, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs4, 56

Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs5, 57

Code_ESTMClass_Paved1, 57

Code_ESTMClass_Paved2, 57

Code_ESTMClass_Paved3, 57

Code_EveTr, 57

Code_Grass, 58

Code_Paved, 58

Code_Water, 58

col, 157

CondCode, 59

CRWMax, 59

CRWMin, 59

DaysSinceRain, 141
 DayWat(1), 59
 DayWat(2), 60
 DayWat(3), 60
 DayWat(4), 60
 DayWat(5), 60
 DayWat(6), 60
 DayWat(7), 61
 DayWatPer(1), 61
 DayWatPer(2), 61
 DayWatPer(3), 61
 DayWatPer(4), 61
 DayWatPer(5), 61
 DayWatPer(6), 62
 DayWatPer(7), 62
 decidCap0, 140
 DecTrState, 141
 DisaggMethod, 27
 DisaggMethodESTM, 29
 DrainageCoef1, 62
 DrainageCoef2, 62
 DrainageEq, 63
 DSMname, 157
 DSMPath, 157
 EF_umolCO2perJ, 64
 EmissionsMethod, 21
 Emissivity, 64
 EndDLS, 65
 EnEF_v_Jkm, 65
 EnergyUseProfWD, 65
 EnergyUseProfWE, 66
 EntrainmentType, 149
 ESTMCode, 66
 EveTrState, 141
 evolveTibld, 152
 FAI_Bldgs, 67
 FAI_DecTr, 67
 FAI_EveTr, 67
 Faut, 67
 FcEF_v_Jkm, 68
 FcEF_v_kgkm, 46
 fcd, 68
 FileCode, 25
 FileInputPath, 25
 FileOutputPath, 25
 FileSonde(id), 150
 FlowChange, 68
 Fr_Bldgs, 70
 Fr_Bsoil, 70
 Fr_DecTr, 70
 Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs1, 70
 Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs2, 70
 Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs3, 71
 Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs4, 71
 Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs5, 71
 Fr_ESTMClass_Paved1, 71
 Fr_ESTMClass_Paved2, 71
 Fr_ESTMClass_Paved3, 71
 Fr_EveTr, 72
 Fr_Grass, 72
 Fr_Paved, 72
 Fr_Water, 72
 Fraction1of8, 68
 Fraction2of8, 68
 Fraction3of8, 69
 Fraction4of8, 69
 Fraction5of8, 69
 Fraction6of8, 69
 Fraction7of8, 69
 Fraction8of8, 70
 FrFossilFuel_Heat, 72
 FrFossilFuel_NonHeat, 72
 G1, 73
 G2, 73
 G3, 73
 G4, 73
 G5, 73
 G6, 74
 gamq_gkgm, 74
 gamt_Km, 74
 GDD_1_0, 139
 GDD_2_0, 139
 GDDFull, 74
 GrassState, 141
 Grid, 74
 GridConnection1of8, 75
 GridConnection2of8, 75
 GridConnection3of8, 76
 GridConnection4of8, 76
 GridConnection5of8, 76
 GridConnection6of8, 76
 GridConnection7of8, 76
 GridConnection8of8, 77
 gsModel, 77
 GVF_out, 156
 H_Bldgs, 77
 H_DecTr, 77
 H_EveTr, 77
 heightgravity, 157
 IblldCHmod, 152
 id, 78
 Ie_a1, 78
 Ie_a2, 78
 Ie_a3, 78
 Ie_end, 78
 Ie_m1, 78
 Ie_m2, 79
 Ie_m3, 79

Ie_start, 79
ih, 79
imin, 79
InfiltrationRate, 80
InitialData_use, 149
InitialDataFileName, 150
Internal_albedo, 80
Internal_CHbld, 80
Internal_CHroof, 80
Internal_CHwall, 80
Internal_emissivity, 81
Internal_k1, 81
Internal_k2, 81
Internal_k3, 81
Internal_k4, 81
Internal_k5, 82
Internal_rhoCp1, 82
Internal_rhoCp2, 82
Internal_rhoCp3, 82
Internal_rhoCp4, 82
Internal_rhoCp5, 82
Internal_thick1, 83
Internal_thick2, 83
Internal_thick3, 83
Internal_thick4, 83
Internal_thick5, 83
InternalWaterUse, 84
IrrFr_DecTr, 84
IrrFr_EveTr, 84
IrrFr_Grass, 84
IrrigationCode, 84
it, 85
iy, 85
kdiff, 85
kdir, 85
kdown, 85
Kdown2d_out, 156
KdownZen, 28
KeepTstepFilesIn, 26
KeepTstepFilesOut, 27
Kmax, 86
Kup2d_out, 155
lai, 86
LAIEq, 86
LAIinitialDecTr, 140
LAIinitialEveTr, 140
LAIinitialGrass, 140
LAIMax, 86
LAIMin, 87
lat, 87
LBC_soil, 152
ldown, 87
Ldown2d_out, 155
LeafGrowthPower1, 87
LeafGrowthPower2, 88
LeafOffPower1, 88
LeafOffPower2, 88
LeavesOutInitially, 139
lng, 89
LUMPS_Cover, 89
LUMPS_DrRate, 89
LUMPS_MaxRes, 89
Lup2d_out, 155
MaxConductance, 90
MaxQFMetab, 90
min_respi, 52
MinQFMetab, 90
MultipleESTMFiles, 26
MultipleInitFiles, 26
MultipleMetFiles, 25
MultRainAmongN, 28
MultRainAmongNUpperI, 29
NARP_Trans, 91
ncMode, 29
nCol, 29
NetRadiationMethod, 20
nroom, 91
nRow, 29
OBS_SMCap, 91
OBS_SMDepth, 91
OBS_SoilNotRocks, 92
OHMCode_SummerDry, 92
OHMCode_SummerWet, 93
OHMCode_WinterDry, 93
OHMCode_WinterWet, 94
OHMIncQF, 22
OHMThresh_SW, 95
OHMThresh_WD, 96
onlyglobal, 154
OutInterval, 157
PavedState, 141
PipeCapacity, 96
PopDensDay, 97
PopDensNight, 97
PopProfWD, 97
PopProfWE, 97
porosity0, 140
PorosityMax, 98
PorosityMin, 98
Posture, 154
PrecipiLimAlb, 98
PrecipLimSnow, 98
pres, 98
q+_gkg, 101
q_gkg, 101
qe, 99
qf, 99
QF0_BEU_WD, 53

QF0_BEU_WE, 53
 QF_A_WD, 99
 QF_A_WE, 99
 QF_B_WD, 100
 QF_B_WE, 100
 QF_C_WD, 100
 QF_C_WE, 101
 qh, 101
 QH_Choice, 149
 qn, 101
 qs, 102
 RadMeltFactor, 102
 rain, 102
 RainAmongN, 28
 RainDisaggMethod, 28
 ResolutionFilesIn, 25
 ResolutionFilesInESTM, 25
 ResolutionFilesOut, 25
 resp_a, 52
 resp_b, 52
 RH, 102
 RoughLenHeatMethod, 23
 RoughLenMomMethod, 23
 row, 157
 RunForGrid, 156
 RunoffToWater, 102
 S1, 103
 S2, 103
 SatHydraulicCond, 103
 SDDFull, 103
 SMDMethod, 24
 snow, 104
 SnowAlb0, 145
 SnowClearingProfWD, 104
 SnowClearingProfWE, 104
 SnowCode, 105
 SnowDensBldgs, 145
 SnowDensBSoil, 145
 SnowDensDecTr, 145
 SnowDensEveTr, 145
 SnowDensGrass, 145
 snowDensMax, 105
 snowDensMin, 105
 SnowDensPaved, 144
 SnowDensWater, 145
 SnowFracBldgs, 144
 SnowFracBSoil, 144
 SnowFracDecTr, 144
 SnowFracEveTr, 144
 SnowFracGrass, 144
 SnowFracPaved, 144
 SnowFracWater, 144
 SnowInitially, 142
 SnowLimPatch, 105
 SnowLimRemove, 106
 SnowPackBldgs, 143
 SnowPackBSoil, 143
 SnowPackDecTr, 143
 SnowPackEveTr, 143
 SnowPackGrass, 143
 SnowPackPaved, 143
 SnowPackWater, 144
 SnowUse, 19
 SnowWaterBldgsState, 142
 SnowWaterBSoilState, 143
 SnowWaterDecTrState, 142
 SnowWaterEveTrState, 142
 SnowWaterGrassState, 143
 SnowWaterPavedState, 142
 SnowWaterWaterState, 143
 SoilDensity, 106
 SoilDepth, 107
 SoilstoreBldgsState, 138
 SoilstoreBSoilState, 139
 SoilStoreCap, 107
 SoilstoreDecTrState, 139
 SoilstoreEveTrState, 138
 SoilstoreGrassState, 139
 SoilstorePavedState, 138
 SoilTypeCode, 107
 SOLWEIG_ldown, 156
 SOLWEIGpoi_out, 154
 SOLWEIGUse, 20
 Sondeflag, 149
 StabilityMethod, 22
 StartDLS, 107
 StateLimit, 108
 StorageHeatMethod, 21
 StorageMax, 108
 StorageMin, 109
 SuppressWarnings, 27
 Surf_k1, 110
 Surf_k2, 111
 Surf_k3, 111
 Surf_k4, 111
 Surf_k5, 111
 Surf_rhoCp1, 111
 Surf_rhoCp2, 111
 Surf_rhoCp3, 112
 Surf_rhoCp4, 112
 Surf_rhoCp5, 112
 Surf_thick1, 112
 Surf_thick2, 112
 Surf_thick3, 113
 Surf_thick4, 113
 Surf_thick5, 113
 SurfaceArea, 110
 SVFPath, 158

SVFSuffix, 158
 Tair, 113
 tau_a, 113
 tau_f, 113
 tau_r, 114
 TCritic_Cooling_WD, 114
 TCritic_Cooling_WE, 114
 TCritic_Heating_WD, 114
 TCritic_Heating_WE, 114
 TDSMname, 158
 Temp_C0, 141
 TempMeltFactor, 115
 TH, 115
 Theat_fix, 152
 Theat_off, 152
 Theat_on, 152
 theta, 51
 Theta+_K, 115
 Theta_K, 115
 Tiair, 115
 Timezone, 115
 TL, 116
 Tmrt_out, 155
 ToBldgs, 116
 ToBSoil, 116
 ToDecTr, 116
 ToEveTr, 116
 ToGrass, 117
 ToPaved, 117
 ToRunoff, 117
 ToSoilStore, 117
 ToWater, 117
 TrafficRate_WD, 118
 TrafficRate_WE, 118
 TrafficUnits, 118
 TraffProfWD, 117
 TraffProfWE, 118
 TransMax, 158
 TransMin, 158
 Troad, 119
 Troof, 119
 Tstep, 24
 Tsurf, 119
 TsurfChoice, 151
 Twall, 119
 Twall_e, 119
 Twall_n, 120
 Twall_s, 120
 Twall_w, 120
 U, 120
 usevegdem, 154
 Wall_k1, 120
 Wall_k2, 121
 Wall_k3, 121
 Wall_k4, 121
 Wall_k5, 121
 Wall_rhoCp1, 121
 Wall_rhoCp2, 121
 Wall_rhoCp3, 122
 Wall_rhoCp4, 122
 Wall_rhoCp5, 122
 Wall_thick1, 122
 Wall_thick2, 122
 Wall_thick3, 123
 Wall_thick4, 123
 Wall_thick5, 123
 WaterDepth, 123
 WaterState, 142
 WaterUseMethod, 24
 WaterUseProfAutoWD, 123
 WaterUseProfAutoWE, 124
 WaterUseProfManuWD, 124
 WaterUseProfManuWE, 124
 wdir, 125
 WetThreshold, 125
 WithinGridBldgsCode, 125
 WithinGridBSoilCode, 126
 WithinGridDecTrCode, 126
 WithinGridEveTrCode, 126
 WithinGridGrassCode, 127
 WithinGridPavedCode, 127
 WithinGridWaterCode, 127
 WriteOutOption, 27
 Wsb, 150
 Wuh, 128
 xsmd, 128
 Year, 128
 z, 128
 z0, 129
 zd, 129
 zi0, 129
 CondCode
 command line option, 59
 CRWMax
 command line option, 59
 CRWMin
 command line option, 59
D
 DaysSinceRain
 command line option, 141
 DayWat(1)
 command line option, 59
 DayWat(2)
 command line option, 60
 DayWat(3)
 command line option, 60
 DayWat(4)

command line option, 60
 DayWat(5)
 command line option, 60
 DayWat(6)
 command line option, 60
 DayWat(7)
 command line option, 61
 DayWatPer(1)
 command line option, 61
 DayWatPer(2)
 command line option, 61
 DayWatPer(3)
 command line option, 61
 DayWatPer(4)
 command line option, 61
 DayWatPer(5)
 command line option, 61
 DayWatPer(6)
 command line option, 62
 DayWatPer(7)
 command line option, 62
 decidCap0
 command line option, 140
 DecTr, [242](#)
 DecTrState
 command line option, 141
 DEM, [242](#)
 DisaggMethod
 command line option, 27
 DisaggMethodESTM
 command line option, 29
 DrainageCoef1
 command line option, 62
 DrainageCoef2
 command line option, 62
 DrainageEq
 command line option, 63
 DSM, [242](#)
 DSMname
 command line option, 157
 DSMPath
 command line option, 157
 DTM, [242](#)
E
 EF_umolCO2perJ
 command line option, 64
 EmissionsMethod
 command line option, 21
 Emissivity
 command line option, 64
 EndDLS
 command line option, 65
 EnEF_v_Jkm

command line option, 65
 EnergyUseProfWD
 command line option, 65
 EnergyUseProfWE
 command line option, 66
 EntrainmentType
 command line option, 149
 ESTM, [242](#)
 ESTMCode
 command line option, 66
 EveTr, [242](#)
 EveTrState
 command line option, 141
 evolveTibld
 command line option, 152

F

FAI_Bldgs
 command line option, 67
 FAI_DecTr
 command line option, 67
 FAI_EveTr
 command line option, 67
 Faut
 command line option, 67
 FcEF_v_Jkm
 command line option, 68
 FcEF_v_kgkm
 command line option, 46
 fclld
 command line option, 68
 FileCode
 command line option, 25
 FileInputPath
 command line option, 25
 FileOutputPath
 command line option, 25
 FileSonde(id)
 command line option, 150
 FlowChange
 command line option, 68
 Fr_Bldgs
 command line option, 70
 Fr_Bsoil
 command line option, 70
 Fr_DecTr
 command line option, 70
 Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs1
 command line option, 70
 Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs2
 command line option, 70
 Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs3
 command line option, 71
 Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs4

- command line option, 71
- Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs5
 - command line option, 71
- Fr_ESTMClass_Paved1
 - command line option, 71
- Fr_ESTMClass_Paved2
 - command line option, 71
- Fr_ESTMClass_Paved3
 - command line option, 71
- Fr_EveTr
 - command line option, 72
- Fr_Grass
 - command line option, 72
- Fr_Paved
 - command line option, 72
- Fr_Water
 - command line option, 72
- Fraction1of8
 - command line option, 68
- Fraction2of8
 - command line option, 68
- Fraction3of8
 - command line option, 69
- Fraction4of8
 - command line option, 69
- Fraction5of8
 - command line option, 69
- Fraction6of8
 - command line option, 69
- Fraction7of8
 - command line option, 69
- Fraction8of8
 - command line option, 70
- FrFossilFuel_Heat
 - command line option, 72
- FrFossilFuel_NonHeat
 - command line option, 72

G

- G1
 - command line option, 73
- G2
 - command line option, 73
- G3
 - command line option, 73
- G4
 - command line option, 73
- G5
 - command line option, 73
- G6
 - command line option, 74
- gamq_gkgm
 - command line option, 74
- gamt_Km

- command line option, 74
- GDD, [241](#)
- GDD_1_0
 - command line option, 139
- GDD_2_0
 - command line option, 139
- GDDFull
 - command line option, 74
- Grass, [242](#)
- GrassState
 - command line option, 141
- Grid
 - command line option, 74
- GridConnection1of8
 - command line option, 75
- GridConnection2of8
 - command line option, 75
- GridConnection3of8
 - command line option, 76
- GridConnection4of8
 - command line option, 76
- GridConnection5of8
 - command line option, 76
- GridConnection6of8
 - command line option, 76
- GridConnection7of8
 - command line option, 76
- GridConnection8of8
 - command line option, 77
- gsModel
 - command line option, 77
- GVF_out
 - command line option, 156

H

- H_Bldgs
 - command line option, 77
- H_DecTr
 - command line option, 77
- H_EveTr
 - command line option, 77
- HDD, [241](#)
- heightgravity
 - command line option, 157

I

- IbldCHmod
 - command line option, 152
- id
 - command line option, 78
- Ie_a1
 - command line option, 78
- Ie_a2
 - command line option, 78

- Ie_a3
 - command line option, 78
 - Ie_end
 - command line option, 78
 - Ie_m1
 - command line option, 78
 - Ie_m2
 - command line option, 79
 - Ie_m3
 - command line option, 79
 - Ie_start
 - command line option, 79
 - ih
 - command line option, 79
 - imin
 - command line option, 79
 - InfiltrationRate
 - command line option, 80
 - InitialData_use
 - command line option, 149
 - InitialDataFileName
 - command line option, 150
 - Internal_albedo
 - command line option, 80
 - Internal_CHbld
 - command line option, 80
 - Internal_CHroof
 - command line option, 80
 - Internal_CHwall
 - command line option, 80
 - Internal_emissivity
 - command line option, 81
 - Internal_k1
 - command line option, 81
 - Internal_k2
 - command line option, 81
 - Internal_k3
 - command line option, 81
 - Internal_k4
 - command line option, 81
 - Internal_k5
 - command line option, 82
 - Internal_rhoCp1
 - command line option, 82
 - Internal_rhoCp2
 - command line option, 82
 - Internal_rhoCp3
 - command line option, 82
 - Internal_rhoCp4
 - command line option, 82
 - Internal_rhoCp5
 - command line option, 82
 - Internal_thick1
 - command line option, 83
 - Internal_thick2
 - command line option, 83
 - Internal_thick3
 - command line option, 83
 - Internal_thick4
 - command line option, 83
 - Internal_thick5
 - command line option, 83
 - InternalWaterUse
 - command line option, 84
 - IrrFr_DecTr
 - command line option, 84
 - IrrFr_EveTr
 - command line option, 84
 - IrrFr_Grass
 - command line option, 84
 - IrrigationCode
 - command line option, 84
 - it
 - command line option, 85
 - iy
 - command line option, 85
- ## K
- kdiff
 - command line option, 85
 - kdir
 - command line option, 85
 - kdown
 - command line option, 85
 - Kdown2d_out
 - command line option, 156
 - KdownZen
 - command line option, 28
 - KeepTstepFilesIn
 - command line option, 26
 - KeepTstepFilesOut
 - command line option, 27
 - Kmax
 - command line option, 86
 - Kup2d_out
 - command line option, 155
- ## L
- L, **242**
 - L↓, **242**
 - LAI, **242**
 - lai
 - command line option, 86
 - LAIEq
 - command line option, 86
 - LAInitialDecTr
 - command line option, 140
 - LAInitialEveTr

- command line option, 140
- LAIinitialGrass
 - command line option, 140
- LAIMax
 - command line option, 86
- LAImin
 - command line option, 87
- lat
 - command line option, 87
- LBC_soil
 - command line option, 152
- ldown
 - command line option, 87
- Ldown2d_out
 - command line option, 155
- LeafGrowthPower1
 - command line option, 87
- LeafGrowthPower2
 - command line option, 88
- LeafOffPower1
 - command line option, 88
- LeafOffPower2
 - command line option, 88
- LeavesOutInitially
 - command line option, 139
- lng
 - command line option, 89
- LUMPS, [242](#)
- LUMPS_Cover
 - command line option, 89
- LUMPS_DrRate
 - command line option, 89
- LUMPS_MaxRes
 - command line option, 89
- Lup2d_out
 - command line option, 155

M

- MaxConductance
 - command line option, 90
- MaxQFMetab
 - command line option, 90
- MD, [242](#)
- min_respi
 - command line option, 52
- MinQFMetab
 - command line option, 90
- MU, [242](#)
- MultipleESTMFiles
 - command line option, 26
- MultipleInitFiles
 - command line option, 26
- MultipleMetFiles
 - command line option, 25

- MultRainAmongN
 - command line option, 28
- MultRainAmongNUpperI
 - command line option, 29

N

- NARP, [242](#)
- NARP_Trans
 - command line option, 91
- ncMode
 - command line option, 29
- nCol
 - command line option, 29
- NetRadiationMethod
 - command line option, 20
- nroom
 - command line option, 91
- nRow
 - command line option, 29

O

- O, [242](#)
- OBS_SMCap
 - command line option, 91
- OBS_SMDepth
 - command line option, 91
- OBS_SoilNotRocks
 - command line option, 92
- OHM, [242](#)
- OHMCode_SummerDry
 - command line option, 92
- OHMCode_SummerWet
 - command line option, 93
- OHMCode_WinterDry
 - command line option, 93
- OHMCode_WinterWet
 - command line option, 94
- OHMIncQF
 - command line option, 22
- OHMThresh_SW
 - command line option, 95
- OHMThresh_WD
 - command line option, 96
- onlyglobal
 - command line option, 154
- OutInterval
 - command line option, 157

P

- Paved, [242](#)
- PavedState
 - command line option, 141
- PipeCapacity
 - command line option, 96

- PopDensDay
command line option, 97
- PopDensNight
command line option, 97
- PopProfWD
command line option, 97
- PopProfWE
command line option, 97
- porosity0
command line option, 140
- PorosityMax
command line option, 98
- PorosityMin
command line option, 98
- Posture
command line option, 154
- PrecipiLimAlb
command line option, 98
- PrecipLimSnow
command line option, 98
- pres
command line option, 98
- Q**
- q+_gkg
command line option, 101
- q_gkg
command line option, 101
- QE, **242**
- qe
command line option, 99
- QF, **242**
- qf
command line option, 99
- QF0_BEU_WD
command line option, 53
- QF0_BEU_WE
command line option, 53
- QF_A_WD
command line option, 99
- QF_A_WE
command line option, 99
- QF_B_WD
command line option, 100
- QF_B_WE
command line option, 100
- QF_C_WD
command line option, 100
- QF_C_WE
command line option, 101
- QH, **242**
- qh
command line option, 101
- QH_Choice
command line option, 149
- qn
command line option, 101
- qs
command line option, 102
- Qstar, **242**
- R**
- RadMeltFactor
command line option, 102
- rain
command line option, 102
- RainAmongN
command line option, 28
- RainDisaggMethod
command line option, 28
- ResolutionFilesIn
command line option, 25
- ResolutionFilesInESTM
command line option, 25
- ResolutionFilesOut
command line option, 25
- resp_a
command line option, 52
- resp_b
command line option, 52
- RH
command line option, 102
- RoughLenHeatMethod
command line option, 23
- RoughLenMomMethod
command line option, 23
- row
command line option, 157
- RunForGrid
command line option, 156
- Runoff, **242**
- RunoffToWater
command line option, 102
- S**
- S1
command line option, 103
- S2
command line option, 103
- SatHydraulicCond
command line option, 103
- SDDFull
command line option, 103
- SMDMethod
command line option, 24
- snow
command line option, 104
- SnowAlb0

- command line option, 145
- SnowClearingProfWD
 - command line option, 104
- SnowClearingProfWE
 - command line option, 104
- SnowCode
 - command line option, 105
- SnowDensBldgs
 - command line option, 145
- SnowDensBSoil
 - command line option, 145
- SnowDensDecTr
 - command line option, 145
- SnowDensEveTr
 - command line option, 145
- SnowDensGrass
 - command line option, 145
- snowDensMax
 - command line option, 105
- snowDensMin
 - command line option, 105
- SnowDensPaved
 - command line option, 144
- SnowDensWater
 - command line option, 145
- SnowFracBldgs
 - command line option, 144
- SnowFracBSoil
 - command line option, 144
- SnowFracDecTr
 - command line option, 144
- SnowFracEveTr
 - command line option, 144
- SnowFracGrass
 - command line option, 144
- SnowFracPaved
 - command line option, 144
- SnowFracWater
 - command line option, 144
- SnowInitially
 - command line option, 142
- SnowLimPatch
 - command line option, 105
- SnowLimRemove
 - command line option, 106
- SnowPackBldgs
 - command line option, 143
- SnowPackBSoil
 - command line option, 143
- SnowPackDecTr
 - command line option, 143
- SnowPackEveTr
 - command line option, 143
- SnowPackGrass
 - command line option, 143
- SnowPackPaved
 - command line option, 143
- SnowPackWater
 - command line option, 144
- SnowUse
 - command line option, 19
- SnowWaterBldgsState
 - command line option, 142
- SnowWaterBSoilState
 - command line option, 143
- SnowWaterDecTrState
 - command line option, 142
- SnowWaterEveTrState
 - command line option, 142
- SnowWaterGrassState
 - command line option, 143
- SnowWaterPavedState
 - command line option, 142
- SnowWaterWaterState
 - command line option, 143
- SoilDensity
 - command line option, 106
- SoilDepth
 - command line option, 107
- SoilStore, **242**
- SoilstoreBldgsState
 - command line option, 138
- SoilstoreBSoilState
 - command line option, 139
- SoilStoreCap
 - command line option, 107
- SoilstoreDecTrState
 - command line option, 139
- SoilstoreEveTrState
 - command line option, 138
- SoilstoreGrassState
 - command line option, 139
- SoilstorePavedState
 - command line option, 138
- SoilTypeCode
 - command line option, 107
- SOLWEIG, **242**
- SOLWEIG_ldown
 - command line option, 156
- SOLWEIGpoi_out
 - command line option, 154
- SOLWEIGUse
 - command line option, 20
- Sondeflag
 - command line option, 149
- StabilityMethod
 - command line option, 22
- StartDLS

- command line option, 107
- StateLimit
 - command line option, 108
- StorageHeatMethod
 - command line option, 21
- StorageMax
 - command line option, 108
- StorageMin
 - command line option, 109
- SuppressWarnings
 - command line option, 27
- Surf_k1
 - command line option, 110
- Surf_k2
 - command line option, 111
- Surf_k3
 - command line option, 111
- Surf_k4
 - command line option, 111
- Surf_k5
 - command line option, 111
- Surf_rhoCp1
 - command line option, 111
- Surf_rhoCp2
 - command line option, 111
- Surf_rhoCp3
 - command line option, 112
- Surf_rhoCp4
 - command line option, 112
- Surf_rhoCp5
 - command line option, 112
- Surf_thick1
 - command line option, 112
- Surf_thick2
 - command line option, 112
- Surf_thick3
 - command line option, 113
- Surf_thick4
 - command line option, 113
- Surf_thick5
 - command line option, 113
- SurfaceArea
 - command line option, 110
- SVF, 242
- SVFPath
 - command line option, 158
- SVFSuffix
 - command line option, 158
- T**
- Tair
 - command line option, 113
- tau_a
 - command line option, 113
- tau_f
 - command line option, 113
- tau_r
 - command line option, 114
- TCritic_Cooling_WD
 - command line option, 114
- TCritic_Cooling_WE
 - command line option, 114
- TCritic_Heating_WD
 - command line option, 114
- TCritic_Heating_WE
 - command line option, 114
- TDSMname
 - command line option, 158
- Temp_C0
 - command line option, 141
- TempMeltFactor
 - command line option, 115
- TH
 - command line option, 115
- Theat_fix
 - command line option, 152
- Theat_off
 - command line option, 152
- Theat_on
 - command line option, 152
- theta
 - command line option, 51
- Theta+_K
 - command line option, 115
- Theta_K
 - command line option, 115
- Tiair
 - command line option, 115
- Timezone
 - command line option, 115
- TL
 - command line option, 116
- Tmrt_out
 - command line option, 155
- ToBldgs
 - command line option, 116
- ToBSoil
 - command line option, 116
- ToDecTr
 - command line option, 116
- ToEveTr
 - command line option, 116
- ToGrass
 - command line option, 117
- ToPaved
 - command line option, 117
- ToRunoff
 - command line option, 117

ToSoilStore
 command line option, 117

ToWater
 command line option, 117

TrafficRate_WD
 command line option, 118

TrafficRate_WE
 command line option, 118

TrafficUnits
 command line option, 118

TraffProfWD
 command line option, 117

TraffProfWE
 command line option, 118

TransMax
 command line option, 158

TransMin
 command line option, 158

Troad
 command line option, 119

Troof
 command line option, 119

Tstep
 command line option, 24

Tsurf
 command line option, 119

TsurfChoice
 command line option, 151

tt, [242](#)

Twall
 command line option, 119

Twall_e
 command line option, 119

Twall_n
 command line option, 120

Twall_s
 command line option, 120

Twall_w
 command line option, 120

U

U
 command line option, 120

UMEP, [242](#)

usevegdem
 command line option, 154

W

Wall_k1
 command line option, 120

Wall_k2
 command line option, 121

Wall_k3
 command line option, 121

Wall_k4
 command line option, 121

Wall_k5
 command line option, 121

Wall_rhoCp1
 command line option, 121

Wall_rhoCp2
 command line option, 121

Wall_rhoCp3
 command line option, 122

Wall_rhoCp4
 command line option, 122

Wall_rhoCp5
 command line option, 122

Wall_thick1
 command line option, 122

Wall_thick2
 command line option, 122

Wall_thick3
 command line option, 123

Wall_thick4
 command line option, 123

Wall_thick5
 command line option, 123

WATCH, [243](#)

Water, [243](#)

WaterDepth
 command line option, 123

WaterState
 command line option, 142

WaterUseMethod
 command line option, 24

WaterUseProfAutoWD
 command line option, 123

WaterUseProfAutoWE
 command line option, 124

WaterUseProfManuWD
 command line option, 124

WaterUseProfManuWE
 command line option, 124

wdir
 command line option, 125

WetThreshold
 command line option, 125

WithinGridBldgsCode
 command line option, 125

WithinGridBSoilCode
 command line option, 126

WithinGridDecTrCode
 command line option, 126

WithinGridEveTrCode
 command line option, 126

WithinGridGrassCode
 command line option, 127

WithinGridPavedCode
command line option, 127

WithinGridWaterCode
command line option, 127

WriteOutOption
command line option, 27

Wsb
command line option, 150

Wuh
command line option, 128

X

xsmc
command line option, 128

Y

Year
command line option, 128

Z

z
command line option, 128

z0
command line option, 129

zd
command line option, 129

zi, [243](#)

zi0
command line option, 129